

**ADSORPTION, KINETICS AND THERMODYNAMICS
STUDIES ON REMEDIATION OF DYES USING
HALLOYSITE NANOTUBES AND UNMODIFIED CLAY
MINERALS**

A Thesis

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements for Award of the Degree of

DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY

in

NANO SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

by

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MUKKA, DAKSHINA KANNADA, INDIA

March 2021

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Name of Course	DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY in NANO SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
Title of Thesis	ADSORPTION, KINETICS AND THERMODYNAMICS STUDIES ON REMEDIATION OF DYES USING HALLOYSITE NANOTUBES AND UNMODIFIED CLAY MINERALS.
Name of the Guide	Dr. Prasad P.
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Acknowledgements

From the innermost depths of my heart I praise Almighty for this work has been accomplished by His everlasting mercy and abundant compassion.

This thesis of mine was possible only due to the incessant prayers, guidance, support, cooperation, assistance, encouragement and good wishes of a number of people to whom I owe a great debt of gratitude. I feel the presence of unseen hands of GOD in providing me with people, material, enlightenment and opportunities to complete the research work without any hassle. I bow my head to him for the innumerable blessings showered on me and my family.

With a grateful heart I am immensely pleased to place on record of gratitude to my research guide, **Dr. Prasad P.**, Professor, Centre for Nano Science and Technology, Srinivas University College of Engineering and Technology, Mangaluru, for giving me an opportunity to complete doctoral studies in his research group, for his invaluable, meticulous and untiring guidance and positive criticism of this research work.

I am very much thankful to Shri. CA. A. Raghavendra Rao, Honourable Chancellor, Srinivas University, Dr. A. Shrinivasa Rao, Honourable Pro-Chancellor, Srinivas University, for providing the infrastructure facility to carry out my research work comfortably. I thank Dr. P. Shreeramana Aithal, Honourable Vice-Chancellor, Srinivas University, Dr. Anil Kumar, Honourable Registrar, Srinivas University, **Dr. Srinivasa Mayya D.**, Honourable Registrar Evaluation, Srinivas University, and Principal, Srinivas Institute of Technology for their support and motivation.

Fervently and humbly, I acknowledge the genuine co-operation, inspiration and affection offered by **Dr. Syed Akheel Ahmed**, Professor of Chemistry, Department of Studies in Chemistry, University of Mysore, Manasagangothri, Mysore, India right from the initiation of the work to the preparation of the manuscript. The present work bears at every stage the impression of his wise counsel and concrete suggestions and criticisms and of meticulous attention to details. It is indeed a rare privilege for me to work under his enduring inspiration and indomitable spirit.

A great deal of credit goes to my wife Mrs. Shaheenbanu, my son Mohammed Yousuf, my beloved parents, Haji. Jamalasab Ukkund and Hajah. Ayesha, my sisters Rameeza, Jameela and Anjum Kouser who are behind all my success and without their support I would not have reached this stage.

It gives me immense pleasure to express my deep sense of reverence and gratefulness to Mrs. Ayesha Nasreen, Dr. Syed Raihan Taqui, Dr. Noeman, Dr. Usman, Ms. Bhavna Alke, Mrs. Apoorva Udupa, Dr. Darshan, Mr. Raghunandan G., Mr. Adarsh D. P., Ms. Abhinaya, Mr. Yashwanth, Mr. Vinay B. K., Mr. Sulthan M., and Raghavendra M. J., for their kind help during my tenure as a research scholar.

I am also greatly indebted to Dr. Savitha M. B., Associate Professor, Department of Chemistry and Research Centre, Sahyadri College of Engineering and Management, Adyar, Mangaluru for her support throughout my research work. I also place in record my appreciation for the encouragement from Mrs. Bhavya M. S., and Mr. Naveen Kumar J. R., my fellow researchers who were with me from the beginning and have been a great support and have helped me timely in all my hardships. I also extend my sincere thanks to Mr. Chethan and Mr. Kiran Montero, Srinivas College Pharmacy, Valachil.

The author thanks Directorate of Minorities, Govt. of Karnataka, Bangalore for the research fellowship to carry out the research work. I thank the authorities of IISc Bangalore, University of Mysore, Mangalore University, SJEC Mysore, and NITK, Surathkal for permitting me to carry out literature survey and analysis of research samples throughout my research work.

Mr. Shareefraju J. Ukkund

LIST OF SYMBOLS AND ABBREVIATIONS

α	: Brouers-Sotolongo isotherm constant
A_{RP}	: Redlich-Peterson constant (mg^{-1})
B_{RP}	: Redlich-Peterson constant (L g^{-1})
b_{TO}	: Toth isotherm constant (mg g^{-1})
β_{VS}	: Vieth-Sladek isotherm constant
χ^2	: Chi-squared
C_o	: Initial concentration
C_e	: Equilibrium concentration
ΔG^0	: Standard free energy
ΔH^0	: Enthalpy change
ΔS^0	: Entropy change
g	: Redlich-Peterson isotherm constant
K_a	: Langmuir constant (L mg^{-1})
K_{ad}	: Dubinin-Radushkevich constant ($\text{mol}^2\text{k}^{-1}\text{J}^{-2}$)
K_{BS}	: Brouers-Sotolongo isotherm constant
K_F	: Freundlich constant related to adsorption capacity (mg g^{-1})
K_J	: Jovanovic isotherm constant
K_{rp}	: Radke-Prausnitz isotherm model exponent
K_{VS}	: Vieth-Sladek isotherm constant
m_{rp}	: Radke-Prausnitz isotherm model exponent
n_F	: Heterogeneity factor (mg L^{-1}) ^{-1/n}
n_{TO}	: Toth isotherm constant (L mg^{-1})
R_L	: Separation factor
R^2	: Correlation coefficient
q_e	: Adsorption capacity (mg L^{-1})
Q_m	: Maximum adsorption capacity (mg L^{-1})
q_t	: Adsorption capacity at time 't' (mg L^{-1})
q_s	: Dubinin-Radushkevich constant (mg g^{-1})

DR13	: Direct red 13
FFED	: Fractional factorial experimental design
FTIR	: Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy
NIS	: Nutraceutical industrial spent
NIFGS	: Nutraceutical industrial fenugreek seed spent
NISPS	: Nutraceutical industrial saw palmetto spent
NITRS	: Nutraceutical industrial turmeric root spent
NITTS	: Nutraceutical industrial tribulus terrestris spent
SEM	: Scanning electron microscopy
SSE	: Sum of square errors
TIE	: Textile industrial effluent
BNT/Bent	: Bentonite
HNT	: Halloysite Nanotubes
MNT/Mt	: Montmorillonite
KAO/KAL	: Kaolinite
O/K	
NP	: Nanoparticles
DSSC	: Dye Sensitized Solar Cell
CNT	: Carbon Nanotube
SWCNT	: Single Walled Carbon Nanotube

ADSORPTION, KINETICS AND THERMODYNAMICS STUDIES ON REMEDIATION OF DYES USING HALLOYSITE NANOTUBES AND UNMODIFIED CLAY MINERALS

SYNOPSIS

1. Introduction

The ever-increasing population and living standard have created an increasing demand for textiles and clothing - one of the primary needs of human beings. Dyes have a long history of invention and development constitutes an important component of our daily lives. The magnitude and growth of dye industry is intricately linked to that of the Indian textile industry which produced an astonishing 46.1 million Kgs of fabric in 2014 and used billions of liters of water leading to the unprecedented demand to address the issues of carbon and water foot prints of textile industry. Bringing down water footprint and carbon footprint is the ultimate concern for sustainable development of world's textile industry. Amongst the existing many industries, textile industries are considered as one amongst the top ten most polluting industries. Predictions about the rapid growth of the textile industry in coming decades due to several factors including growing population, increasing disposable income, and changing consumer trends will present new challenges to the scientists, technologist and policy makers to find new avenues.

Textile industries use varieties of chemicals and are one of the major consumers of dyes. Reactive dyes are the most prominent classes of chemicals which are used extensively in textile industries. Most of the reactive dyes come under the category of azo dyes. Azo dyes have a high degree of chemical and photolytic stability and this property is of great concern for pollution abatement. Azo dyes toxicity is generally not because of the dye itself, but due to its biotransformation and/or degradation product(s) which display high level of acute and chronic toxicity and carcinogenicity

A large number of techniques, methods and procedures are used for the disposal of effluents. They can be broadly classified as physical, chemical, and biological techniques and these are applied to treat effluents containing dyes and heavy metals. However, they have limitations and disadvantages for one reason or the other. Adsorption techniques, of late are gaining prominence due to their efficiency in the removal of pollutants that are otherwise too stable for conventional methods.

1.2 Overview

About the thesisin brief

To address the daunting task of textile industrial effluents which releases about 28,000 tons of dyes every year into the environment – a simple low-cost and low energy technique, namely, adsorption is used using the adsorbents which are abundantly available in large quantities. Two classes of adsorbents, namely, inorganic materials and agro-based biomass are used as eco-friendly and low materials for the remediation of toxic dyes from the industrial effluents. To understand the behavior of the adsorbents and exploring the possibilities of extending to use clean technology; the following minerals are selected for my study: bentonite, kaolin light, montmorillonite K10 and halloysite nanotube. I have selected three dyes which are used extensively in the textile industries in India. They are; Direct Blue 15, Direct Red 13 and Brilliant Green. The former two dyes belong to bis azo dye class of compounds and the latter, namely, brilliant green belongs to the triarylmethane dyes class of compounds. The outline of the thesis is presented here for clarity and ready reference. Each unit of the thesis is presented as an independent unit and culminates with the relevant references.

1.3 Structure of chapters

About the chapters.....in brief

PART A

Chapter 1 presents an overview of the environmental pollution caused by major industries with a reference to textile industries and nutraceutical industries. Remediation strategy of dyes from textile industrial effluent has been presented using halloysite nanotubes and abundantly available unmodified clay minerals which are eco-friendly and cost-effective.

PART B

This part consists of two chapters and devoted to the remediation studies using halloysite nanotubes.

Chapter 2 describes a novel laboratory scale experiments are designed to allude to the concept of Circular Economy (CE) through remediation of Direct Blue 15 (DB15) dye using abundantly available and nontoxic halloysite nanotubes (HNT) and their application to textile industrial effluent (TIE). The DB15 adsorbed-HNT “sludge” was used as reinforcing material along with plastic waste for the fabrication of composites. To understand the phenomena of DB15 adsorption on HNT as a prelude to commercialization; various factors, namely, pH, adsorbate initial concentration, adsorbent dosage, and temperature were experimentally studied. To estimate the adsorption capacity of HNT, nine isotherm models were studied. Brouers-Sotolongo adsorption isotherm model was found to be the best fit. The predominant mechanism for the overall rate of for a multi-step dye adsorption process fits best to pseudo-second-order reaction. Mechanistic studies relate mass transfer phenomena were more likely to be dominant over diffusion process. The study of the thermodynamic parameters reveals that the process is physisorption. SEM and FTIR studies suggest the adsorption of the dye on HNT. Statistical optimization of process parameters were carried out.

The interactions between the HNT as adsorbent and DB15 dye as adsorbate showed experimental equilibrium (q_e) value of 96.00 mg g⁻¹ at pH 2 and 69.00 mg g⁻¹ at almost neutral pH. To understand the process of adsorption, nine isotherm models were studied. The adsorption follows Brouers-Sotolongo model. The interactions between HNT and DB15 are physical in nature and follows psuedo-second-order kinetics. Contact time, dye concentration, dosage and initial pH of the solution have profound influence on adsorption process. The dye-modified HNT has the potential as reinforcing material for the fabrication of the composites using plastic waste. Preliminary investigations gave encouraging results.

Chapter 3 presents experimental investigations carried out using halloysite nanotubes (HNT), a relatively low-cost nanomaterial abundantly available with least toxicity for the removal of brilliant green dye from aqueous media is reported. Factors affecting adsorption

studies were carried out to assess the adsorption capacity, the kinetics and the equilibrium thermodynamics. All the experiments were designed at about pH 7. The Toth isotherm model fits best amongst nine isotherm models studied. Kinetic studies data conformed to pseudo-second-order model. Mechanistic studies suggest that the rate controlling step is predominantly dominated by intraparticle diffusion. Scanning electron microscopy and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy were used in characterizing the adsorbent. Process optimization was carried out using Response Surface Methodology (RSM) through two-level Fractional Factorial Experimental Design (FEED) to study the influence of parameters on the process of adsorption. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to study the combined effect of the parameters. Possibilities of the use of dye-adsorbed HNT (“sludge”) for the fabrication of the composites using plastic waste are suggested.

The interactions between the HNT as adsorbent and BG dye as adsorbate showed experimental equilibrium (q_e) value of 91.00 mg g⁻¹ at pH 2 and 84.00 mg g⁻¹ at almost neutral pH. To understand the process of adsorption, nine isotherm models were studied. The adsorption follows Toth isotherm model. The interactions between HNT and BG were physical in nature and follow second-order kinetics. Contact time, dye concentration, dosage and initial pH of the solution have profound influence on adsorption process. The dye-modified HNT has the potential as reinforcing material for the fabrication of the composites using plastic waste.

PART C

This part consists of two chapters and devoted to the studies on unmodified clay minerals for remediation of dyes in textile industrial effluent.

Chapter 4 explores first-ever study on the potential use of low-cost, abundantly available, eco-friendly and unmodified bentonite (Bent), montmorillonite K10 (Mt) and kaolin light (K) as adsorbents for the remediation of Direct red 13 (DR13), a bisazo dye, from textile industrial effluent (TIE) is reported. The parameters affecting the adsorption capacity, kinetics and equilibrium were evaluated. Toth isotherm model was found to be best fit for the dye uptake process. The predominant kinetic mechanism fits best to pseudo-second-order reaction. Film diffusion studies indicated that the external mass transfer phenomena were

more likely to be dominant over the diffusion process. The low ΔH° values indicate that the process of adsorption is physical in nature. Weak interactions like Van der Waal forces and hydrogen bonds play major roles as supported by FT-IR analysis. Statistical model was developed for optimization of adsorption processes. Prospects on the use of dye-adsorbed clay mineral for the fabrication of composites are reported.

The adsorption capacity of Bent and Mt obtained from the quadratic model developed for process optimization gave values of 801 mg g^{-1} and 436 mg g^{-1} and follows Toth's isotherm. The kinetic, mechanistic and thermodynamic studies confirm that the process is physisorption and follows second-order kinetics with a multi-step diffusion route. A broad range of pH 4 to 10 for the remediation of DR13 dye on Bent and Mt is encouraging. The high removal efficiency among studied clay minerals, followed the order Bent > Mt >>> K. The dye-adsorbed Bent and Mt minerals obtained as "sludge" can be used as filler/reinforcing materials for the fabrication of composites using plastic waste. The detailed study on the composites is in progress in our laboratory.

Chapter 5 examines the inexpensive unmodified clay minerals for the first-ever study on the potential use of low-cost, abundantly available, eco-friendly and unmodified bentonite (Bent), montmorillonite K10 (Mt) and kaolin light (K) as adsorbents for the remediation of Brilliant Green (BG), a triarylmethane dye, from textile industrial effluent (TIE) is reported. The parameters affecting the adsorption capacity, kinetics and equilibrium were evaluated. Dubinin-Radushkevich isotherm model was found to be best fit for the dye uptake process. The predominant kinetic mechanism fits best to pseudo-second-order reaction. Film diffusion studies indicated that the external mass transfer phenomena were more likely to be dominant over the diffusion process. The low ΔH° values indicate that the process of adsorption is physical in nature. Weak interactions like Van der Waal forces and hydrogen bonds play major roles as supported by FT-IR analysis. Statistical model was developed for optimization of adsorption processes. Prospects on the use of dye-adsorbed clay mineral for the fabrication of composites are reported.

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PART D

This part consists of two chapters and devoted to the studies on applications of nanomaterials for remediation of dyes in textile industrial effluent.

Chapter 6 examines the Photocatalytic dye remediation of Methylene Violet by using nanomaterials like NiO/CdS nanoparticles and carbon nanotubes (CNT). The nanomaterials were mixed and made NiO/CdS-CNT nanocomposites. On comparing the efficacy of both the nanoparticles, the results were almost similar, except the CdS nanoparticles shows faster degradation rates when compared to the NiO nanoparticles.

Chapter 7 explores the use of toxic dyes such as Azobenzene for commercial applications among which solar cells were of primary interest. The Azobenzene dye can be utilized to coat on the surface of the solar cells which will increase the solar radiations absorption capacity of the solar cells. These dyes can be utilized in Dye Sensitized Solar Cells (DSSCs) which are gaining high importance in recent times. The chapter describes the use of nanomaterials TiO₂ nanoparticles and carbon nanotubes for their excellent electronic properties. TiO₂ nanoparticles acted as photocatalyst and whereas CNTs boosted conductivity and also showed the ability of their use as capacitors in the device. The solar cell efficiency was tested and found effective.

PART E

This part outlines the major conclusions and scope of the future work.

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Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

Textile companies are considered as one of the top ten most contaminating companies [1]. Textile manufacturing is one of the major areas which produce astonishing 60 million tons of fabric utilising up to 9 trillion gallons of water annually [2]. This huge scale of water consumption by the industry is ultimately key component for creating pollution. Bringing down water supply and carbon footprint is the ultimate fear for sustainable progress of global textile industry [2]. Textile industries use varied varieties of chemicals and are one of the major consumers of dyes. Reactive dyes are the most prominent classes of chemicals which are used extensively. Most of the reactive dyes come under the category of azo dyes. Azo dyes have got excellent chemical and photolytic firmness and this property is of great concern for pollution abatement [3].

Twenty first century is an era characterized by global change that stems from the interdependence between development and the environment. The mushrooming growth of industries, non-planned chemical based agricultural practices and ever-increasing number of vehicles on the roads has contributed substantially to the production and emission of myriad of chemicals and other reagents possessing variegated properties. Associated with these is the never-ending-list of waste materials generated, which are mostly toxic and a large number which are hazardous. These materials which are discharged into environment in substantial amounts can be broadly classified into inorganics, organics and organo-metallics. This is responsible for the degradation of our environment and is posing serious threats to the health and disruption of our ecosystem.

Dyes manufacturing industries is one amongst the top ten polluting industries of the world. As of now, no data is available on the precise quantity of yearly producing of organic dyes globally. Nevertheless, more than hundreds of thousands varieties of largely obtainable dyes available and global production of nearly 1 million tons has been reported yearly in the literature. It is approximated that 90% of the entire dyes manufactured will end up in fabrics, and the left out part is utilised in leather, paper, plastic, and chemical industry. It is also approximated that 280 thousand tons of textile dyes is released as effluent globally annually. According to a new study by the Freedonia Group, a Cleveland-based consulting firm, Asia-

Pacific region is said to lead the production and increase its market share to about 50% of the world's demand by 2013. The global market of dyes and organic stain is anticipated to raise 6% annually to reach nearly \$25 billion in 2023 from \$14.5 billion in 2014, as per the new Freedonia Group report.

Dyes are toxic in nature and adversely affect the water bodies. They are known to cause gene mutation in humans and host of other skin diseases. They reduce the intake, development and fertilization rates. They cause damage to liver, spleen, kidney and the heart .Owing to their aromatic structures along with multiple functional groups they are biologically non degradable and highly stable. They are the most hazardous class of chemical compounds found in effluents coming from food, textile, paper, rubber and plastic industry. These effluents are directly let into the water bodies thereby polluting them severely. Apart from damaging the aquatic flora they make the water unfit for human and animal consumption. The World Bank approximates that nearly 20% of industrial water contamination arrives from textile industry.

The present-day technologies for colour removal are divided into three categories, viz chemical, physical and biological approaches. Recently numerous physico-chemical decolourization routes are established, naming membrane process, electrochemical routes, reverse osmosis, biotic treatments, to name a few. Nevertheless, these routes are discriminatory, costly and require distinct setup. The decolouration of waste by the elimination of dyes via a marketable system is still an important issue faced by the textile manufacturing plants. Amid the mentioned routes, adsorption techniques are proven to be the utmost active and promised technique ensuring widespread prospective applications in both water and wastewater treatment.

1.1 Major Challenges of Textile Industries

Worldwide textile manufacturing units are presently dealing with crucial challenges, such as high rivalry, excess-capacity, dropping profits, and increased ecological considerations. This has outcome in shortage of funds for raised expenses especially in the direction of R&D and waste-water management. Hence, cost-effective elimination of colour and harmfulness from wastes becomes an important issue. The limitations and disadvantages of biological, chemical and physical techniques, methods and procedures led to the resurgence of adsorption as a technique and as a tool of paramount importance. Adsorption

routes are recently receiving importance due to high effectiveness in the removal of contaminants that are otherwise highly stable for conservative routes [4].

1.2 Azo Dyes - Revisited

Azo dyes account for about 70% of total world dye production, thereby contributing to the largest spectrum of colored azo dyes [5]. A large portion of about 20% of the unconsumed dyes due to lack of sophisticated technology and/or inherent problems faced during processing in the industrial effluent causes many aesthetic problems besides creating serious health risks by their toxicity to aquatic organisms and humans [6-8].

Azo dyes exhibit high molar extinction coefficient which causes a reasonable change in color at as low as 1 ppm concentration [9]. It also affects the aquatic ecosystem by limiting light penetration. Azo dyes toxicity is generally due to its biotransformation into primary amines [6, 10]. I have chosen two groups of two bis azo dyes; namely, Direct Blue 15 (DB15), Brilliant Green (BG) and Direct Red 13 (DR13). The structures of all three dyes are shown in the Figures 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3.

Figure 1.1: Structure of Direct Blue 15

Figure 1.2: Structure of Brilliant Green

Figure 1.3: Structure of Direct Red 13

1.3 The Techniques, Methods, and Procedures

A large number of techniques, methods and procedures used are of varied types for the disposal of effluents. They can be broadly classified as physical, chemical, and biological routes and these are used for effluent treatments of dyes and heavy metals present in effluent. Physical routes have two serious limitations; first it is difficult to scale to industrial output and second, harmfulness of dyes yet remains essentially unresolved [11-14]. The chemical methods for disposal of effluents are not only expensive, but add on to the E- factor. Besides, the high cost limits the commercial feasibility [15-25]. Biological treatment has the advantage of mineralization of the pollutant, resulting in most of the cases a complete detoxification but slowness of the process, limits its field level application [26-30].

1.4 Adsorption, Biosorption, and Biosorbent

Adsorption is bulk transfer between the solid and the liquid at the interphase on a two-dimensional surface. Biosorption differs from adsorption as the mass transfer phenomena involve the removal or separation of constituents from sample by biotic material. Biosorbents could be both living (beyond the scope of the thesis) and dead biomass. In majority of cases the linkage established between the adsorbent and the adsorbate is a surface complex [31-34] involving such functional groups as $-OH$, $-COOH$, $-SH$, to mention a few. It is used as a successful analytical technique to isolate and recover toxic and/or hazardous substances, precious metals, and other materials. It is being very selective under the operating conditions. Comparatively, it has advantages over other separation techniques, including; apparent efficiency without discharging any harmful by-products, cost-effective, eco-friendly, low energy consumption, flexibility at field operations analogous to conventional ion exchange technology and easy to scale up from laboratory to field level [35-39]. In the

field of adsorption studies appropriate selection of the adsorbent is of paramount importance.

An ideal adsorbent under the conditions needed should have the following characteristics:

- It should be accessible in plenty and cost effective
- It should have lower usage so that it won't be in demand
- It should not require any pre-treatments and readily available
- It should have optimum pore organization as to permit extreme adsorption
- It should be amenable to modest and low cost technology to recycle the sludge/contaminated biomass formed after the remediation

1.5 Nanoclays: The Promising Adsorbents

Nanoparticles are potentially useful in textiles as a good adsorbent [40]. The nanoclay materials selected for my present study include montmorillonite nanoclay and halloysite nanoclay as they are commercially available on a large scale with required consistent properties. Our research school has used nanoclay materials for the fabrication of polymer composites and the results are encouraging. Use of nanoclay as an adsorbent improves the dye adsorption capability. The dye adsorbed nanoclay commonly known as “sludge” can be used as a filler material. Our research school is engaged in carrying out this line of research study. The adsorbents utilised in this research work are Halloysite nanotube (HNT), Montmorillonite nanoclay (MNC/Mt), Bentonite nanoclay (BNT/Bent) and Kaolinite (KALO/K). The structures of these adsorbents are depicted in the Figures 1.4, 1.5 1.6 and 1.7.

Figure 1.4: The lattice structure of Halloysite

Figure 1.5: The lattice structure of Montmorillonite

Figure 1.6: The lattice structure of Bentonite

Figure 1.7: The lattice structure of Kaolinite

1.6 Scientific Relevance

Waste can be converted to wealth. It can be a way to increase the eminence of life of the urban poor. Increased migration to the cities makes urban waste management extremely difficult. Waste minimization should therefore be the new mantra. The research should be targeted keeping in view bio-based economy which has three important elements, namely: economics, environmental aspect and social responsibility. The strength for the research activity is originated from the biotic based cost effectiveness which imitates the natural environment – recover, re-use and re-generate are the areas which will be explored to find an effective solution for overcoming the menace of spent generated every year by the nutraceutical industry. Hence it is proposed to use the waste streams and develop eco-friendly and cost effective process. It is envisaged that the products thus produced would be both economically viable and socially relevant.

1.7 Social Relevance

Environmental pollution and protection are the two major issues faced by us in the twenty-first century. Industrial revolution has ensured economic well-being but unfortunately at the cost of environment. Each year millions tons of solid, liquid and gaseous effluents are released causing large scale of air, water and land pollution. Sustainable development thus remains an illusion. Thus, the present work drives home the need for remediation of dyes from industrial effluents and to study the resultant “sludge” as filler/reinforcing substance for

the production of compounds. Transfer of waste to wealth is a new paradigm as zero pollution is literally unattainable.

1.8 Scope of Research on Nanoclay

Survey of literature revealed that, only a little effort has been made to utilize nanoclay for adsorbing the toxic dyes from textile industrial effluent and making use of resultant sludge for making composites. The major advantage of adsorption technology using nanoclay is its efficiency in decreasing the quantity of dyes to lower stages. Additionally, Nanoclays are advantageous over traditional approaches include: great effectiveness, reduction of biochemical sludge, redevelopment of bio-sorbent, no supplementary nutrient necessity and probability of dye recovery. The application of adsorption in ecological treatment has developed a substantial investigation area in the past 10 years.

- Adsorption of dyes from aqueous samples is a comparatively novel method that has demonstrated very encouraging in the elimination of pollutants from aqueous wastes.
- Adsorbent materials derived from nanoclay can be utilized for the active elimination and regaining of dyes from industrial effluents.
- Little efforts have been made to use nanoclay for the elimination of pollutants from the effluents.
- The large surface area of nanoclay and tendency to retain anionic dyes such as azo dyes can be proved to be potential adsorbent.

1.9 Literature Survey

Survey of literature revealed that limited research work has been carried out for using nanoclay as adsorbent in removing dyes from aqueous solutions. Massaro et al. [41] have developed Halloysite nanoclay as an effective adsorbent for the absorption of Rhodamine B. The efficiency of dye adsorption was improved by using Halloysite nanosponges which are combined with the derivatives of cyclodextrin. The parameters witnessed the significant removal of cation and anion dyes was reported. Pandey et al. [42], reported the amazing uses of Halloysite nanotubes in the sector of toxic dye remediation, energy and sustainable environment progress. They concluded that the Halloysite nanotubes as an alumina-silicate support plays very important role as an effective dye removal.

Nyankson et al. [43] conducted a study on Halloysite nanotubes for water soluble dye and also reported pharmaceutical waste removal. The Halloysite nanotubes were combined with Ag_3PO_4 for photocatalytic degradation which showed excellent results. Wang et al. [44] utilized Halloysite nanotubes for the removal of various dyes including Methylene Blue and anionic-cationic dyes. The study gave promising results for Halloysite nanotubes as an excellent multifunctional nanoadsorbent. Rawtani et al. [45] reviewed about Halloysite nanotubes and their use as multifunctional material ranging from biological application to remediation of environmental contaminants. In their review they concluded that the Halloysite nanotubes are surely going to be useful in many industries because of their mechanical, chemical and biological properties. Yuan et al. [46] enumerated the characteristics and properties of Halloysite nanotubes, they has also discussed about the functionalization of Halloysite nanotubes. Researchers reported that HNT can be used as filler materials for polymer nanocomposites for various applications. Radoor et al. [47] conducted a study on MB dye adsorption by using Halloysite nanoclay along with polymer biocomposites. The study included the adsorption kinetics, adsorption isotherm and antimicrobial activity. The Halloysite nanoclay exhibited excellent antibacterial property along with efficient dye adsorption. Kuśmierk et al. [48] used Halloysite nanotubes for the adsorption of Direct Orange 26 dye. The results were highly promising and excellent compare to traditional dye adsorbents. The adsorption was highly dependent on pH, follows pseudo-2nd order kinetic and Langmuir adsorption models. Ngulube et al. [49] conducted a study on dye adsorption of Methylene Blue by using Halloysite nanocomposites. Halloysite nanocomposites rapidly removed the MB dye and gave maximum efficiency of 99.66% which makes it as the best adsorbent material. The adsorption was highly dependent on pH, follows pseudo-2nd order kinetic and Langmuir adsorption models. Cavallaro et al. [50] demonstrated the removal of organic and inorganic contaminants from environments by using Kaolinite nanosheets and Halloysite nanotubes. They reported that the nanoclay minerals can act as highly effective dye removal adsorbents and also can be used as filler materials for membranes with amazing filtration efficiency.

Zayani et al. [51] reported photocatalytic degradation of azo dye by using TiO_2 nanoparticles. The degradation was very effective as surface area played important role in removal of dye significantly. The use of TiO_2 nanoparticles as a photocatalytic dye degradation was also supported by the study made by Sathishkumar et al. [52] and Tejaswini et al. [53].

Zhang et al. [54] reported a study on dye adsorption by using chitosan-bentonite as an adsorbent. The dye used was Amido Black 10 (AB 10). The experimental data suggested the Langmuir model as the best fitting model and highest adsorption quantity was 418.4 mg/g at neutral pH and room temperature. The kinetic data followed pseudo-second order kinetic model. The similar studies for bentonite as an effective adsorbent for azo dyes were reported by Özcan et al. [55], Li et al. [56], Bulut et al. [57] and Hu et al. [58], all the mentioned dye remediation were following pseudo-second order reaction kinetics and Langmuir isotherm model. Toor et al. [59] used naturally existing clay minerals or unmodified clay minerals as cost effective dye adsorbents. In their study they used bentonite as unmodified clay mineral as an adsorbent for remediation of Congo Red (CR) dye. The experimental data suggest the reactions were reported as exothermic and spontaneous in nature and follows Freundlich theoretical model and pseudo second-order reaction. The maximum efficiency of dye adsorption by bentonite was reported of 95%. Similar studies were performed on Bentonite by Turabik et al. [60] for Basic Yellow 28 (BY28) dye, Yang et al. [61] and Lian et al. [62] for Methylene Blue (MB) dye, Bulut et al. [63] for Congo Red (CR) dye, Bulut et al. [64] and for Malachite Green (MG) dye, all the mentioned dye remediation were following pseudo-second order reaction kinetics and Langmuir isotherm model.

Sciascia et al. [65] conducted a study on Montmorillonite as an adsorbent to adsorb the basic building blocks of nucleic acids. The research was carried out on Adenine and Cytosine bases and Montmorillonite exhibited excellent adsorption at pH 2 and 6 respectively. Elaziouti et al. [66] studied about the dye adsorption capacity of the Montmorillonite adsorbent for various cationic dyes including Methylene Blue. At optimal conditions Montmorillonite reported more than 90% removal efficiency. The similar studies were reported for Montmorillonite by various research groups including; Bhattacharyya et al. [67], for adsorption of Rhodamine B (RB) dye.

Yavuz et al. [68] investigated on Kaolinite and its ability to remove contaminants and heavy metals from waste water. In their study they observed that Kaolinite effectively removed heavy metals such as Mn, Co, Ni and Cu. The experimental data was best fit for Langmuir model. Thermodynamic analysis revealed that the adsorption was endothermic response and optimal at higher degree of temperature. The similar studies were reported for Montmorillonite by various research groups including; Doğan et al. [69], for adsorption of Maxilon Yellow 4GL (MY 4GL) and Maxilon Red GRL (MR GRL) dyes, wherein adsorption process was found to be exothermic process. Recent studies also suggest that

Kaolinite adsorbent can also be used to adsorb cationic dyes with high efficacy and better capacity.

1.10 Objectives of the Research Work

The principle objective of the research work is the usage of nanoclays/nanotubes to adsorb several dyes to eliminate hazardous dyes.

The other objectives are:

- To study parameters affecting adsorption such as: contact time, pH, adsorbent dosage and temperature on the elimination of the dyes on nanoclay
- To study the surface appearance of the adsorbents before and after adsorption of dyes using techniques such as SEM and FT-IR
- To study the adsorption isotherms and modelling
- To study the kinetics and thermodynamics of the adsorption process
- To study the developed method for the remediation of industrial effluents
- To study the dye adsorbed nanoclay as filler/reinforcing substance for the production of composites
- To study dye remediation of toxic dyes by using nanomaterials
- To study toxic Azo dyes usage in commercial applications- Dye Sensitized Solar Cells (DSSCs)

1.11 References

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Chapter 2

ADSORPTION, KINETICS AND THERMODYNAMICS STUDIES ON REMEDIATION OF DB15 DYE USING HALLOYSITE NANOTUBES

A novel laboratory scale experiments are designed through remediation of Direct Blue 15 (DB15) dye using abundantly available and nontoxic halloysite nanotubes (HNT) and their application to textile industrial effluent (TIE). The DB15 adsorbed-HNT “sludge” was used as reinforcing material along with plastic waste for the fabrication of composites. To understand the phenomena of DB15 adsorption on HNT as a prelude to commercialization; various factors, namely, pH, adsorbate initial concentration, adsorbent dosage, and temperature were experimentally studied. To estimate the adsorption capacity of HNT, nine isotherm models were studied. Brouers-Sotolongo adsorption isotherm model was fitted best. The predominant mechanism for the overall rate of for a multi-step dye adsorption process fits best to pseudo-second-order reaction. Mechanistic studies relate mass transfer phenomena as more likely to be dominant over the diffusion process. The study of the thermodynamic parameters reveals that the process is physisorption. SEM and FTIR studies suggest the adsorption of the dye on HNT. Statistical optimization of process parameters were carried out.

2.1 Introduction

We were the first to demonstrate, nutraceutical industrial spent as new class of biosorbents to amputate the dyes from water and industrial effluents and the resultant dye adsorbed waste as filler material along with plastic waste for the fabrication of composites [1]. The ever-growing demand for textile products has dubious distinction as one of the major contributors to the pollution in the world. The insatiable consumption of water in textile industries has led to a massive water pollution problem [2]. The industry during various processes discharge waste containing a variety of dyes that pose a great challenge for the environment in terms of health of the ecosystem [3].

A perpetual thirst to innovate efficient, economical and eco-friendly methodologies for the treatment of textile industrial effluents has resulted in three major categories, namely, biological [4], chemical [5], photochemical [6] and physical methods [7-9]. However, they have three major deficiencies; economically unviable, production of undesirable degradation products which most of them display more toxicity than the precursors and production of undesirable sludge.

Adsorption as a technique offers the best prospects in relation to the other techniques, methods, procedures and protocols for the remediation of dyes [10]. One of the major drawbacks of adsorption techniques for the remediation of dyes in textile industrial effluent is that it is known to produce highly concentrated sludge that leads to a problem of disposal. This limits the adsorption technique to qualify as a sustainable technique. Activated carbon has been traditionally used for remediation of dyes in the textile industries. Therefore, the cost of activated carbon was higher and processing charges to regenerate limits its use [11]. This limitation has created a surge amongst scientists to look for an alternative, which is economically feasible and environmentally acceptable.

The requirement of the quantity of adsorbent for remediation in a textile industry runs into tons of material. Thus, the removal of dyes from the effluents obtained from textile industries should have the following features: availability in abundance, eco-friendly and economical. To suit to these features clay minerals are most appropriate as adsorbents for the amputation of dyes from effluents. However, clay minerals need to be optimized as nano materials to enhance several properties targeted for a particular application [12]. Amongst many nanoclay minerals available in abundance, halloysite nanotube (HNT) finds

applications in including catalysis [13], cosmetics and pharmacy [14] and medicine [15]. We have selected HNT as a choice of adsorbent to suit to the design of CE concept for two reasons; first, it has tubular structure with functional groups on the surface and inside the pore with different chemistries which enhances the efficiency of adsorption during the process of remediation of dyes and second, HNT as a reinforcement material has been extensively used in the fabrication of nano composites [16].

Azo dyes are banned all over the world. Yet they make up to 70% of dyes used in textile industry due to their inherent properties, such as, i) simple and cost-effective methods of synthesis in aqueous media, ii) availability of colossal choice of starting materials, iii) wide spectrum of shades, iv) high intensity and superior fastness of the colour, v) versatility in applications on a variety of substrates and vi) energy saving dyeing process at 60 °C compared to boiling temperature of its counterparts have made them important and indispensable to the textile industry [17]. Direct Blue 15 (DB15) is a bis azo dye used to dye cellulose and cotton; leather and wool and paper and silk. The dye is also used to stain biological materials and to tint cinematographic film. The use pattern for the dye in the USA is 65%, 30% and 5% for textile dyeing, paper colorant and other uses respectively [18]. Survey of the literature revealed that there is scant literature available for the remediation of DB15 by adsorption technique [19].

The purpose of the current study is to improve a design and an effective technique for the remediation of DB15 from water and Textile Industrial Effluent (TIE). The dye adsorbed HNT generated as “sludge” is used in the fabrication of composites using waste plastic in tune with CE approach.

2.2 Materials and Methods

2.2.1 Materials

Halloysite nanotubes (HNT) and Direct Blue 15 (DB15) dye [C.I. = 24400; CAS registry number = 2429-74-5; chemical formula = $C_{34}H_{24}N_6Na_4O_{16}S_4$; molecular weight = 992.81] were obtained from Aldrich, India. The dye is commonly referred to as Direct Sky Blue 5B. The structure of the DB15 dye is displayed in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Structure of Direct Blue 15 dye

2.2.2 Studies on the variables affecting adsorption of DB15 dye on HNT

The influence of experimental parameters (pH, initial DB15 dye concentration, HNT dosage and temperature) was studied using batch experiments. For preparing stock solution of DB15 (1000 mg L^{-1}) double distilled water was used. Required solution concentrations ($25 - 500 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) were prepared from the stock solution. A series of 250-mL Erlenmeyer flask, 50 mL aqueous DB15 dye solution ($25 - 500 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) was added. Required amount of HNT was introduced into each flask. Evaluations were conducted based on the effects of varying parameters such as, pH (2, 4, 6, 7, 8, 10 and 12); DB15 dye initial concentration ($25 - 500 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) and dosage of adsorbent ($0.025 - 0.3 \text{ g per } 50 \text{ mL}$; $0.5 - 6.0 \text{ g per L}$). To study the effect of temperature on the process of adsorption, three temperatures were selected to study the initial dye concentration of 100 mg L^{-1} and fitted into Eqs. 1, 2 and 3 - Table 2.1. Solution was subjected to stirring in a thermostatic orbital shaker at 165 rpm for 180 min. The unadsorbed DB15 dye in solution phase was detached from HNT for five minutes at 3000 rpm centrifugation. If the solution was unclear the centrifugation was repeated for an additional five min. The DB15 dye concentration at equilibrium pertaining to the supernatant centrifuged solution was resolved using UV-vis spectrometer (Perkin-Elmer Lambda EZ-201) at λ_{max} 602 nm. To study the effect in a range of pH 2-12 batch experiments were performed. The pH of the solution was attuned using 0.01-1.00 M HCl or NaOH solution. Adsorption kinetic studies of DB15 dye solution (100 mg L^{-1}), three temperatures (303, 313 and 323 K) were selected and experiments carried out with time as independent variables. Experiments were replicated thrice and the mean values are considered.

Table 2.1: Mathematical equations used in the study

Eq. No.	Equation	Description	Parameter
General adsorption studies			
1	$q_e = \frac{(C_o - C_e) V}{W}$	Adsorption capacity at equilibrium	q_e is adsorption capacity at equilibrium (mg L ⁻¹) q_t is adsorption capacity at time t (mg L ⁻¹)
2	$q_t = \frac{(C_o - C_t) V}{W}$	Adsorption capacity at time t	C_o is initial adsorbent concentration (mg L ⁻¹) C_e is adsorbent concentration at equilibrium (mg L ⁻¹) C_t is the adsorbent concentration at time t
3	$RE\% = \left[\frac{C_o - C_e}{C_o} \right] * 100$	Percentage removal efficiency (RE)	V is the volume of the adsorbate solution (L) W is the weight of the adsorbent (g)
Adsorption isotherm studies			
4	$q_e = \frac{Q_m K_a C_e}{1 + K_a C_e}$	Langmuir isotherm	Q_m is the monolayer adsorption capacity (mg g ⁻¹) K_a is Langmuir isotherm adsorption constant (L mg ⁻¹)
5	$R_L = \frac{1}{1 + K_a C_o}$	Separation factor of Langmuir isotherm	R_L factor implies whether the adsorption is unfavourable when ($R_L > 1$), linear ($R_L = 1$), favourable ($0 < R_L < 1$) and irreversible ($R_L = 0$)
6	$q_e = K_F C_e^{1/n_F}$	Freundlich isotherm	K_F is Freundlich isotherm adsorption capacity constant (mg g ⁻¹) n_F is heterogeneity factor indicates the nature of adsorption is chemisorption ($n_F < 1$), linear ($n_F = 1$) or physisorption ($n_F > 1$)
7	$q_e = Q_m (1 - e^{-(K_J C_e)})$	Jovanovic isotherm	K_J is Jovanovic isotherm adsorption constant (L mg ⁻¹)
8	$q_e = q_s e^{-k_{ad} \varepsilon^2}$	Dubinin-Radushkevich isotherm	q_s is Dubinin-Radushkevich isotherm constant (mg g ⁻¹) K_{ad} is Dubinin-Radushkevich isotherm constant (mol ² J ⁻¹) $\varepsilon = RT \ln \left[1 + \frac{1}{C_e} \right]$

9	$q_e = Q_m C_e (b_{TO} + C_e^{n_{TO}})^{-1/n_{TO}}$	Toth isotherm	b_{TO} is Toth isotherm constant (mg g^{-1}) n_{TO} is Toth isotherm model exponent
10	$q_e = Q_m [1 - e^{-(k_{BS} C_e)^{\alpha_{BS}}}]$	Brouers-Sotolongo isotherm	K_{BS} is Brouers-Sotolongo isotherm constant (L mg^{-1}) α_{BS} is Brouers-Sotolongo model exponent
11	$q_e = K_{VS} C_e + \frac{Q_m \beta_{VS} C_e}{1 + \beta_{VS} C_e}$	Vieth-Sladek isotherm	K_{VS} is Vieth-Sladek isotherm adsorption constant (L mg^{-1}) β_{VS} is Vieth-Sladek isotherm diffusivity constant
12	$q_e = \frac{K_{RP} Q_m C_e}{(1 + K_{RP} C_e)^{m_{RP}}}$	Radke-Prausnitz isotherm	K_{RP} is Radke-Prausnitz isotherm adsorption constant (L mg^{-1}) m_{RP} is Radke-Prausnitz isotherm model exponent
13	$q_e = \frac{A_{RP} C_e}{1 + B_{RP} C_e^g}$	Redlich-Peterson isotherm	A_{RP} and B_{RP} are Redlich-Peterson isotherm constants (m g^{-1}) g is Redlich-Peterson model exponent
Adsorption kinetic studies			
14	$q_t = q_e (1 - e^{-k_1 t})$	Pseudo-first-order equation	q_t is adsorption capacity at time t (mg L^{-1}) q_e is adsorption capacity at equilibrium (mg L^{-1}) k_1 is pseudo-first-order rate constant (s^{-1})
15	$q_t = \frac{q_e^2 k_2 t}{1 + q_e k_2 t}$	Pseudo-second-order equation	k_2 is pseudo-second-order rate constant ($\text{mol}^{-1} \text{L}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$) t is time of adsorption (s)
16	$\ln \left[\frac{1 - q_t}{q_e} \right] = R^1 t$	Film diffusion model	R^1 is insoluble, nondiffusible anionic portion of the adsorbent constant (s^{-1})
17	$q_t = k_{int} t^{1/2}$	Intraparticle diffusion model	k_{int} is intra-particle diffusion rate constant ($\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1/2}$) $t^{1/2}$ is half-adsorption time of adsorbate (s)
18	$q_t = k_{id} t^{1/2} + C$	Weber-Morris model	k_{id} is intra-particle diffusion rate constant ($\text{mg g}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1/2}$) C is intercept of the plot q_t versus $t^{1/2}$

19	$\log (1 - f^2) = \frac{k}{2.303t}$	Dumwald-Wagner model	k is intra-particle diffusion rate constant ($\text{mg g}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$) f is ratio of adsorption capacities at time t and at equilibrium
Adsorption thermodynamic studies			
20	$\Delta G^0 = \Delta H^0 - \Delta S^0 T$	Standard Gibbs free energy	ΔG^0 is Standard Free Energy (J mol^{-1}) ΔH^0 is Enthalpy Change (J mol^{-1}) ΔS^0 is Entropy Change ($\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) T is absolute temperature (K) R is ideal gas constant ($\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) K_{eq} is chemical equilibrium constant C_o is initial adsorbent concentration (mg L^{-1}) C_e is adsorbent concentration at equilibrium (mg L^{-1})
21	$\Delta G^0 = -RT \ln K_{eq}$	Standard Gibbs free energy at chemical equilibrium	
22	$K_{eq} = \frac{C_o}{C_e}$	Thermodynamic equilibrium constant	
23	$\ln K_{eq} = \frac{\Delta S^0}{R} - \frac{\Delta H^0}{R}$	Variant of standard Gibbs free energy	

2.2.3 Characterization methods

IR spectra were recorded using the FTIR spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer 3 lambda). JEOL model 3300 scanning electron microscope was used to record SEM images. A pH meter Model 802 - Systronics, India was used to measure pH. Point-of-zero-charge (pH_{PZC}) of HNT was determined by carrying out the procedure described by us elsewhere [20].

2.2.4 Statistical optimization of process parameters

An experimental design [21] for the optimization of five process parameters at two levels as mentioned in Table 2.2 were prepared for the DB15-HNT system to obtain a quadratic regression equation using the ANOVA model.

Table 2.2: Experimental range for individual factors

Factor	Name	Units	Minimum	Maximum
A	Time	min	0	180
B	Temperature	°C	27	50
C	Concentration	mg L ⁻¹	25	500
D	Adsorbent dosage	g L ⁻¹	0.5	6
E	pH	-	2	12

2.2.5 Studies on composites

2.2.5.1 Preparation of DB15 dye adsorbed HNT

To 100-litre barrel, 100 g of commercial DB15 dye was transferred. The dye was dissolved in 25 litres of TIE. 5 Kg of commercial HNT were transferred and the solution was stirred manually using a plastic rod. The solution was kept for about 24 h with occasional stirring. The dye adsorbed HNT was separated using a cloth and the precipitate was washed thoroughly with distilled water till the filtrate was almost colourless. The blue colour dye adsorbed HNT was air dried. The resultant powder containing lumps were grinded and sieved through 177 µm mesh and dried in an oven at 60°C for 24 h. The powder was cooled in a closed container with an airtight lid. DB15 dye adsorbed HNT was referred to as dye modified HNT powder (dmHNT).

2.2.5.2 Preparation of the composites

The composites of High Density Polyethylene/dye modified Halloysite nanotubes (HDPE/dmHNT) were prepared in two stages; dry-blending of HDPE resin with different proportions of dmHNT in a tumble mixer and melt compounding of master batches. HDPE granules and/or recycled product and dmHNT master batch flakes were compounded using twin screw extruder. The specimens were prepared by cutting the extrudate strands into pellets and were tested for physico-mechanical and chemical properties. The results were encouraging and investigations are in progress.

2.3 Results and Discussion

2.3.1 Characterization of HNT and DB15-HNT surfaces

2.3.1.1 Analyses of SEM Images and FTIR spectrum

Surface characterization of HNT and DB15-HNT was done through SEM. Figure 2.2a and Figure 2.2b displayed the surface of HNT covered with the DB15 dye. A comparison of FTIR spectra of pristine HNT, DB15 dye and DB15 dye adsorbed on HNT revealed the following: absence of peaks between 2800-3000 cm^{-1} was noticed in pristine HNT (Figure 2.3), whereas, a tiny peak appeared at around 3750 cm^{-1} was ascribed to traces of adsorbed water. The typical peaks at 2830 and 2852 cm^{-1} were due to the C-H stretching asymmetric and symmetric vibrations respectively. The vibration band at 1000-1080 cm^{-1} was correlated to the vibrations of single bonds of Si-O, Al-O and C-O molecules.

FTIR spectra for DB15 dye exhibit the distinctive N-H and CH-aromatic stretching vibrations peaks at 2800-3000 and 2900 cm^{-1} respectively. The vibration peak at 1700 was attributed to S=O of sulphites group in dyes structure. The triplet peaks generally ascribed to C=C in aromatic rings coupled with N=N of azo group are seen at 1640, 1570 and 1460 cm^{-1} respectively. The multiple peaks attributed to bending vibrations of N-H and CH appears at 1460-1300 cm^{-1} was also realized.

FTIR spectra of DB15 dye displayed a major band in the range 2800-3000 cm^{-1} . This peak appears to be less intense and tends to vanish due to the interactions between the NH groups in dyes with Si/Al in HNT as $(\text{Si}^{4+} \cdots \text{NH})$ and $(\text{Al}^{3+} \cdots \text{NH})$ in the DB15-HNT FTIR

spectra. Additionally, the disappearance of N=N stretching peak at 1598 cm^{-1} confirms the adsorption of DB15 dye on HNT. The interaction between components will affect the property of double bonds and increase the character of the single bond which is reflected in sharp increase in the intensity of peak around 1100 cm^{-1} . Moreover, disappearance of IR absorption frequencies established adsorption of DB15 onto HNT. Determination of pH_{PZC} confirms that HNT at $\text{pH } 7.61$ displays zero charge (Figure 2.4).

Figure 2.2: SEM image of a) HNT and b) DB15-HNT

Figure 2.3: FTIR spectra of DB15 dye, HNT and DB15-HNT

Figure 2.4: Point of zero charge of HNT at the intersection

2.3.2 The influence of variables on DB15 adsorption on HNT

2.3.2.1 Solution pH

The adsorption capacity of HNT depends on solution pH. The pH plays two important roles; first, it influences the characteristics of adsorbent surface and second, the chemistry of the dye solution [22]. pH as a parameter, assumes importance to substantiate the efficiency of the adsorbent under study. The knowledge of this parameter is significant when the process is scaled to commercial levels [23]. The shape of the curve displayed in Figure 2.5a was consistent with the expected chemistry. The principal constituents of HNT are the oxides of aluminium and silicon. These oxides display different ionization properties and surface charges due to different zeta potentials when kept in contact with water [24]. The external surface of HNT displayed negative charges due to silica above pH values of 1.5. Conversely, at lower pH the anionic dye exhibits positive charge as shown in the Figure 2.6. Thus, maximum absorption takes place between pH 2 and 4. With increase in pH the amount of degree of protonation of NH_2 and OH groups of the dye decreases. Accordingly, the adsorption capacity of the substrate decreases sharply from pH 4 to 6. The marginal decrease from pH 6 to 10 is attributed to the positive charges of alumina in neutral and alkaline media which attracts the negatively charged azo dye. A sharp increase at $\text{pH} > 10$ is likely due to adsorption of dye onto positively charged Al^{3+} and Si^{4+} ions. Also, the degradation of the dye at $\text{pH} > 10$ resulting in decrease in absorbance of the experimental solution cannot be ruled out.

Figure 2.5: Effect of (a) pH, (b) initial dye concentration with % removal efficiency, (c) dosage and (d) temperature of DB15-HNT

Figure 2.6: Structures of Direct Blue 15 dye in aqueous media

2.3.2.2 Initial DB15 dye concentration

The influence of initial dye concentration has profound influence on the adsorption capacity of HNT. This is manifested in the results displayed in Figure 2.5b. The shape of the curve suggests that the percent removal capacity of the adsorbate (DB15) by the adsorbent (HNT) is maximum in the lower concentrations of the dye and decreases with increase in the concentrations as is observed in most of the cases [25]. Conversely, the q_e increases sharply from 25 – 200 mg L⁻¹ and marginal increase was observed with increase in the concentration.

2.3.2.3 Effect of adsorbent dosage

The dosage as a parameter will have profound influence on the commercialization of the process, because it decides the economic feasibility. The removal of DB15 dye from the solution increases with increase in adsorbent dosage from 0.025 to 2.0 g L⁻¹. It was observed that the percent DB15 dye removal increased exponentially from 0.025 to 2.0 g L⁻¹ with the increase in the amount of adsorbent dosage. Thereafter, marginal increase in the removal efficiency was observed (Figure 2.5c). This observation assumes importance in the commercialization process where the number of trials with minimum amounts of the adsorbent substantially increases the removal efficiency of the dye by HNT.

2.3.2.4 Effect of temperature

Keeping in view, our focus to scale to commercial applications, evaluation of the process of adsorption of dyes onto HNT as a function of solution temperature was studied. The influence of temperature on DB15 dye adsorption onto HNT is presented in Figure 2.5d. The data obtained for the classical thermodynamic parameters, namely, ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° indicate the nature and type of a reaction. For example, the positive ΔH° (enthalpy) values obtained from 303 to 323 K of HNT indicate endothermic process. The overall negative values of ΔG° (free energy) obtained for DB15-HNT system confirm the spontaneity and viability of the adsorption process. The magnitude of ΔG° values is indicative of rapid and spontaneous adsorption at lower temperature. Further, it is inferred that the positive values of ΔS° (entropy) indicate the decrease in the randomness at dye/HNT interface [26].

2.4 Adsorption Isotherms - Modeling Analysis

The study of the isotherm models was intended to provide a view of efficiency of HNT for the remediation of the dye for commercial applications with an eye on degree of economic advantages. The data of adsorption of DB15 dye onto HNT were analyzed using the adsorption isotherm models proposed by Langmuir, Freundlich, Jovanovic, Dubinin-Radushkevich, Toth, Brouers-Sotolongo, Vieth-Sladek, Radke-Prausnitz and Redlich-Peterson isotherm models. The main criterion of the study of adsorption isotherms was to select a model, where q_e (the experimental equilibrium) values were almost equal to Q_m (monolayer adsorption capacity) value with coefficient of variance (R^2) value ≥ 0.90 . To refine the results and to make a distinction between almost similar data obtained by various isotherm models, SSE and χ^2 as two additional error functions were incorporated in our study.

Langmuir [27] proposed a model on the assumption that the adsorbent will have active sites possessing almost uniform energies. This was further established on the idea that no lateral interaction takes place between adsorbed molecules. A plateau in a two-dimensional graph with equilibrium concentration (C_e) as independent variable and q_e (Figure 3a) as a dependent variable characterizes the saturation of the active sites on the surface of the adsorbent. This implies that further adsorption cannot take place and the possibility of multilayer adsorption of the dye is ruled out. The equations of the Langmuir isotherm model are shown in Eqs. 4 and 5 - Table 1. The experimental data, $R^2 = 0.94$, $q_e = 69.00 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$ and $Q_m = 97.96 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$ for DB15-HNT system indicate good fit to the Langmuir adsorption isotherm model. The separation factor (R_L) values of 0.035 and 0.419 indicate favourable adsorption of DB15 dye onto HNT. Moreover, the adsorption is considered more favourable if the increase in initial concentrations decreases the R_L value. This is in contradiction to our results displayed in Figure 2.7a. Additionally, the variation between Q_m and q_e values of 97.96 and 69.00 mg g^{-1} respectively for HNT has given impetus to explore other models.

In contrast to Langmuir isotherm model, Freundlich proposed heterogeneity of the surface sites with different energy of adsorption and demonstrated relevance to multilayer adsorption [28]. The mathematical expression is shown in Eq. 6 – Table 1. The values of $n_F = 3.977$ and $1/n_F 0.251$ (Table 2.3) of HNT indicate that the process of adsorption is physical in nature and suits the behaviour of Langmuir Isotherm.

The Jovanovic model [29] attempts to minimize the deviancies from the Langmuir isotherm model by introducing the exponential term K_J . The mathematical model is presented in Eq. 7 - Table 1. On comparing the difference in the values of $q_e = 69.00 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$ and $Q_m = 85.67 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$ with the values obtained by Langmuir isotherm model one may surmise that values obtained in Jovanovic isotherm is better to Langmuir isotherm model.

The adsorption isotherm empirical model proposed by Dubinin-Radushkevich [30] describes the process of adsorption through filling of the pore of the adsorbent. The mathematical model is presented in Eq. 8 - Table 1. A value of 110.59 mg g^{-1} for q_s is more compared to the Langmuir and Jovanovic models (Table 2.3). A value of 0.97 for correlation coefficient (R^2) confirms that the process of adsorption is linear (Figure 3b).

In pursuit to identify specific model(s) which has smaller gap between experimental q_e values and Q_m values; five isotherm models, namely, Toth, Brouers-Sotolongo, Vieth-Sladek, Redlich-Peterson and Radke-Prausnitz, were also studied. The importance of these models is described by us elsewhere [31]. To describe a heterogeneous adsorption system an empirical mathematical Eq. 9 - Table 1 was developed by Toth [32]. Eq. 10 and Eq 11 - Table 1 represent Brouers-Sotolongo isotherm model [33] and Vieth-Sladek isotherm model [34] respectively. The results are presented in Figure 2.7c. The mathematical Eq. 12 - Table 1 represents Radke-Prausnitz isotherm model [35]. Redlich–Peterson isotherm model [36] Eq. 13 - Table 2.1 has ‘g’ value of 1.063 as a correction exponent which shows similarity to Langmuir isotherm (Figure 2.7d).

Table 2.3: Two-parameter isotherms

Two Parameter Isotherms							
Langmuir		Freundlich		Jovanovic		Dubinin-Radushkevich	
Q_m	97.96	K_F	24.17	Q_m	85.67	Q_s	110.59
K_S	0.055	n_F	3.977	K_J	0.046	K_{ad}	4.46E-05

Figure 2.7: Fitting of adsorption data to (a) Langmuir and Freundlich, (b) Jovanovic and Dubinin-Radushkevich, (c) Vieth-Sladek and Brouers-Sotolongo and (d) Redlich-Petersen, Radke-Prausnitz and Toth adsorption isotherm of DB15-HNT

Table 2.4: Three-parameter isotherms

Three Parameter Isotherms									
Toth		Brouers-Sotolongo		Vieth-Sladek		Radke-Prausnitz		Redlich-Peterson	
Q_m	87.60	Q_m	84.00	A_{RP}	4.70	Q_m	114.80	A_{RP}	4.70
n_{T0}	1.876	K_{BS}	0.027	B_{RP}	0.03	K_{rp}	0.043	B_{RP}	0.034
b_{T0}	442.37	α	1.21	g	1.06	m_{rp}	1.06	g	1.06

Table 2.5: Fitting of isotherm models

Isotherms	Langmuir	Freundlich	Jovanovic	Dubinin-Radushkevich	Toth	Brouers-Sotolongo	Vieth-Sladek	Radke-Prausnitz	Redlich-Peterson
SSE	321.3	1080.3	297.4	4324.3	227.2	281.7	321.3	306.4	296.9
χ^2	12.14	40.80	8.02	67.55	6.42	5.59	12.14	10.79	10.15
R^2	0.94	0.80	0.94	0.97	0.96	0.95	0.94	0.94	0.95

Table 2.6: Parameters for adsorption kinetic models

Initial dye concentration [$\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$]	Temp [K]	$q_{e, \text{expt}}$ [mg g^{-1}]	Pseudo-first-order				Pseudo-second-order			
			$q_{e, \text{pred}}$ [mg g^{-1}]	k_1	R^2	χ^2	$q_{e, \text{pred}}$ [mg g^{-1}]	k_2	R^2	χ^2
100	303	60	50.18	1.40E-01	0.68	0.96	55.64	3.99E-03	0.87	1.72
	313	57	48.58	1.40E-01	0.63	1.10	53.92	4.10E-03	0.84	0.46
	323	55	45.89	1.54E-01	0.58	0.98	50.40	5.07E-03	0.81	0.42
200	303	80	70.67	1.79E-01	0.78	0.39	75.69	4.78E-03	0.95	0.08
	313	76	65.34	6.53E+01	0.51	0.54	65.88	1.71E-03	0.76	1.65
	323	73	64.35	2.19E-01	0.51	0.54	67.94	7.39E-03	0.80	0.22
300	303	86	76.28	2.39E-01	0.49	0.47	79.82	7.72E-03	0.80	0.19
	313	80	68.28	2.97E-01	0.40	0.20	70.19	1.54E-02	0.71	0.10
	323	75	68.07	3.04E-01	0.46	0.14	69.78	1.70E-02	0.79	0.06

The data obtained in Table 2.4 using five three-parameter models. The study of nine isotherm models and evaluation of statistical parameters are presented in Table 2.5. In brief, the graphs obtained by nine models have the similarity that it contains two parts, viz., nonlinear part and a plateau. The former, indicates that the dye molecule adheres to the active site of the porous HNT and the latter characterizes the saturation of the adsorption process. Considering the values of Q_m , R^2 , SSE and χ^2 ; Brouers-Sotolongo isotherm model fits best.

2.5 Adsorption Kinetics

Kinetic models provide an insight on the performance of adsorption of DB15 dye on HNT with time as independent variable. This is of great significance to scale for commercial applications. To provide the variation in adsorption rate, a concentration of 100, 200 and 300 mg L⁻¹ of DB15 dye was used to carry out kinetic studies at 303, 313 and 323 K. The results are presented in Table 2.6 and Figure 2.8. The kinetic data of adsorption of DB15 on minerals was analysed using pseudo-first-order Eq. 14 - Table 2.1 [37] and pseudo-second-order Eq. 15 - Table 2.1 [38]. The R^2 and χ^2 values suggest the pseudo-second-order model is well-fitted compared to pseudo-first-order for the DB15-HNT system.

Analysis of adsorption kinetics data confirmed multiple levels of linearity, which in turn suggests multiple mechanisms. Higher concentrations and higher temperature leads to higher adsorption rate which leads to different linear routes. However, the process of adsorption gets stabilized with respect to time. This was observed in film diffusion model Eq. 16 - Table 1 [39]. It can be seen from Figure 2.9 and Table 2.7 that the values of diffusion constant R' of a liquid film are in agreement with high R^2 values. Furthermore, the values of R' infers, fast adsorption of solute onto the surface of the particles leaving a thin film. The phenomena retard the process of diffusion which affects the rate of adsorption. This step confirms that the adsorption process is limited by diffusion phenomenon.

Figure 2.8: Kinetic model fits for (a) $100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, (b) $200 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and (c) $300 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ initial concentration of DB 15 dye on HNT system at different temperatures

Figure 2.9: Kinetics data fitted to the Film diffusion model with initial DB15 concentration (a) $100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, (b) $200 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and (c) $300 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$

Table 2.7: Parameters for diffusion models

Initial dye concentration [$\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$]	Temp [K]	Film diffusion model		Weber-Morris model		Dumwald-Wagner	
		R' [min^{-1}]	R^2	k_{ist} [$\text{mg g}^{-1} \text{s}^{-0.5}$]	R^2	K [min^{-1}]	R^2
100	303	0.0238	0.98	3.05	0.99	0.021	0.98
	313	0.0285	0.94	2.99	0.98	0.026	0.93
	323	0.0234	0.95	2.59	0.98	0.021	0.94
200	303	0.0225	0.99	2.89	0.98	0.021	0.99
	313	0.0175	0.98	2.18	0.98	0.016	0.98
	323	0.0216	0.97	2.18	0.98	0.020	0.97
300	303	0.0193	0.98	2.18	0.98	0.018	0.98
	313	0.0096	0.95	1.23	0.94	0.009	0.95
	323	0.0138	0.99	1.09	0.98	0.014	0.99

2.6 Mechanistic Study

Mathematical models of adsorption reaction and adsorption diffusion are proposed to identify the importance of diffusion in the adsorption process of the DB15 dye onto HNT. We have resorted to a functional empirical relationship of the uptake of the substrate at a given time q_t varying almost proportionally with $t^{1/2}$. This was done by fitting an intraparticle diffusion model Eq. 17 - Table 2.1. These results demonstrate that the process of adsorption is not rate-limiting and the progression of adsorption is taking place in multiple steps. Thus, it may be envisaged that the movement of DB15 dye molecules onto the surface of HNT precedes the diffusion into the pores of HNT.

According to Weber-Morris model [26] the solute uptake varies with $t^{1/2}$ as shown in Eq. 18 - Table 1. A straight line was obtained on plotting q_t versus $t^{1/2}$ and the graph is presented in Figure 2.10. From the data we arrived at a conclusion that intraparticle diffusion is the rate-limiting step for the process of adsorption of the dye on the adsorbent. Hence q_t versus $t^{1/2}$ plot should provide a straight line whose slope (k_{int}) will be the diffusion rate constant (Figure 2.10). This inferred that the intraparticle diffusion is the sole rate-limiting step. Conversely, the Dumwald-Wagner model [40] calculates the true absorption rate Eq. 19 - Table 2.1. The data are presented in Table 2.7 and Figure 2.11.

Figure 2.10: Kinetics data fitted to the Weber-Morris model with initial DB15 concentration (a) 100 µg mL⁻¹, (b) 200 µg mL⁻¹ and (c) 300 µg mL⁻¹

Fig. 2.11 Kinetics data fitted to the Dumwald-Wagner model with initial DB15 concentration (a) 100 µg mL⁻¹, (b) 200 µg mL⁻¹ and (c) 300 µg mL⁻¹

2.7 Thermodynamics of the Adsorption Process

Gibbs free energy change (ΔG°) and entropy (ΔS°) of the dye-HNT system are the main features of the process design of adsorption thermodynamics. The relationship of ΔH° , ΔS° and E_a are presented in Eqs. – 20, 21, 22 and 23 - Table 1. The thermodynamic parameters are presented in Table 2.8 and plot of enthalpy and Gibbs free energy and Pseudo – second order kinetics of DB15-HNT were shown in Figure 2.12. The values of ΔG° suggest that the adsorption process is almost spontaneous. The decrease in the negative values of ΔG° with increase in the temperature infers that the reaction is almost spontaneous at lower temperature. The positive values of ΔS° indicate the randomness of dye/HNT interface.

Table 2.8: Effect of temperature and initial dye concentration on thermodynamic parameters

Initial dye concentration [$\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$]	Temp [K]	ΔG° [kJ mol $^{-1}$]	ΔS° [J mol $^{-1}$ K $^{-1}$]	ΔH° [kJ mol $^{-1}$]	ln A	E_a [kJ mol $^{-1}$]
100	303	-2.14				
	313	-2.19	3.39	2.04	0.86	9.66
	323	-2.31				
200	303	-1.22				
	313	-1.24	5.68	3.31	1.72	16.64
	323	-1.29				
300	303	-0.75				
	313	-0.81	8.73	4.80	4.07	32.36
	323	-0.87				

(a)

(b)

Figure 2.12: (a) Plot of enthalpy and Gibbs free energy of DB15-HNT and (b) Pseudo – second order kinetics of DB15-HNT

2.8 Statistical Process Optimization

The process optimization is achieved by using Fractional Factorial Experimental Design (FFED) [41] under different combinations of five independent variables. The quadratic regression equation derived from ANOVA shows the possible individual and combined effect of the factors for the DB15-HNT system (Table 2.9). The p -value $< 0.05\%$ with 95% confidence interval was considered significant.

Table 2.9 ANOVA Table of DB15-HNT

Source	Sum of Squares	Degree of freedom	Mean Square	F-Value	P-Value
Model	32566.3	13	2505.1	34.3	< 0.001
A	1961.3	1	1961.3	26.9	< 0.001
B	371.8	1	371.8	5.1	0.0264
C	2269.7	1	2269.7	31.1	< 0.001
D	4245.0	1	4245.0	58.1	< 0.001
AB	499.6	1	499.6	6.8	0.0104
AC	55.9	1	55.9	0.8	0.3840
BC	47.6	1	47.6	0.7	0.4214
A ²	2606.2	1	2606.2	35.7	< 0.001
B ²	31.8	1	31.8	0.4	0.5112
C ²	1404.8	1	1404.8	19.2	< 0.001
D ²	666.1	1	666.1	9.1	0.0033
E ²	1011.4	1	1011.4	13.9	< 0.001
Residual	6643.9	91	73.0		
Lack of fit	6569.3	88	74.7	3.0	0.1988
Total	39210.2	104			

The graphs in Figure 2.13 suggest a strong correlation between the experimental data and expected responses. A, C, D, A², C², D² and E² are significant model terms for the DB15-HNT system. The regression Equation obtained for DB15-HNT system is shown below:

$$\text{DB15-HNT} = 42.1 + 18.5*A - 6.2*B + 19.5*C - 32.0*D - 13.4*E - 3.4*AB + 11.8*AC - 3.0*BC - 19.8*A^2 + 1.6*B^2 - 27.5*C^2 + 24.2*D^2 + 23.4*E^2$$

Figure 2.13: Actual versus predicted values of DB15-HNT

The regression coefficient equation indicates the effect of the parameter(s) on the adsorption capacity. The surface and contour plots illustrate the combined effect of two factors on the process of adsorption and the results are graphically presented in Figure 2.14. Statistical optimization experiment was 112 mg g^{-1} with conditions optimized pH at 1, adsorbent dosage of 0.500 g L^{-1} , and an initial dye concentration of 412 mg L^{-1} for an adsorption time of 177 min with orbital shaking of 165 rpm at temperature 20°C .

Figure 2.14: 3D surface plot and contour plot showing the variation of adsorption capacity with (a) time versus concentration, (b) time versus adsorbent dosage and (c) time versus pH

2.9 Adsorption Process for Textile Industrial Effluents

The details about the composition of the industrial textile effluent (TIE), sample collection, measurement of absorbance are described elsewhere [42]. 0.1% (w/v) DB15 dye solutions were prepared by dissolving 5 g each of the dye in 5-litre distilled water (Solution 1) and in 5-litre TIE (Solution 2). Preliminary investigations were carried out to know factors responsible for the enhancement of efficiency of the dye from aqueous matrices. Besides, the factors derived from statistical optimization, we observed that addition of fresh samples at short intervals gave encouraging results. We also observed that the adsorbent had the capacity to amputate the dye along with the allied materials present in the Solution 2. The recovery of the dye measured from UV-visible spectroscopy was 96% (Figure 2.15).

Figure 2.15: Color of the solutions before and after adsorption: 1 Distilled water; 2 DB15 dye in distilled water; 3 TIE; 4 DB15 dye in TIE; 5 Filtrate after adsorption of dye on HNT after 15 min

To scale up the experiments by one and two orders; 0.5 and 5.0 g each of HNT was transferred to 1-liter and 10-liter polyethylene beakers. 500 mL and 5 liters Solution 2 was added to one-liter and 10-liter polyethylene beakers respectively. Using a magnetic stirrer the solutions were agitated. The procedure was repeated as described earlier [42]. The coefficients of variance of the data obtained for the experiments carried out in triplicate did not exceed $\pm 2\%$ error.

2.10 Conclusions

The interactions between the HNT as adsorbent and DB15 dye as adsorbate showed experimental equilibrium (q_e) value of 96.00 mg g⁻¹ at pH 2; 69.00 mg g⁻¹ at almost neutral pH and 112 mg g⁻¹ statistically optimized conditions. To understand the process of adsorption, nine isotherm models were studied. The adsorption follows Brouers-Sotolongo model. The interactions between HNT and DB15 are physical in nature and follows pseudo-second-order kinetics. Contact time, dye concentration, dosage and initial pH of the solution have profound influence on the process of adsorption. The dye-modified HNT has the potential as reinforcing material for the fabrication of the composites using plastic waste. Preliminary investigations gave encouraging results.

2.11 References

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Chapter 3

ADSORPTION, KINETICS AND THERMODYNAMICS STUDIES ON REMEDIATION OF BG DYE USING HALLOYSITE NANOTUBES

First-ever use of halloysite nanotube (HNT), a relatively low-cost nanomaterial abundantly available with least toxicity for the removal of brilliant green (BG) dye from aqueous media is reported. Factors affecting adsorption studies were carried out to assess the adsorption capacity, the kinetics and the equilibrium thermodynamics. All the experiments were designed at about pH 7. The Redlich-Peterson isotherm model fits best amongst nine isotherm models studied. Kinetic studies data conformed to pseudo-second-order model. Mechanistic studies suggest that the rate controlling step is predominantly dominated by intraparticle diffusion. Scanning electron microscopy and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy were used in characterizing the adsorbent. Process optimization was carried out using Response Surface Methodology (RSM) through two-level Fractional Factorial Experimental Design (FEED) to study the influence of parameters on the process of adsorption. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to study the combined effect of the parameters. Possibilities of the use of dye-adsorbed HNT (“sludge”) for the fabrication of the composites using plastic waste are suggested.

3.1 Introduction

A report on Global Sustainable Fabrics Market mentions a Compound Annual Growth Rate of 11.4% valued at USD 58.3 billion [1]. Manufacturing fabrics by textile industries has an abysmal impact on the environment due to huge expending of synthetic dyes; most of them, increase BOD and COD, impair photosynthesis, hinder plant growth, provide recalcitrance and promote carcinogenicity and mutagenicity [2]. Besides, insatiable consumption of water running to trillions of gallons per annum and large amounts of processed dye effluents containing thousands of tons of unconsumed dyes pose a great threat to ecology and environment [3-4]. Despite stringent regulations imposed on the textile industries on the wastewater treatment, the outcomes have been abysmally disappointing [5-6]. One of the major reasons is the absence of a sustainable remediation technique, method and/or procedure for the removal of toxic dyes.

Sustainability as a system addresses the issues of economics, environment and social concern [7]. The various techniques and methods reported in the literature may be broadly classified into four types; namely, biological [8-9], chemical [10-12], physico-chemical [13-14] and physical methods [15-17]. The aforesaid methods have serious limitations; time of completion of the remediation process, cost of the technique and/or method, fall-out of chemical, electrochemical and photo-chemical degradation processes resulting toxic substances [18]. Besides, one of the major problems associated with all the reported techniques is the disposal of sludge.

Adsorption as a technique addresses many of aforesaid problems with tangible solutions for the remediation of dyes from industrial effluents [19]. However, this technique also falls short of the problem of disposal of “sludge” produced after the adsorption of the adsorbate onto the adsorbent. Thus, it is ethically imperative to address the issue to provide a congenial solution for disposal of sludge [20]. One of the alternatives is to use inorganic class of adsorbents which will have less impact on the environment and ecology [21].

Textile industry requires an enormous quantity of the adsorbent for the process of remediation of dyes and allied materials for the treatment of effluents. Thus, it is necessary that the adsorbent should have the following characteristics: availability in abundance, cost-effective, environmental-friendly, ready-to-use without any pre-treatment and should possess pore structure. The latter assumes importance, as adsorption technique is a physical method and requires a large surface area for the interaction of the adsorbent with the adsorbate [22].

Halloysite nanotube (HNT) as an adsorbent qualifies as a candidate to meet the above requirements. Moreover, tubular structure of HNT with different chemistries inside the pore and on the surface suits our present study. Additionally, HNT has been extensively used as reinforcement material in the fabrication of the composites [23]. The latter helps us to address the issue of disposal of the sludge as a reinforcement material.

Brilliant green (BG) belongs to the triarylmethane class of dyes. It is extensively used in the paper industry, to dye wool, biological staining and as a dermatological agent. It is a hazardous contaminant which causes diarrhoea, eye irritation, nausea and vomiting [24]. Besides, there is a scant literature available for the removal of triarylmethane class of compounds using HNT [25]. Though, there are about a dozen research articles reported in the literature pertaining to use of inorganic materials, but none of the papers have used the nano material and addressed the issue of “sludge” generated after the adsorption of BG from aqueous media.

The aim of the present research work is to optimize the experimental conditions for the factors affecting the adsorption process, to model the studies for better understanding and to carry out RSM studies based on fractional factorial experimental design (FFED) for possible commercialization. Investigations on the use of dye-adsorbed HNT (“sludge”) for the fabrication of the composites using plastic waste are reported.

3.2 Materials and Methods

3.2.1 Materials

Halloysite nanotubes (HNT) and brilliant green (BG) dye were obtained from Aldrich, India. The dye is commonly referred to as Emerald Green. [C.I. = 42040; CAS registry number = 633-03-4; chemical formula = $C_{27}H_{33}N_2HO_4S$; molecular weight = 482.64. λ_{max} at 625 nm. The molecular structure of the BG dye is shown in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Structure of Brilliant Green dye

3.2.2 Studies on the variables affecting adsorption of BG dye on HNT

The influence of experimental parameters (pH, initial BG dye concentration, dosage and temperature) was studied using batch experiments. For preparing stock solution of BG (1000 mg L^{-1}) double distilled water was used. Required solution concentrations ($25\text{--}200 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) were prepared from the stock solution. To a series of 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask, 50 mL aqueous BG dye solution ($25\text{--}200 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) was added. Required amount of HNT was introduced into each flask. Evaluations were conducted based on the effects of varying parameters such as, pH (2, 4, 6, 7, 8, 10 and 12); BG dye initial concentration ($25 - 200 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) and dosage of adsorbent ($0.025 - 0.300 \text{ g } 50 \text{ mL}^{-1}$ ($0.500 - 6.000 \text{ g L}^{-1}$)). To study the effect of temperature on the process of adsorption, three temperatures were selected with an initial dye concentration of 100 mg L^{-1} . The data was fitted into Eqs. 1, 2 and 3 - Table 2.1. Solution was subjected to stirring in a thermostatic orbital shaker at 165 rpm for 180 min. Samples were withdrawn at predetermined equilibrium time. The unadsorbed BG dye in solution phase was separated from HNT by centrifugation with 3000 rpm for five minutes. If the solution was unclear the centrifugation was repeated for an additional five min. The BG dye concentration at equilibrium pertaining to the supernatant centrifuged solution was determined using Perkin-Elmer Lambda EZ-201 UV-vis spectrometer. To study the effect in a range of pH 2-12 batch experiments were performed. The pH of the solution was attuned using 0.01-1.00 M HCl or NaOH solution. Adsorption kinetic studies of BG dye solution (100 mg L^{-1}), three temperatures (303, 313 and 323 K) were selected and experiments carried

out with time as independent variables. Experiments were replicated thrice and the mean values are considered.

3.2.3 Characterization methods

IR spectra were recorded using the FTIR spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer 3 lambda). JEOL model 3300 scanning electron microscope was used to record SEM images. A pH meter Model 802 - Systronics, India was used to measure pH.

3.2.4 Statistical optimization of process parameters

An experimental design [26] for the optimization of five process parameters at two levels as mentioned in Table 3.1 were prepared for the BG-HNT system to obtain a quadratic regression equation using ANOVA model.

Table 3.1: Experimental range for individual factors

Factor	Name	Units	Minimum	Maximum
A	Time	min	0	180
B	Temperature	°C	27	50
C	Concentration	mg L ⁻¹	25	200
D	Adsorbent dosage	g L ⁻¹	0.5	6
E	pH	-	2	12

3.2.5 Studies on composites

3.2.5.1 Preparation of BG dye adsorbed HNT

To 100-litre barrel, 100 g of commercial BG dye was transferred. The dye was dissolved in 25 litres of TIE. 5 Kg of commercial HNT were transferred and the solution was stirred manually using a plastic rod. The solution was kept for about 24 h with occasional stirring. The dye adsorbed HNT was separated using a cloth and the precipitate was washed thoroughly with distilled water till the filtrate was almost colourless. The blue colour dye adsorbed HNT was air dried. The resultant powder containing lumps were grinded and sieved through 177 µm mesh and dried in an oven at 60°C for 24 h. The powder was cooled in a closed container with an airtight lid. BG dye adsorbed HNT was referred to as dye modified HNT powder (dmHNT).

3.2.5.2 Preparation of the composites

The composites of High Density Polyethylene/dye modified Halloysite nanotubes (HDPE/dmHNT) were prepared in two stages; dry-blending of HDPE resin with different proportions of dmHNT in a tumble mixer and melt compounding of master batches. HDPE granules and/or recycled product and dmHNT master batch flakes were compounded using twin screw extruder. The specimens were prepared by cutting the extrudate strands into pellets and were tested for physico-mechanical and chemical properties. The results were encouraging and investigations are in progress.

3.3 Results and Discussions

3.3.1 Characterization of HNT and BG-HNT surfaces

3.3.1.1 Analyses of SEM images and FTIR spectrum

SEM images of HNT and BG dye adsorbed HNT are shown in Figure 3.2a and 3.2b. The Figure 3.2b confirms the adsorption of the dye on the surface of HNT. The FTIR spectra for BG dye (Figure 3.3), exhibits the distinctive peaks at 3500 and 3200 and 3100 cm^{-1} refer to N-H and CH-aromatic stretching vibrations respectively. The vibration peak at 1700 cm^{-1} is attributed to S=O of sulphites group in dyes structure. The triplet peaks exist in spectrum between 1620, 1590 and 1480 cm^{-1} are due to C=C in aromatic ring which couples with N=N of azo group in dyes structure. The multi peaks which appear at 1460-1337 cm^{-1} are ascribed to bending vibrations of N-H and CH respectively. Besides, the spectrum of the halloysite, the band at 3660 cm^{-1} represents the stretching vibration of the inner surface -OH groups, while the band at 1010 cm^{-1} represents the stretching band of the Si-O. The inner surface -OH groups are connected to the aluminium-centred octahedral sheets and form hydrogen bonds with the oxygen sheet in the next double layer.

Figure 3.2: SEM image of a) HNT and b) BG-HNT

The FTIR spectrum of complex BG-HNT in (Figure 3.3) displays a significant change in the vibration modes compared to pure BG. It is clearly noticed that the vibrational peaks at $3500\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which are referred to -OH and -NH groups in BG dye tend to vanish. This indicates the HNT's strong interactions with functional groups and modifies the morphology of dyes structure in BG-HNT. Similar behaviours can be also observed at 3000 cm^{-1} , $1600\text{--}1450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1260\text{--}1030\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively, which confirms the HNT has the high adsorption and good interaction with BG dye.

Figure 3.3: FTIR spectra of BG dye, HNT and BG-HNT

3.3.2 The influence of variables on BG adsorption on HNT

3.3.2.1 Solution pH

The adsorption capacity of HNT depends on solution pH. The pH plays two important roles; first, it influences the characteristics of adsorbent surface and second, the chemistry of the dye solution [27]. pH as a parameter, assumes importance to substantiate the efficiency of the adsorbent under study. The knowledge of this parameter is significant when the process is scaled to commercial levels [28]. The shape of the curve displaced in Figure 3.4a was consistent with the expected chemistry. The principal constituents of HNT are the oxides of aluminium and silicon. These oxides display different ionization properties and surface charges due to different zeta potentials when kept in contact with water [29]. The external surface of HNT displayed negative charges due to silica above pH values of 2. Accordingly, the adsorption capacity of cationic BG dye decreased from pH 2 to 4. The pH has profound influence on the structure of BG and also its characteristic feature as cationic dye. Thus, increase in the pH the BG dye loses its positive charge and also changes its colour. A marginal increase of q_e from pH 6 to 12 is attributed to the positive charges of alumina in neutral and alkaline media which attracts the possibly negatively charged BG dye.

3.3.2.2 Initial BG dye concentration

The influence of initial dye concentration has profound influence on the adsorption capacity of HNT. This is manifested in the results displayed in Figure 3.4b. The shape of the curve suggests that the percent removal capacity of the adsorbate (BG) by the adsorbent (HNT) remains almost constant in the range 25-100 mg L⁻¹ and decreases with increase in the concentrations as is observed in most of the cases [30].

3.3.2.3 Effect of adsorbent dosage

The dosage as a parameter will have profound influence on the commercialization of the process, because it decides the economic feasibility [31]. The removal of BG dye from the solution decreases with increase in adsorbent dosage from 0.50 to 6.00 g L⁻¹. It was observed that the percent BG dye removal increased sharply with increase in adsorbent dosage from 0.50 to 1.00 g L⁻¹. Thereafter, marginal increase in the removal efficiency was observed (Figure 3.4c). This observation assumes importance in the commercialization

process where the number of trials with minimum amounts of the adsorbent substantially increases the dye removal efficiency of the dye by HNT.

3.3.2.3 Effect of temperature

Keeping in view, our focus to scale to commercial applications, evaluation of the process of adsorption of dyes onto HNT as a function of solution temperature was studied using the Table 2.1. The influence of temperature on BG dye adsorption onto HNT is presented in Figure 3.4d. The data obtained for the classical thermodynamic parameters, namely, ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° indicate the nature and type of a reaction. For example, the negative ΔH° (enthalpy) values obtained from 303 to 323 K of HNT indicate exothermic process. The overall negative values of ΔG° (free energy) obtained for BG-HNT system confirm the spontaneity and viability of the adsorption process. The magnitude of ΔG° values is indicative of rapid and spontaneous adsorption at lower temperature. Further, it is inferred that the negative values of ΔS° (entropy) suggest minimum changes in the internal structure of HNT. Similar observation has been reported elsewhere [32].

Figure 3.4: Effect of (a) pH, (b) initial dye concentration, (C_o) with percent removal efficiency, (c) adsorbent dosage and (d) temperature of BG-HNT

3.4 Adsorption Isotherms - Modeling Analysis

The study of the isotherm models was intended to provide a view of efficiency of HNT for the remediation of the dye for commercial applications with an eye on degree of economic advantages. The data of adsorption of BG dye onto HNT were analyzed using the adsorption isotherm models proposed by Langmuir, Freundlich, Jovanovic, Dubinin-Radushkevich, Toth, Brouers-Sotolongo, Vieth-Sladek, Radke-Prausnitz and Redlich-Peterson isotherm models. The main criterion of the study of adsorption isotherms was to select a model, where q_e (the experimental equilibrium) values were almost equal to Q_m (monolayer adsorption capacity) value with coefficient of determination (R^2) value ≥ 0.90 . To refine the data and to make a distinction between similar results obtained by various isotherm models, SSE and χ^2 as two additional error functions were incorporated in our study.

Langmuir [33] proposed a model on the assumption that the adsorbent will have active sites possessing almost uniform energies. This was further established on the idea that no lateral interaction takes place between adsorbed molecules. A plateau in a two-dimensional graph with equilibrium concentration (C_e) as independent variable and q_e (Figure 3.5a) as dependent variable characterizes the saturation of the active sites on the surface of the adsorbent. This implies that further adsorption cannot take place and the possibility of multilayer adsorption of the dye is ruled out. The equations of the Langmuir isotherm model are shown in Eqs. 4 and 5 - Table 2.1. The experimental data, $R^2 = 0.82$, $q_e = 87.00 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$ and $Q_m = 124.15 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$ for BG-HNT system indicate nearly fit to the Langmuir adsorption isotherm model. The separation factor (R_L) values of 0.039 and 0.247 indicate favourable adsorption of BG dye onto HNT. Moreover, the adsorption is considered more favourable if the increase in initial concentrations decreases the R_L value. This is in contradiction to our results displayed in Figure 3.5a. Additionally, the variance between Q_m and q_e values of 124.15 and 87.00 mg g^{-1} respectively for HNT has given impetus to explore other models.

In contrast to Langmuir isotherm model, Freundlich proposed heterogeneity of the surface sites with different energy of adsorption and demonstrated relevance to multilayer adsorption [34]. The mathematical expression is shown in Eq. 6 – Table 2.1. The values of $n_F = 4.060$ and $1/n_F = 0.246$ (Table 3.2) of HNT indicate that the process of adsorption is physical in nature and suits the behaviour of Langmuir Isotherm.

The Jovanovic model [35] attempts to minimize the deviancies of the experimental results obtained from the Langmuir isotherm model by introducing the exponential term K_J . The mathematical model is presented in Eq. 7 – Table 2.1. On comparing the difference in the values of $q_e = 87.00 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$ and $Q_m = 109.71 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$ with the values obtained by Langmuir isotherm model one may surmise that values obtained in Jovanovic isotherm is better to Langmuir isotherm model.

The adsorption isotherm empirical model proposed by Dubinin-Radushkevich [36] describes the process of adsorption through filling of the pore of the adsorbent. The mathematical model is presented in Eq. 8 – Table 2.1. A value of 110.59 mg g^{-1} for q_s is more compared to the Langmuir and Jovanovic models (Table 3.2). A value of 0.97 coefficient of determination (R^2) confirms that the process of adsorption is linear (Figure 3.5b).

In pursuit to identify specific model(s) which has smaller gap between experimental q_e values and Q_m values; five isotherm models, namely, Toth, Brouers-Sotolongo, Vieth-Sladek, Redlich-Peterson and Radke-Prausnitz, were also studied. The importance of these models is described by us elsewhere [37]. To describe heterogeneous adsorption system an empirical mathematical Eq. 9 - Table 2.1 was developed by Toth [38]. Eq. 10 and Eq. 11 - Table 2.1 represent Brouers-Sotolongo isotherm model [39] and Vieth-Sladek isotherm model [40] respectively. The results are presented in Figure 3.5c. The mathematical Eq. 12 - Table 2.1 represents Radke-Prausnitz isotherm model [41]. Redlich-Peterson isotherm model [42] Eq. 13 - Table 3.2 has 'g' value of 1.638 as correction exponent which show similarity to Langmuir isotherm (Figure 3.5d).

The data obtained using five three-parameter models are presented in Table 3.2. The study of nine isotherm models and evaluation of statistical parameters are presented in Table 3.2. In brief, the graphs obtained by nine models have the similarity that it contains two parts, viz., nonlinear part and a plateau. The former, indicates that the dye molecule adheres to the active site of the porous HNT and the latter characterizes the saturation of the adsorption process. Considering the values of R^2 , SSE and χ^2 ; Redlich-peterson isotherm model fits best.

Figure 3.5: Fitting of adsorption data to (a) Langmuir and Freundlich, (b) Jovanovic and Dubinin-Radushkevich, (c) Vieth-Sladek and Brouers-Sotolongo and (d) Redlich-Petersen, Radke-Prausnitz and Toth adsorption isotherm of BG-HNT system

Table 3.2: Calculated parameters of adsorption isotherms

Two-parameter isotherms								Three-parameter isotherms									
Langmuir	Freundlich	Jovanovic	Dubinin-Radushkevich		Toth	Brouers-Sotolongo		Vieth-Sladek		Radke-Prausnitz		Redlich-Peterson					
Q_m	124.2	K_F	37.9	Q_m	109.7	Q_s	110.6	Q_m	106.4	Q_m	107.1	Q_m	124.2	Q_m	774.8	A_{RP}	7.8
K_S	0.12	n_F	4.06	K_J	0.09	K_{ad}	6.43E-06	n_{T0}	12.50	K_{BS}	0.02	K_{VS}	1E-07	k_{rp}	0.01	B_{RP}	0.01
								b_{T0}	1.13*10 ¹⁵	α	1.61	β_{VS}	0.12	m_{rp}	2.89	g	1.64

Table 3.3: Statistical parameters for isotherm model fitting

Isotherms	Langmuir	Freundlich	Jovanovic	Dubinin-Radushkevich	Toth	Brouers-Sotolongo	Vieth-Sladek	Radke-Prausnitz	Redlich-Peterson
SSE	1581.8	3506.7	777.9	544.4	311.1	311.8	1581.8	244.5	140.7
χ^2	31.28	77.08	12.84	7.82	4.47	3.61	31.29	7.70	4.63
R^2	0.91	0.92	0.99	0.94	0.96	0.96	0.82	0.98	0.98

Table 3.4: Experimentally determined and theoretically predicted parameters for adsorption kinetics models

Initial Concentration [$\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$]	Temp [K]	$q_{e, \text{expt}}$ [mg g^{-1}]	Pseudo-first-order				Pseudo-second-order			
			$q_{e, \text{pred}}$ [mg g^{-1}]	k_1	R^2	χ^2	$q_{e, \text{pred}}$ [mg g^{-1}]	k_2	R^2	χ^2
50	303	40	35.96	6.63E-02	0.94	0.59	44.26	1.64E-03	0.97	3.94
	313	44	117.53	2.28E-02	1.00	149.57	48.08	1.79E-03	0.96	0.32
	323	47	45.09	5.32E-02	0.96	0.80	57.85	9.04E-04	0.97	0.48
100	303	86	38.86	1.02E-01	0.91	8.51	44.68	3.12E-03	0.91	0.48
	313	89	43.90	4.39E+01	0.93	1.54	65.88	1.71E-03	0.93	1.65
	323	93	43.32	1.07E-01	0.94	1.58	49.70	2.94E-03	0.94	0.76
150	303	110	77.79	1.95E-01	0.91	0.36	82.43	5.33E-03	0.95	0.07
	313	117	85.27	4.76E-02	0.94	1.65	111.58	4.01E-04	0.97	0.92
	323	122	96.90	4.04E-02	0.96	4.99	127.72	2.95E-04	0.90	3.61

3.5 Adsorption Kinetics

Kinetic models provide an insight on the performance of adsorption of DB15 dye on HNT with time as independent variable. The studies will have a great impact to scale for commercial applications. To provide the variation in adsorption rate, a concentration of 50, 100 and 150 g mL⁻¹ of BG dye was used to carry out kinetic studies at 303, 313 and 323 K. The results are presented in Table 3.4 and Figure 3.6. The kinetic data of adsorption of BG on minerals was analysed using pseudo-first-order Eq. 14 - Table 2.1 [43] and pseudo-second-order Eq. 15 - Table 2.1 [44]. The R^2 and χ^2 values suggest the pseudo-second-order model is well-fitted compared to pseudo-first-order for the BG-HNT system.

Analysis of adsorption kinetics data confirmed multiple levels of linearity, which in turn suggests multiple mechanisms. Higher concentrations and higher temperature leads to higher adsorption rate which leads to different linear routes. However, the process of adsorption gets stabilized with respect to time. This was observed in film diffusion model Eq. 16 - Table 2.1 [45]. It can be seen from Figure 3.7 and Table 3.5 that the values of diffusion constant R' of a liquid film are in agreement with high R^2 values. Furthermore, the values of R' infers, fast adsorption of solute onto the surface of the particles leaving a thin film. The phenomena retard the process of diffusion which affects the rate of adsorption. This step confirms that the adsorption process is limited by diffusion phenomenon.

Figure 3.6: Kinetic model fits for (a) $50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ (b) $100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and (c) $150 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ initial concentration of BG dye on HNT system at different temperatures

Figure 3.7: Kinetics data fitted to the Film diffusion model with initial BG concentration (a) $50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ (b) $100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and (c) $150 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$

Table 3.5: Calculated parameters for diffusion models

Initial Concentration [$\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$]	Temp [K]	Film diffusion model		Weber-Morris model		Dumwald-Wagner	
		R' [min^{-1}]	R^2	k_{ist} [$\text{mg g}^{-1} \text{s}^{-0.5}$]	R^2	K [min^{-1}]	R^2
50	303	0.0372	0.98	3.73	0.99	0.032	0.97
	313	0.0397	0.99	3.88	0.99	0.035	0.98
	323	0.0437	0.99	5.12	0.97	0.038	0.98
100	303	0.0055	0.99	3.08	0.98	0.032	0.99
	313	0.0078	0.99	4.49	0.99	0.005	0.99
	323	0.0060	0.99	3.42	0.97	0.004	0.98
150	303	0.0066	0.90	2.67	0.94	0.005	0.90
	313	0.0171	0.99	9.95	0.99	0.012	0.99
	323	0.0202	0.96	11.09	0.96	0.023	0.97

3.6 Mechanistic Study

Mathematical models of adsorption reaction and adsorption diffusion are proposed to identify the importance of diffusion in the adsorption process of the BG dye onto HNT. We have resorted to a functional empirical relationship of the uptake of the substrate at a given time q_t varying almost proportionally with $t^{1/2}$. This was done by fitting an intraparticle diffusion model Eq. 17 - Table 2.1. These results demonstrate that the process of adsorption is not rate-limiting and the progression of adsorption is taking place in multiple steps. Thus, it may be envisaged that the movement of BG dye molecules onto the surface of HNT precedes the diffusion into the pores of HNT.

According to the Weber-Morris model [32] the solute uptake varies with $t^{1/2}$ as shown in Eq. 18 - Table 2.1. A straight line was obtained on plotting q_t versus $t^{1/2}$. The diffusion rate constant was calculated from the slope of the straight line as shown in Figure 3.8. From the data we arrived at a conclusion that intraparticle diffusion is the rate-limiting step for the process of adsorption of the dye on the adsorbent. Hence q_t versus $t^{1/2}$ plot should provide a straight line whose slope (k_{int}) will be the diffusion rate constant (Figure 3.8). The shape of the curve infers that the intraparticle diffusion is not the sole rate-limiting step. Conversely, the Dumwald-Wagner model [46] calculates the true absorption rate (Eq. 19 - Table 2.1). The data are presented in Table 3.5 and Figure 3.9.

Figure 3.8: Kinetics data fitted to the Weber-Morris model with initial BG concentration (a) 50 µg mL⁻¹ (b) 100 µg mL⁻¹ and (c) 150 µg mL⁻¹

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Figure 3.9: Kinetics data fitted to Dumwald-Wagner model with initial BG concentration (a) 50 µg mL⁻¹ (b) 100 µg mL⁻¹ and (c) 150 µg mL⁻¹

3.7 Thermodynamics of the Adsorption Process

Gibbs free energy change (ΔG°) and entropy (ΔS°) of the dye-HNT system are the main features of the process design of adsorption thermodynamics. The relationship of ΔH° , ΔS° and E_a are presented in Eqs. - 20, 21, 22 and 23 - Table 2.1. The thermodynamic parameters presented in Table 3.6 were obtained from the plots of $\ln(K_d)$ versus $1/T$ shown in Figure 3.10. The values of ΔG° suggest that the adsorption process is almost spontaneous. The decrease in the negative values of ΔG° with increase in the temperature infers that the reaction is almost spontaneous at lower temperature. The positive values of ΔS° indicate the decrease in the randomness at dye/HNT interface.

Table 3.6: Thermodynamic parameters of BG-HNT system

Initial Concentration [$\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$]	Temp [K]	ΔG° [kJ mol $^{-1}$]	ΔS° [J mol $^{-1}$ K $^{-1}$]	ΔH° [kJ mol $^{-1}$]	ln A	E_a [kJ mol $^{-1}$]
50	303	-6.54	486.19	120.45	2.90	38.33
	313	-6.37				
	323	-6.15				
100	303	-5.95	645.33	233.61	4.51	59.69
	313	-5.74				
	323	-5.14				
150	303	-3.93	862.91	432.70	6.46	73.76
	313	-3.62				
	323	-3.31				

Figure 3.10: Plot of thermodynamic equilibrium constant versus $1/T$ to determine the enthalpy and Gibbs free energy of BG-HNT

3.8. Statistical Process Optimization

Quadratic model in FEED under RSM was used to statistically optimize the adsorption capacity [47]. The model can be explained by the following general equation.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_i X_i + \sum \beta_{ii} X_i^2 + \sum \beta_{ij} X_i X_j$$

Where Y represents the dependent response variable, β_0 is a regression coefficient, β_i is the linear effect, β_{ii} is the squared effect and β_{ij} is the interaction effect of independent variable X. Statistical software was used for RSM study and graphical representation of 3D and contour plots for the effect of independent variables on the response. The quadratic regression equation derived from ANOVA shows the possible individual and combined effect of the factors for BG-HNT system (Table 3.7). The p -value < 0.05% with 95% confidence interval was considered significant.

Table 3.7: ANOVA table of BG-HNT system

Source	Sum of Squares	Degree of freedom	Mean Square	F-Value	P-Value
Model	60415.24	13	4647.33	30.12	<0.001
A	18483.5	1	18483.5	119.8	<0.0001
B	66.8	1	66.8	0.4	0.5128
C	17876.0	1	17876.0	115.8	<0.0001
D	6660.9	1	6660.9	43.2	<0.0001
E	479.8	1	479.8	3.1	0.0821
AB	217.6	1	217.6	1.4	0.2389
AC	1176.8	1	1176.8	7.6	0.0073
BC	1.32	1	1.3	0.0086	0.9265
A ²	736.5	1	736.5	4.8	0.0322
B ²	100.7	1	100.7	0.7	0.4218
C ²	223.0	1	223.0	1.4	0.2333
D ²	2437.6	1	2437.6	15.8	0.0002
E ²	494.3	1	494.3	3.2	0.0777
F ²	552.6	1	736.5	4.8	0.0322
Residual	10955.8	71	154.3		
Total	71371.0	84			

The graphs in Figure 3.11 suggest a strong correlation between the experimental data and expected responses. A, C, D, A², C², D², and E² are significant model terms for the BG-HNT system. The regression Equation obtained for BG-HNT system is shown below:

$$\text{BG-HNT} = 4.2 + 26.1 * A + 1.4 * B + 37.1 * C - 40.9 * D + 10.2 * E + 3.2 * AB + 11.4 * AC - 0.4 * BC + 11.3 * A^2 + 3.3 * B^2 + 8.3 * C^2 + 46.5 * D^2 + 16.8 * E^2$$

Figure 3.11: Actual versus predicted values of BG-HNT

The values of the regression coefficient indicate the effect of the parameter(s) on the adsorption capacity. The surface and contour plots illustrate the combined effect of two factors on the process of adsorption and the results are graphically presented in Figure 3.12a and Figure 3.12b. Under optimized conditions evolved through statistical modeling a value of $q_e = 203 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$ was obtained at initial dye concentration of 344 mg L^{-1} at pH 12, adsorbent dosage of 0.52 g L^{-1} for an adsorption time of 180 min with orbital shaking of 165 rpm at temperature 27.7°C .

Figure 3.12A: 3D surface plot and contour plot showing the variation of adsorption capacity with (a) time versus temperature, (b) time versus concentration, (c) time versus adsorbent dosage, (d) time versus pH, (e) temperature versus concentration

Figure 3.12B: 3D surface plot and contour plot showing the variation of adsorption capacity with (a) temperature versus adsorbent dosage, (b) temperature versus pH, (c) concentration versus adsorbent dosage, (d) concentration versus pH and (e) adsorbent dosage versus pH

3.9 Conclusion

The interactions between the HNT as adsorbent and BG dye as adsorbate showed experimental equilibrium (q_e) value of 91.00 mg g⁻¹ at pH 2; 84.00 mg g⁻¹ at almost neutral pH and 203 mg g⁻¹ at statistically optimized conditions. To understand the process of adsorption, nine isotherm models were studied. The adsorption follows Redlich-Peterson isotherm model. The interactions between HNT and BG were physical in nature and follow second-order kinetics. Contact time, dye concentration, dosage and initial pH of the solution have profound influence on adsorption process. Preliminary investigations to regenerate dye-adsorbed HNT were carried out. It was found that the cost of the process of regeneration was higher than the cost of the adsorbent. Moreover, the dye-modified HNT was found as promising reinforcing material for the fabrication of the composites using plastic waste.

In brief, the present work has relevance to three industrial sectors, namely, Textile industries, Clay minerals and Plastic industries. The industrial production has a linear model to create value in making the product and completes the life-cycle with the disposal after-use. This model seriously affects the environment due to the ever-increasing problem of resource depletion. To address the issue of resource depletion there is a need from the industries to shift from the virgin inputs to recycled and/or reuse the products in line with circular economy. This research is a step towards this direction.

3.10 References

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Chapter 4

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF LOW-COST SUSTAINABLE BENT AND MT UNMODIFIED CLAY MINERALS FOR THE REMEDIATION OF THE TOXIC BISAZO DYE DR13 FROM TEXTILE INDUSTRIAL EFFLUENT

The potential use of low-cost, abundantly available, eco-friendly and unmodified bentonite (Bent), montmorillonite K10 (Mt) and kaolin light (K) as adsorbents for the remediation of Direct red 13 (DR13), a bisazo dye, from textile industrial effluent (TIE) is reported. The parameters affecting the adsorption capacity, kinetics and equilibrium were evaluated. Toth isotherm model was found to be best fit for the dye uptake process. The predominant kinetic mechanism fits best to pseudo-second-order reaction. Film diffusion studies indicated that the external mass transfer phenomena were more likely to be dominant over the diffusion process. The low ΔH° values indicate that the process of adsorption is physical in nature. Weak interactions like Van der Waal forces and hydrogen bonds play major roles as supported by FT-IR analysis. Statistical model was developed for optimization of adsorption processes. Prospects on the use of dye-adsorbed clay mineral for the fabrication of composites are reported.

4.1 Introduction

The concern towards pollution of textile industries has led to stringent regulations to amputate toxic and hazardous substances from effluents [1]. This has led to extensive use of activated carbon because of higher surface area which supports fast kinetics and better adsorption [2]. The economic constraints faced by the industries for using high cost activated carbon have led to the resurgence of cheap and abundantly available biomass and inorganic materials [3, 4]. These materials display low adsorption capacity compared to activated carbon. A lot of research is devoted to enhance the adsorption capacity by the process of modification [5]. It is our understanding that enhancement in adsorption capacity of the modified adsorbents is marginal and does not commensurate with large inputs of cost, labour and time of the resultant material [4-6]. Besides, the process of modification of the adsorbents augments carbon and water footprints and increases the E-factor [7]. Thus, it is desirable to optimize the process based on the cost, abundant availability, and prospects of reusing the material after the remediation vis-à-vis the adsorption capacity of the adsorbent material.

Textile industry ranks one amongst most polluting industries. The global textile market is dominated by reactive dyes owing to the widespread use in the textile and leather industry [8]. Azo dyes are reactive dyes containing chemical groups (-N=N-) and represent about 70% of all the total dyes used in textile industry. They exhibit characteristic features; such as, low cost of synthesis, availability in the extensive range of colours, high intensity, colour fastness and dyeing process at 60°C. Associated with these advantages, the azo dyes pose serious health risk to humans. Moreover, they affect aesthetic merit, transparency and water-gas solubility. One of the major reasons for the health hazard is the loss of over 50% of the colorant during the dyeing process. This is due to lack of appropriate technology to improve the efficacy of azo molecules attachment to the fabric and/or matrix [1]. Thus, the treatment of the textile industrial effluent assumes paramount importance. The treatment techniques, methods, procedures and protocols can broadly be classified into biological, chemical, physico-chemical and physical methods. However, these methods have deficiencies and limitations (6).

Adsorption technique is extensively used in textiles industries. Cost-effective materials which do not leave ecological foot print [9] and environmental foot print [10] is

desirable. Myriad research articles reported in the literature about the adsorption techniques have failed to address the issue of accumulation of the concentrated “sludge”. The fabrication of composites using plastic waste and “sludge” as filler material was first demonstrated by our research school [11]. The unmodified clay minerals have been used as reinforcing/filler material for the fabrication of composites [12]. Hence, it is desirable to use unmodified clay minerals and find an alternate approach to provide value-addition to the ‘waste by-products’ commonly known as “sludge”. Keeping in view the reuse of the “sludge” we have chosen unmodified representative clay minerals, bentonite (Bent), montmorillonite K10 (Mt) and kaolin light (K) all containing hydrated aluminium silicate in tune with circular economy [13, 14]. These minerals are cheap, eco-friendly, abundantly available, show high adsorption rate and exhibit high ionexchange capacity for the amputation of the bisazo dye from water and textile industrial effluent (TIE) [4, 6, 7].

Direct Red 13 (DR13) is a bisazo anionic dye with comparable structure as that of Congo red. Its metabolized product is benzidine, which is a known human carcinogen. The high solubility of sodium salt of the dye in water renders it difficult for biodegradation [15, 16]. In the present paper, the first-ever study on the use of Bent, Mt and K for the removal of DR13 dye and preliminary investigations on the resultant dye adsorbed clay, commonly known as “sludge” used for the fabrication of the composites are reported.

4.2 Materials and Methods

4.2.1 Materials

Bentonite (colloidal native hydrated aluminum silicate) (Bent) and Kaolin light (bole white powder – aluminum silicate hydrated) (K) were procured from SD Fine-chem Limited, India. Montmorillonite K10 (MT) and Direct Red 13 dye were obtained from Aldrich, India. The mineral samples were heated at 373 K for 8 h, cooled and kept in a desiccator before use. DR13 dye is soluble in water and ethanol producing wine red and red color respectively. It is insoluble in many organic solvents. [C.I. = 22155; CAS registry number=1937-35-5; chemical formula = $C_{32}H_{22}N_6Na_2O_7S_2$; molecular weight = 712.66. Initial and residual dye concentration was determined using the Perkin-Elmer Lambda EZ-201 UV-vis spectrometer

at absorbance maximum (λ_{\max}) = 503 nm. The molecular structures of the DR13 dye in acidic and basic pH are shown in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: Structures of Direct Red 13 dye in aqueous media

4.2.2 Studies on the variables affecting adsorption of DR13 dye on clay minerals

Batch experiment approach was adopted to study the influence of pH, initial dye concentration, adsorbent dosage and temperature as experimental parameters on the adsorption process. For preparing stock solution of DR13 (1000 mg L⁻¹) double distilled water was used. Solution concentrations in the range 25–500 mg L⁻¹ were made by diluting the stock solution. To a series of 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks, 50 mL of 300 mg L⁻¹ DR13 dye solution and 0.050 g of Bent were added. Evaluations were then conducted based on the effects of varying parameters such as, pH, DR13 dye initial concentration, dosage of adsorbent and temperature. Solution was subjected to stirring in a thermostatic orbital shaker 165 rpm for 180 min. Samples were withdrawn at predetermined equilibrium time. The

unadsorbed DR13 dye solution was separated from Bent mineral by centrifugation with 3000 rpm for five minutes. If the solution was unclear the centrifugation was repeated for an additional five min. The concentration of the DR13 dye at equilibrium pertaining to the supernatant centrifuged solution was determined using a UV-visible spectrophotometer. To study the effect of initial solution pH, adsorption studies were carried out in pH range 2-12. The initial solution pH was controlled by adding either dilute HCl or NaOH (0.01-1.00 M). Three temperatures, 303, 313 and 323 K were selected and experiments carried out as a function of 60 min equilibrium time to study adsorption kinetics of DR13 dye solution (300 mg L⁻¹). Experiments were replicated thrice and the mean values are considered. The experiments were repeated with Mt and K clay minerals.

4.2.3 Characterization methods

IR spectra were recorded using the FTIR spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer 3 lambda). Scanning electron microscope (JEOL model 3300) was used to record SEM images. A pH meter Model 802 - Systronics, India was used to measure pH. Point-of- zero charge (pH_{PZC}) of Bent, Mt and K was determined by carrying out the procedure described by us elsewhere [17].

4.2.4 Statistical optimization of process parameters

The five independent variables affecting adsorption of DR13 dye on clay minerals using batch experiments namely, time of contact of dye and adsorbent (A), temperature of the system (B), initial dye concentration (C), adsorbent dosage (D) and pH (E) (Table 4.1) of the solution using two-level Fractional Factorial Experimental Design (FEED) to statistically optimize the adsorption capacity of Bent and Mt. The data was fitted to a second-order polynomial model for calculating the optimum conditions to obtain a quadratic regression equation. The empirical second-order polynomial model is as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_i X_i + \sum \beta_{ii} X_i^2 + \sum \beta_{ij} X_i X_j$$

Where Y represents the dependent response variable, β_0 is a regression coefficient, β_i is the linear effect, β_{ii} is the squared effect and β_{ij} is the interaction effect of independent variable X. Statistical software was used to study Response Surface Methodology (RSM) and

to draw 3-D graphs and 2-D contour plots to evaluate the effect of independent variables on the response (dependent variable). Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used as a tool for the analyses of data obtained from polynomial models using 95% confidence level and a value of coefficient of determination $R^2 \geq 0.90$.

Table 4.1: Experimental design for individual factors for RSM studies

Factor	Name	Units	Minimum	Maximum
A	Time	minutes	0	180
B	Temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	27	50
C	Concentration	mg L^{-1}	25	500
D	Adsorbent dosage	g L^{-1}	0.5	6
E	pH	-	2	12

4.3 Results and Discussion

4.3.1 Surface characterization of the clay minerals

4.3.1.1 SEM and FTIR spectroscopy analyses

SEM images of Bent and Mt and dye adsorbed minerals display a thin film over the particles of the clay minerals. The images are shown in Figures 4.2a, 4.2b, 4.3a and 4.3b. The FTIR of DR13 (Figure 4.4a) displayed a vibration band at around 3650 cm^{-1} which is referred to as moisture adsorb onto the surface of the dye. Bent clay mineral with Al-centered octahedral displayed stretching vibration of the inner surface -OH groups at 3660 cm^{-1} which forms hydrogen bonds with the oxygen of the Si-O double layer which shows a stretching band at 1010 cm^{-1} . Figure 4.4a shows the change in the shape with change in the intensity of the peaks at 3650 , 1640 , 1566 , 1500 , 1185 and 1010 cm^{-1} which are referred to -OH, N=N, C=C, -C-N- and Si-O respectively in Bent and DR13 structure. It can be explained that the mutual effects and interactions between the components denote adsorption of DR13 dye on Bent.

Figure 4.4b presents FTIR spectra of Mt. The spectra consists of a broadband at 3353 - 3454 cm^{-1} is attributed to -OH groups and adsorbed water molecules, while C-O and C-H stretching frequencies are seen as sharp bands at 1598 and 2852 cm^{-1} . The C-O-C stretching

bands appeared at 1091,1158,1355,1404 and 1418 cm^{-1} respectively. Observation of the spectra recorded after the adsorption of DR13 dye on Mt mineral revealed the disappearance of broad bands at 3300-3500 cm^{-1} and 3353-3454 cm^{-1} . This observation confirms the formation of hydrogen bonds between $-\text{NH}_2$ and hydroxyl groups. Strong adsorption of DR13 dye on Mt clay mineral is endorsed to the disappearance of N-N stretching frequency at 1598 cm^{-1} .

Figure 4.2: SEM image of a) Bent and b) DR13-Bent

Figure 4.3: SEM image of a) Mt and b) DR13-Mt

Figure 4.4a: FTIR spectra of DR13 dye, Bent and DR13-Bent

Figure 4.4b: FTIR spectra of DR13 dye, Mt and DR13-Mt

4.3.1.2 The role of point of zero charge (pH_{pzc})

DR13 is a disodium ionic dye, when placed in a solvent of high dielectric constant, such as water, dissociates to give anionic and cationic species. The three minerals under study, namely, Bent, Mt and K exhibit ionic character when placed in water. The ionic affinity of three minerals is pH dependent. As the pH of the solution in contact with the mineral is reduced below the pH_{pzc} , the surface of the mineral becomes positively charged. Conversely, as the pH is increased above pH_{pzc} , the surface becomes negatively charged. The protonation and deprotonation of the surface hydroxyl groups of the minerals is shown in Figures 4.5a, 4.5b and 4.5c.

Figure 4.5: Point of zero charge of (a) Bent (b) Mt and (c) K

pH_{PZC} studied for the three minerals, Bent, Mt and K are 7.60, 6.69 and 7.90 respectively. The plateau obtained for Bent and Mt between pH 4 and pH 10 infers that generic properties of surface charge, replicate certain macroscopic conditions imposed by electro neutrality and thermodynamic stability [18, 19]. This observation offers a great advantage for the use of Bent and Mt as adsorbents in remediation of DR13 in a wide range of pH 4 to 10 for textile industrial effluent. Conversely, K did not display encouraging results.

4.3.2 The influence of variables on DR13 adsorption on clay minerals

4.3.2.1 Effect of solution pH

The adsorption capacity of the clay mineral depends on solution pH. The pH plays two important roles; first, it influences the characteristics of adsorbent surface and second, the chemistry of the dye solution [20]. Contrary to the common observation the adsorption

capacity of Bent and Mt was found to be almost independent of pH between the ranges 4 to 10. Similar observation was observed for K but at low adsorption capacity (Figures 4.6a, 4.6b and 4.6c). The latter observation is similar to our studies on kaolinite [21]. This can be explained as follows: Bent and Mt have almost similar structures. They present octahedral alumina between two tetrahedral silica layers. Both the minerals are highly colloidal and have the ability to absorb large quantities of water due to weak electrostatic forces. On the contrary, K is reported to be the least reactive clay [22].

Figure 4.6: Effect of pH on adsorption of DR13 on (a) Bent (b) Mt and (c) K

4.3.2.2 Effect of initial dye concentration

The methods available for colour measurement are colorimetry and spectrophotometry. The main disadvantage of colorimetric method is time consuming. Conversely, spectrophotometric method by knowing molar absorption coefficient (ϵ) of dye solution will help in the calculations of the absorbance of the dye at a given wavelength. The procedure for the calculation of ϵ is described elsewhere [23]. The adsorbed amount of DR13 dye at equilibrium q_e (mg g^{-1}) at a given time q_t (mg g^{-1}) and percentage removal efficiency

(RE %) of the dye from aqueous solutions was determined using the Eqs. 1, 2 and 3 - Table 2.1. Mean values of three trials of the adsorption experiments were used in data analysis. Control experiments were performed with the addition of Bent, Mt or K.

The effect of initial DR13 dye concentration has profound influence on the adsorption capacity of clay minerals. The per cent adsorption capacity of Bent remains almost constant around 80% in the range 25-500 mg L⁻¹; while, Mt displayed a plateau between 25–300 mg L⁻¹ and gradually decreased to 60% in the range 300-500 mg L⁻¹. The novel behaviour exhibited by Bent and Mt in range 50-500 mg L⁻¹ and 50-300 mg L⁻¹ respectively is in contradiction to the earlier observation that increase in initial dye concentration leads to a decrease in the percentage of dye removal from the bulk solution. However, Mt behaves to the trend between 300-500 mg L⁻¹. The behaviour of Bent and Mt gives scope to scale to commercial applications as the industrial effluents have undefined composition, while, K does not show any encouraging results (Figures 4.7a, 4.7b and 4.7c).

Figure 4.7: Effect of initial dye concentration on adsorption of DR13 dye with % removal efficiency of (a) Bent (b) Mt and (c) K

4.3.2.3 Effect of adsorbent dosage

The dosage as a parameter will have profound influence on the commercialization of the process, because it decides the economic feasibility. Increase in adsorbent dose enhances the removal of dye from the solution. However, no significant changes were observed beyond 6.000 g L⁻¹. The results are depicted in Figures 4.8a, 4.8b and 4.8c. K did not give encouraging results.

Figure 4.8: Effect of dosage on adsorption of DR13 (a) Bent (b) Mt and (c) K

4.3.2.4 Effect of temperature

Keeping in view, our focus to scale to commercial applications [24], evaluation of the process of adsorption of dyes onto the clays as function of solution temperature was studied using the Eqs. 4 and 5 - Table 2.1. The influence of temperature on DR13 dye adsorption onto the mineral clays is presented in Figs. 4.9a, 4.9b and 4.9c. ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° are the important thermodynamic parameters used to describe thermodynamic behaviour of the process of adsorption.

Figure 4.9: Effect of temperature on adsorption of DR13 (a) Bent (b) Mt and (c) K

The negative enthalpy (ΔH°) values obtained by increasing the temperature of adsorption process from 303 to 323 K of all clay minerals indicate exothermic process. The overall negative values of free energy (ΔG°) obtained for three systems namely, DR13-Bent, DR13-Mt and DR13-K confirm the feasibility and the spontaneous nature of the adsorption process in the order Bent>Mt>>K. The magnitude of ΔG° values is indicative of rapid and spontaneous adsorption at lower temperature. Further, it is inferred that the negative values of entropy (ΔS°) suggests minimum changes in the internal structure of the clay minerals. Similar observation has been reported elsewhere [25]. Preliminary investigations on K did not give encouraging results to commensurate with needs and demands of commercialization of the process. Thus, further studies on K were not pursued.

4.4 Adsorption Isotherms - Modeling Analysis

Adsorption as process comprises of mass transfer phenomena of the species from the liquid phase (dye solution) onto the adsorbent (clay minerals) in three steps; first, the transfer of dye from solution onto external surface of the solid adsorbent, also known as external film diffusion; second, percolating into the solid pores by liquid phase diffusion and surface diffusion, commonly known as intraparticle diffusion. This step is slower than the other steps which influence the kinetics of the process. The latter step has two segments, first, adsorption kinetics described by mass transfer processes and second, adsorption equilibrium between the concentration of the bulk dye solution and adsorbent surface concentrations which are reached almost instantaneously inside the pores. These segments help in constructing an adsorption isotherm [26, 27]. Adsorption isotherm models record the distribution of DR13 dye between the bulk solution and adsorbent at various equilibrium concentrations. Also, the study of the remediation of the dye was planned to provide a prospect of the adsorption process under study to indicate the efficiency of the clay minerals for economic feasibility to scale for commercial applications. The data of adsorption of DR13 dye onto Bent and Mt were analyzed with the help of Langmuir, Freundlich, Jovanovic, Toth, Brouers-Sotolongo, Sips, Vieth-Sladek, Radke-Prausnitz and Redlich-Peterson isotherm models.

The main criterion to study different isotherm models is to select the best fit which has monolayer adsorption capacity Q_m value as closer to experimental equilibrium q_e value with coefficient of determination (R^2) ≥ 0.90 . In our study we found that R^2 for all the nine models studied display a value of 0.99. Thus, sum square error (SSE) and chi-square test (χ^2) as two additional error functions were also calculated to arrive at the best fit.

Langmuir [28] established an isotherm model on the basis of two important assumptions. The surface of the adsorbent has a finite number of almost identical adsorption sites having uniform energies and no lateral interaction takes place between adsorbed molecules. A two-dimensional graphical representation of equilibrium concentration (C_e) as independent variable and adsorption capacity of the adsorbent (q_e) as dependent variable are shown in Figs. 4.10a and 4.10b. The part of the curve which resembles a plateau characterizes the saturation point where no further adsorption can follow. In other words, no further adsorption of the dye can take place on the already occupied site by the dye molecule which envisages that only a monolayer adsorption can take place.

Figure 4.10: Fitting of DR13 dye adsorption data to Langmuir, Freundlich and Jovanovic adsorption isotherm (a) Bent and (b) Mt

Mathematical expressions of the Langmuir isotherm model are shown in Eqs. 6 and 7 - Table 2.1. The Q_m values 1233.0 and 582.0 mg g^{-1} obtained are high compared to the experimental q_e values 248.0 and 255.0 mg g^{-1} for Bent and Mt respectively. The experimental data and values of coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.99 and 0.99 for Bent and Mt respectively show a good fit to the Langmuir isotherm model. The R_L values calculated for Bent and Mt were between 0.316 and 0.847; 0.254 and 0.732 respectively. These values indicate favourable adsorption of DR13 dye onto the clay minerals. The decrease in R_L value with increase in initial concentration indicates that the adsorption is more favourable at high concentration. The large difference between Q_m (1233.0 mg g^{-1} and 582.0 mg g^{-1}) and q_e (248.0 and 255.0 mg g^{-1}) for Bent and Mt respectively has made the authors explore other adsorption isotherm models.

Freundlich isotherm model validates that the surface of the adsorbent is always heterogeneous. It further assumes that the process takes place at adsorption sites with different energy of adsorption [29]. The mathematical model proposed by Freundlich is also applicable to multilayer adsorption and is expressed in the Eq. 8 – Table 2.1. The values of n_F and $1/n_F$ 1.14 and 0.877 (Bent) and 1.34 and 0.747 (Mt) indicate that the adsorption is physisorption and favours normal Langmuir Isotherm. The values of K_F and n_F are presented in Table 4.2. The R^2 values of 0.99 each for Bent and Mt show that the process is linear.

The Jovanovic model [30] introduces the exponential term K_J to minimize the deviations of the experimental results obtained from the Langmuir isotherm model. The mathematical model is presented in Eq. 9 - Table 2.1. The Q_m value of 677.5 mg g^{-1} (Bent)

and 358.8 mg g^{-1} (Mt) obtained in Jovanovic isotherm is high compared to the experimental q_e values 248.0 and 255.0 mg g^{-1} respectively. Comparing the values obtained by Jovanovic model and Langmuir isotherm model, it was found that the former model has Q_m values nearer to the experimental q_e value. The data obtained using three two-parameter models are presented in Table 4.2. In pursuit to identify specific model(s) which has smaller gap between Q_m and q_e values; six three-parameter isotherm models, namely, Toth, Brouers-Sotolongo, Sips, Vieth-Sladek, Redlich-Peterson and Radke-Prausnitz, were also studied.

Figure 4.11: Fitting of DR13 dye adsorption data to Radke-Prausnitz and Sips adsorption isotherm (a) Bent and (b) Mt

Figure 4.12: Fitting of DR13 adsorption data to Vieth-Sladek and Brouers-Sotolongo adsorption isotherm (a) Bent and (b) Mt

Figure 4.13: Fitting of DR13 dye adsorption data to Redlich-Petersen and Toth adsorption isotherm (a) Bent and (b) Mt

To describe heterogeneous adsorption system an empirical mathematical Eq. 10 - Table 2.1 was developed by Toth [31]. Eq. 11 - Table 2.1 represents Brouers-Sotolongo model [32]. Sips isotherm [33] is a combined form of Langmuir and Freundlich expressions deduced for predicting the heterogeneous adsorption systems (Figures 4.11a and 4.11b) and the mathematical equation for the Sips isotherm is shown in Eq. 12 - Table 2.1. The Eq. 13 - Table 2.1 represents the Vieth-Sladek isotherm model and the importance of Vieth-Sladek isotherm [34] is described by us elsewhere [35]. The nonlinear component indicates the adherence of solutes to sites on the surface of porous adsorbents (Figures 4.12a and 4.12b). The mathematical Eq. 14 - Table 2.1 represents Radke-Prausnitz isotherm model [36]. Redlich-Peterson isotherm model [37] as shown in Eq. 15 - Table 2.1 has a correction exponent 'g'. The 'g' value of 3.105 and 1.346 obtained for Bent and Mt respectively, indicates that the adsorption tends towards Langmuir isotherm (Figures 4.13a and 4.13b). The data obtained using six three-parameter models are presented in Table 4.3. The study of nine isotherm models and evaluation of statistical parameters are presented in Table 4.4. The study suggests the Toth isotherm is the best fit for the adsorption process of the dye onto the clay minerals. The data presented in the Table 4.4 display coefficient of determination R^2 value of 0.99 surmises that the process of adsorption of DR13 dye onto Bent or Mt is linear. The study of *SSE* as an error function confirms that Bent is better than Mt, while the study of Chi-square test values favours Bent over Mt (Table 4.4).

Table 4.2: Calculated parameters of two-parameter adsorption isotherms

Two Parameter Isotherms								
Langmuir			Freundlich			Jovanovic		
Constants	Bent	Mt	Constants	Bent	Mt	Constants	Bent	Mt
Q_m	1233.0	582.0	K_F	11.13	13.56	Q_m	677.5	358.7
K_S	0.007	0.015	n_F	1.14	1.34	K_J	0.013	0.023

Table 4.3: Calculated parameters of three-parameter adsorption isotherms

Three Parameter Isotherms																	
Toth		Brouers-Sotolongo			Sips			Vieth-Sladek			Radke- Prausnitz			Redlich-Peterson			
Constants	Bent	Mt	Constants	Bent	Mt	Constants	Bent	Mt	Constants	Bent	Mt	Constants	Bent	Mt	Constants	Bent	Mt
Q_m	269.3	384.0	Q_m	416.4	309.7	Q_m	803.3	441.7	Q_m	1232.9	581.9	Q_m	120399.4	4384.9	A_{RP}	8.1	7.8
n_{T0}	9.928	1.53	K_{BS}	0.015	0.02	K_s	0.017	0.04	K_{VS}	1E-07	1E-07	k_{rp}	7.3E-05	0.002	B_{RP}	2.1E-06	0.01
b_{T0}	1.51E+15	396.1	α	1.150	1.1	m_s	1.181	1.39	β_{VS}	0.007	0.015	m_{rp}	84.780	5.735	g	3.105	1.35

Table 4.4: Statistical parameters for adsorption isotherm model fitting

Isotherms	Langmuir		Freundlich		Jovanovic		Toth		Brouers-Sotolongo		Sips		Vieth-Sladek		Radke-Prausnitz		Redlich-Peterson	
	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt
SSE	325.4	547.7	441.4	991.6	317.2	532.1	202.8	506.9	264.4	490.6	284.1	426.2	325.4	547.7	312.8	531.6	225.2	514.6
χ^2	4.50	11.48	4.87	22.86	4.46	10.57	3.80	9.10	5.45	7.46	5.52	5.40	4.50	11.48	4.44	10.29	3.93	9.39
R^2	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99

4.5 Adsorption Kinetics

Kinetic models provide an insight on the kinetic performance of adsorption of DR13 dye on Bent and Mt respectively. This is of great significance to scale for commercial applications. To provide the variation in adsorption rate, a concentration of $300 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of DR13 dye was used to carry out kinetic studies at 303, 313 and 323 K. The results are presented in Table 4.5 and Figures 4.14a and 4.14b. The kinetic data of adsorption of DR13 on minerals was analysed using pseudo-first-order Eq. 16 - Table 2.1 [38] and pseudo-second-order Eq. 17 - Table 2.1 [39]. The R^2 and χ^2 values suggest the pseudo-second-order model is a better fit than pseudo-first-order for Bent and Mt respectively.

Analysis of adsorption kinetics data confirms multiple levels of linearity, which in turn suggests multiple mechanisms. When the concentrations and temperature are higher, the adsorption rate is high followed by a shift in the rate due to different linear routes and gets stabilized with respect to time. This was observed in film diffusion model Eq. 18 - Table 2.1 [40]. It can be seen from Figs. 4.15a and 4.15b that good adherence to the model with high R^2 values gives the liquid film diffusion constant R' (Table 4.6). The values of R' infers that in the beginning the adsorption of solute is quick onto the surface of the particles to form a film which later on slows down further diffusion bringing some change in absorption rates. This confirms that diffusion is a rate limiting process.

Figure 4.14a: Kinetic model fits for $300 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ initial concentration of DR13 dye on Bent at different temperatures

Figure 4.14b: Kinetic model fits for $300 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ initial concentration of DR13 dye on Mt at different temperatures

Figure 4.15a: Kinetics data fitted to the Film diffusion model with initial DR13 dye concentration $300 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ Bent

Figure 4.15b: Kinetics data fitted to the Film diffusion model with initial DR13 dye concentration $300 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ Mt

Table 4.5: Experimentally determined and theoretically predicted parameters for adsorption kinetics models

Initial dye concentration [$\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$]	Temp [K]	$Q_{e_{\text{expt}}}$ [mg g^{-1}]		Pseudo-first order								Pseudo-second order							
				$Q_{e_{\text{pred}}}$ [mg g^{-1}]		k_1		R^2		χ^2		$Q_{e_{\text{pred}}}$ [mg g^{-1}]		k_2		R^2		χ^2	
		Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt
300	303	258	241	26.4	25.4	4.9E-02	3.9E-02	0.83	0.83	1.57	1.57	31.24	30.24	2.6E-03	1.5E-03	0.90	0.90	0.76	0.76
	313	220	203	27.2	26.2	5.2E-02	4.2E-02	0.81	0.81	1.61	1.61	31.92	30.92	2.7E-03	1.6E-03	0.90	0.90	0.76	0.76
	323	205	192	28.8	27.8	5.1E-02	4.1E-02	0.79	0.79	1.98	1.98	33.82	32.82	2.6E-03	1.6E-03	0.87	0.87	1.00	1.00

Table 4.6: Calculated parameters for diffusion models

Initial dye concentration [$\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$]	Temp [K]	Film diffusion model				Weber-Morris model				Dumwald-Wagner			
		R' [min^{-1}]		R^2		k_{ist} [$\text{mg g}^{-1} \text{s}^{-0.5}$]		R^2		K [min^{-1}]		R^2	
		Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt
300	303	0.009	0.022	0.97	0.97	7.59	12.06	0.93	0.96	0.008	0.018	0.97	0.98
	313	0.013	0.014	0.98	0.99	5.69	8.78	0.96	0.99	0.011	0.011	0.97	0.99
	323	0.011	0.018	0.98	0.98	4.34	17.79	0.95	0.97	0.010	0.015	0.98	0.97

4.6 Mechanistic Study

To describe adsorption data, mathematical models are proposed which are classified as adsorption reaction models and adsorption diffusion models. To identify the importance of diffusion in the adsorption process of the DR13 dye onto clay minerals, authors have resorted to functional empirical relationship of the uptake of the substrate at a given time q_t varying almost proportionally with $t^{1/2}$. This is done by fitting an intraparticle diffusion model Eq. 19 - Table 2.1. These results clearly show that the process of adsorption is not rate-limiting. The data also indicated that progression of adsorption is taking place in multiple steps. Initially the DR13 dye molecules move from bulk solution towards the Bent or Mt surface and then the solute molecules diffuse to the pores of clay minerals.

According to the Weber-Morris model [25] the solute uptake varies with $t^{1/2}$ as shown in Eq. 20 - Table 2.1. Hence q_t versus $t^{1/2}$ plot should provide a straight line and it should pass through the origin whose slope (k_{int}) will be the diffusion rate constant (Figures 4.16a and 4.16b). This infers that the intraparticle diffusion is the sole rate-limiting step. Conversely, the Dumwald-Wagner model [41] calculates the true absorption rate (Eq. 21 - Table 2.1). The data with corrections for observed diffusion effects are presented in Table 4.6 and Figures 4.17a and 4.17b.

Figure 4.16: Kinetics data fitted to the Weber-Morris model with initial DR13 dye concentration $300 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ (a) Bent and (b) Mt

Figure 4.17: Kinetics data fitted to the Dumwald-Wagner model with initial DR13 dye concentration of $300 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ (a) Bent and (b) Mt

4.7 Thermodynamics of the Adsorption Process

Gibbs free energy change (ΔG°) and entropy of the dye-clay mineral system (ΔS°) are the main features of the process design of adsorption thermodynamics. The relationship of ΔH° , ΔS° and E_a are presented in Eqs. - 22, 23 and 24 - Table 2.1. These parameters can be calculated from the slope and the intercept of the Van't Hoff plots of $\ln(K_d)$ and $\ln(K_2)$ versus $1/T$ as shown in Figs. 4.18 and 4.19. The thermodynamic parameter estimates are provided in Table 4.7. The values of ΔG° decide the extent of spontaneity of adsorption process. The decrease in the negative values of ΔG° with increase in the temperature infers that the reaction is almost spontaneous at lower temperature. The positive values of ΔS° indicate the randomness of dye/clay interface.

Table 4.7: Thermodynamic parameters of DR13-Bent and DR13-Mt systems

Initial Dye Concentration [$\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$]	Temperature [K]	ΔG° [kJ mol ⁻¹]		ΔS° [J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]		ΔH° [kJ mol ⁻¹]		ln A [-]		E_a [kJ mol ⁻¹]	
		Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt
300	303	-2.84	-4.93								
	313	-2.44	-4.74	94.48	68.69	33.40	24.76	6.71	4.54	6.93	4.84
	323	-2.09	-4.4								

Figure 4.18: Plot of thermodynamic equilibrium constant versus $1/T$ to determine enthalpy and Gibbs free energy of (a) DR13-Bent and (b) DR13-Mt

Figure 4.19: The pseudo-second order kinetics for adsorption of DR13 dye on (a) Bent and (b) Mt

4.8 Statistical Process Optimization

The process optimization is achieved by using Fractional Factorial Experimental Design (FFED) [42] under different combinations of five independent variables. Analysis of variance (Table 4.8) obtained from the quadratic regression analysis manifests the significance of individual and combined effect of the factors for DR13-Bent and DR13-Mt systems respectively. Confidence interval of 95% with p -value $< 0.05\%$ was considered significant. The graphs in Figure 4.20 suggest a strong relationship between the experimental and predicted responses. (A, C, D, E, AC, A², C² and D²) and (A, B, C, D, E, A², C², D² and E²) are significant model terms for DR13-Bent and DR13-Mt systems respectively. The regression equations obtained for DR13-Bent and DR13-Mt systems are shown below:

$$\text{DR13-Bent} = -42.7 + 40.4*A - 15.4*B + 197.5*C - 140.3*D - 67.1*E - 16.3*AB - 9.6*A^2 - 2.6*B^2 - 16.1*C^2 + 150.4*D^2 - 71.0*E^2$$

$$\text{DR13-Mt} = -12.3 + 58.9*A - 27.7*B + 157.1*C - 129.3*D - 42.6*E - 7.3*AB - 50.0*A^2 + 5.2*B^2 - 61.3*C^2 + 127.9*D^2 - 52.5*E^2$$

The multiple regression analysis based on FFED was obtained using the optimum values of variables studied using second-order polynomial equations. The graphs in Figure 4.20 suggest a close interrelationship between the experimental data and expected responses and shows better results for the DR13-Bent system compared to the DR13-Mt system. Figure 4.20 suggests a close interrelationship between the experimental data and expected responses. While developing the regression equation, A, B, C, D, E, AB, D² and E² (DR13-Bent) and A, B, C, D, E, A², C², D² and E² (DR13-Mt) were found to be significant model terms and rest of the variables were considered insignificant. In both the systems cross products AD, AE, BD, BE, BF, CD, CE, CF and DE were found to be zero and therefore were excluded to construct the regression equations. At the confidence interval of 95% and p -value $< 0.05\%$ the two systems, namely, DR13-Bent and DR13-Mt displayed F -values of 117.7 and 54.7; R^2 values of 95.9% and 91.7% and coefficient of variance (CV) of 8.7% and 13.9% respectively. The prospects of the values of R^2 and CV help to navigate into systematic analysis and snipping of unwanted design points based on parameters of interest to indicate the effect of the variable(s) on the adsorption capacity.

Analysis of 3D response surface plots and 2D contour plots showed maximum adsorption obtained by the statistical optimization experiments with adsorbent dosage 0.06 g L^{-1} , particle size $175 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$, orbital shaking 165 rpm at 20°C for DR13-Bent and DR13-Mt systems were 801 mg g^{-1} and 436 mg g^{-1} at pH 5.18 and 5.60; initial dye concentration 950 mg L^{-1} and 560 mg L^{-1} ; adsorption time 237 min and 162 min respectively. The contour and surface plots illustrate the combined effect of two factors on the process of adsorption and the results are graphically presented in Figure 4.21 and Figure 4.22. In brief, the importance of statistical optimization of the process variables leads us to interesting results which help to commercialize the process.

Table 5.8: ANOVA Table of DR13-Bent and DR13-Mt systems

Source	Sum of Squares		Degree of freedom		Mean Square		F Value		P- Value	
Model	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt
		305238.3	280468.2	11	11	27748.9	25497.1	117.7	54.7	< 0.001**
A	21983.8	46885.6	1	1	21983.8	46885.6	93.2	100.7	< 0.001**	< 0.001**
B	4419.1	14217.1	1	1	4419.1	14217.1	18.7	30.5	< 0.001**	< 0.001**
C	172242.9	109070.5	1	1	172242.9	109070.5	730.3	234.1	< 0.001**	< 0.001**
D	78434.9	66540.2	1	1	78434.9	66540.2	332.6	142.8	< 0.001**	< 0.001**
E	12596.0	5074.5	1	1	12596.0	5074.5	53.4	10.9	< 0.001**	0.0017**
AB	2632.9	520.7	1	1	2632.9	520.7	11.2	1.1	0.0015**	0.2950
A ²	361.5	9908.4	1	1	361.5	9908.4	1.5	21.3	0.2209	< 0.001**
B ²	39.8	160.2	1	1	39.8	160.2	0.2	0.3	0.6828	0.5600
C ²	484.0	7044.8	1	1	484.0	7044.8	2.1	15.1	0.1576	< 0.001**
D ²	25528.0	18439.0	1	1	25528.0	18439.0	108.2	39.6	< 0.001**	< 0.001**
E ²	8763.8	4796.8	1	1	8763.8	4796.8	37.2	10.3	< 0.001**	0.0022**
Residual	12971.7	25620.0	55	55	235.8	465.8				
Lack of Fit	12801.1	25331.4	53	53	241.5	478.0	2.8	3.3	0.2960	0.2594
Total	318210.0	306088.3	66	66						

a)

b)

Figure 4.20: Actual versus predicted values of (a) DR13-Bent and (b) DR13-Mt systems

Figure 4.21: 3D-surface plot and contour plot showing the variation of adsorption capacity with DR13-Bent (a) time versus concentration, (b) temperature versus concentration and (c) concentration versus pH

Figure 4.22: 3D-surface plot and contour plot showing the variation of adsorption capacity with DR13-Mt (a) time versus concentration, (b) temperature versus concentration and (c) concentration versus pH

4.9 Adsorption Process for Textile Industrial Effluents

The details about the composition of the TIE, sample collection, measurement of absorbance are described elsewhere [43]. Two separate 0.1% (w/v) DR13 dye solutions were prepared by dissolving 5 g each of the dye in 5-litre distilled water (Solution 1) and in 5-litre TIE (Solution 2). Preliminary investigations revealed that addition of fresh samples of the adsorbent in Solution 1 and 2 after every 15 min enhanced the efficiency of removal of the dye aqueous matrices. The results are in conformance with our observations of adsorption kinetics where the solute adsorbs rapidly onto the surface of the clay particles forming a film. The process of adsorption gets delayed due to diffusion bringing changes in the adsorption rates. To augment the scale of operation, the experiments were performed using 1, 2 and 5 L of Solution 1 taken in polyethylene beakers containing 0.5, 1.0, and 5.0 g of Bent respectively. The polyethylene beakers were placed on three different magnetic stirrers and the solutions were agitated as per the procedure described above. The experiments were repeated with Solution 2 and Bent. The dye adsorbed Bent was separated by filtration and washed with distilled water until the filtrate was colorless. The powder was air-dried and sieved through 177 μ mesh. The resultant powder is referred to as dye-modified Bent (dmBent) powder. Similar experiments were carried out using Mt for Solution 1 and Solution 2. Mean of the results of the three experiments did not exceed $\pm 2\%$ error. The percent recovery of 99% and 87% Bent and Mt respectively was observed from Solution 2 after 30 min. The photographs of the solutions are shown in Figure 4.23.

Figure 4.23: Color of the solutions before and after adsorption: 1. Distilled water; 2. DR13 dye in distilled water; 3. TIE; 4. DR13 dye in TIE; 5. Colour of the filtrate after 30 min adsorption (a) Bent and (b) Mt

4.10 Studies on Composites

High Density Polyethylene/dye unmodified bentonite (HDPE/dmBent) composites were prepared by melt compounding of master batches that were premixed by dry-blending in a tumble mixer and by extrusion of HDPE resin with different proportions of dmBent. HDPE granules and/or recycled product and dmBent master batch flakes were compounded using twin screw extruder. The specimens were prepared by cutting the extrudates strands into pellets and were tested for physico-mechanical and chemical properties. The procedure was repeated with dye unmodified montmorillonite K10 (dmMt). The results were encouraging.

4.11 Conclusion

The adsorption capacity of Bent and Mt obtained from the quadratic model developed for process optimization gave values of 801 mg g^{-1} and 436 mg g^{-1} and follows Toth's isotherm. The kinetic, mechanistic and thermodynamic studies confirm that the process is physisorption and follows second-order kinetics with a multi-step diffusion route. A broad range of pH 4 to 10 for the remediation of DR13 dye on Bent and Mt is encouraging. The high removal efficiency among studied clay minerals, followed the order Bent > Mt >>> K. The dye-adsorbed Bent and Mt minerals obtained as "sludge" can be used as filler/reinforcing materials for the fabrication of composites using plastic waste. The detailed study on the composites is in progress in our laboratory. In brief, two major conclusions are drawn from our study. First, the experimental design of the present study align with one of the facets of circular economy which encourages the waste and/or byproduct of one process as resource material for the other and second, the research on the unmodified adsorbent needs to be encouraged which fits in to low-budget operational cost of the treatment of the industrial effluents.

4.12 References

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Chapter 5

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF LOW-COST SUSTAINABLE BENT, MT AND K UNMODIFIED CLAY MINERALS FOR THE REMEDIATION OF THE TOXIC DYE BG FROM TEXTILE INDUSTRIAL EFFLUENT

The potential use of low-cost, abundantly available, eco-friendly and unmodified bentonite (Bent), montmorillonite K10 (Mt) and Kaolinite (K) as adsorbents for the remediation of Direct red 13 (BG), a bisazo dye, from textile industrial effluent (TIE) is reported. The parameters affecting the adsorption capacity, kinetics and equilibrium were evaluated. Toth isotherm model was found to be best fit for the dye uptake process. The predominant kinetic mechanism fits best to pseudo-second-order reaction. Film diffusion studies indicated that the external mass transfer phenomena were more likely to be dominant over the diffusion process. The low ΔH° values indicate that the process of adsorption is physical in nature. Weak interactions like Van der Waal forces and hydrogen bonds play major roles as supported by FT-IR analysis. Statistical model was developed for optimization of adsorption processes. Prospects on the use of dye-adsorbed clay mineral for the fabrication of composites are reported.

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter a detailed study has been carried out on Bentonite (BNT), Montmorillonite nanoclay (MNC) and Kaolinite (K) for the selective adsorption of Brilliant Green (BG) dye from aqueous media.

5.2 Materials and Methods

5.2.1 Materials

Bentonite (colloidal native hydrated aluminum silicate) (BNT), Montmorillonite (MNT) and Kaolinite (K) (bole white powder – aluminum silicate hydrated) (K) were procured from SD Fine-chem Limited, India. Montmorillonite K10 (MT) and Direct Red 13 dye were obtained from Aldrich, India. The mineral samples were heated at 373 K for 8 h, cooled and kept in a desiccator before use. Brilliant Green (BG) dye is commonly referred to as Emerald Green. [C.I. = 42040; CAS registry number = 633-03-4; chemical formula = $C_{27}H_{33}N_2HO_4S$; molecular weight = 482.64. λ_{max} at 625 nm. The molecular structure of the BG dye is shown in Figure 5.1.

Figure 5.1: Structure of Brilliant Green dye

5.2.2 Studies on the variables affecting adsorption of BG dye on clay minerals

Batch experiment approach was adopted to study the influence of pH, initial dye concentration, adsorbent dosage and temperature as experimental parameters on the adsorption process. For preparing stock solution of BG (1000 mg L^{-1}) double distilled water was used. Solution concentrations in the range $25\text{--}500 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ were made by diluting the

stock solution. To a series of 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks, 50 mL of 300 mg L⁻¹ BG dye solution and 0.050 g of Bent were added. Evaluations were then conducted based on the effects of varying parameters such as, pH, BG dye initial concentration, dosage of adsorbent and temperature. Solution was subjected to stirring in a thermostatic orbital shaker 165 rpm for 180 min. Samples were withdrawn at predetermined equilibrium time. The unadsorbed BG dye solution was separated from Bent mineral by centrifugation with 3000 rpm for five minutes. If the solution was unclear the centrifugation was repeated for an additional five min. The concentration of the BG dye at equilibrium pertaining to the supernatant centrifuged solution was determined using a UV-visible spectrophotometer. To study the effect of initial solution pH, adsorption studies were carried out in pH range 2-12. The initial solution pH was controlled by adding either dilute HCl or NaOH (0.01-1.00 M). Three temperatures, 303, 313 and 323 K were selected, and experiments carried out as a function of 60 min equilibrium time to study adsorption kinetics of BG dye solution (300 mg L⁻¹). Experiments were replicated thrice, and the mean values are considered. The experiments were repeated with MNT and KALO clay minerals.

5.2.3 Characterization methods

IR spectra were recorded using the FTIR spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer 3 lambda). Scanning electron microscope (JEOL model 3300) was used to record SEM images. A pH meter Model 802 - Systronics, India was used to measure pH. Point-of- zero charge (pH_{PZC}) of Bent, Mt and K was determined by carrying out the procedure described by us elsewhere [1].

5.2.4 Statistical optimization of process parameters

The five independent variables affecting adsorption of BG dye on clay minerals using batch experiments namely, time of contact of dye and adsorbent (A), temperature of the system (B), initial dye concentration (C), adsorbent dosage (D) and pH (E) (Table 5.1) of the solution using two-level Fractional Factorial Experimental Design (FEED) to statistically optimize the adsorption capacity of Bent and Mt. The data was fitted to a second-order polynomial model for calculating the optimum conditions to obtain a quadratic regression equation. The empirical second-order polynomial model is as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_i X_i + \sum \beta_{ii} X_i^2 + \sum \beta_{ij} X_i X_j$$

Where Y represents the dependent response variable, β_0 is a regression coefficient, β_i is the linear effect, β_{ii} is the squared effect and β_{ij} is the interaction effect of independent variable X. Statistical software was used to study Response Surface Methodology (RSM) and to draw 3-D graphs and 2-D contour plots to evaluate the effect of independent variables on the response (dependent variable). Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used as a tool for the analyses of data obtained from polynomial models using 95% confidence level and a value of coefficient of determination $R^2 \geq 0.90$.

Table 5.1: Experimental design for individual factors for RSM studies

Factor	Name	Units	Minimum	Maximum
A	Time	minutes	0	180
B	Temperature	°C	27	50
C	Concentration	mg L ⁻¹	25	500
D	Adsorbent dosage	g L ⁻¹	0.5	6.0
E	pH	-	2	12

5.3 Results and Discussion

5.3.1 Surface characterization of the clay minerals

5.3.1.1 SEM and FTIR spectroscopy analyses

SEM images of Bent, Mt and K dye adsorbed minerals display a thin film over the particles of the clay minerals. The images are shown in Figures 5.2a, 5.2b, 5.3a, 5.3b, 5.4a and 5.4b, The FTIR of BG (Figure 5.5a) displayed a vibration band at around 3650 cm⁻¹ which is referred to as moisture adsorb onto the surface of the dye. Bent clay mineral with Al-centered octahedral displayed stretching vibration of the inner surface -OH groups at 3660 cm⁻¹ which forms hydrogen bonds with the oxygen of the Si-O double layer which shows a stretching band at 1010 cm⁻¹. Figure 5.5a shows the change in the shape with change in the intensity of the peaks at 3650, 1640, 1566, 1500, 1185 and 1010 cm⁻¹ which are referred to -OH, N=N, C=C, -C-N- and Si-O respectively in Bent and BG structure. It can be explained

that the mutual effects and interactions between the components denote adsorption of BG dye on Bent.

Figure 5.5b presents FTIR spectra of Mt. The spectra consists of a broadband at 3353-3454 cm^{-1} is attributed to $-\text{OH}$ groups and adsorbed water molecules, while C-O and C-H stretching frequencies are seen as sharp bands at 1598 and 2852 cm^{-1} . The C-O-C stretching bands appeared at 1091,1158,1355,1404 and 1418 cm^{-1} respectively. Observation of the spectra recorded after the adsorption of BG dye on Mt mineral revealed the disappearance of broad bands at 3300-3500 cm^{-1} and 3353-3454 cm^{-1} . This observation confirms the formation of hydrogen bonds between $-\text{NH}_2$ and hydroxyl groups. Strong adsorption of BG dye on Mt clay mineral is endorsed to the disappearance of N-N stretching frequency at 1598 cm^{-1} .

FTIR spectra for BG dye (Figure 5.45c) exhibits the distinctive peaks at 3450 refer to $-\text{OH}$ and 3100 cm^{-1} refer to $-\text{CH}$ aromatic stretching vibrations. The peaks at 2970 and 2879 cm^{-1} are caused by asymmetrical and symmetrical stretching vibrations of C-H groups. The multi peaks which appear at 1493-1330 cm^{-1} are ascribed to bending vibrations of N-H and CH groups respectively. The peaks exist in spectrum between 1611, 1584 and 1412 cm^{-1} are due to C=C in aromatic ring which coupling with N=N of azo group in dyes structure. The strong multi peaks which can be noticed between 1222, 1185, 1049 cm^{-1} are attributing to stretching vibrations of single bonds C-N, C-S, S-O in structure. FTIR spectra represents for pristine Kaolinite, BG dye and BG dye adsorbed on Kaolinite. In pristine Kaolinite, the absence of peaks between 3200-3500 cm^{-1} was noticed, whilst a tiny peak appears at around 3650 cm^{-1} may be attributed to the small traces of adsorbed water. The typical peaks at 2852 and 2830 cm^{-1} are due to the symmetric and asymmetric C-H stretching vibrations, respectively whereas the band at 1598 cm^{-1} is due to C=O stretching vibration of residual organic reagents. The vibration band at 1000-1080 cm^{-1} may refer to vibrations of single bonds of Si-O, Al-O and C-O molecules. The (Figure 9.3) shows the change in the shape with change in the intensity of the peaks at 3476, 1611, 1468, 1368 and 1175 cm^{-1} which referred to $-\text{OH}$, N=N, C=C, $-\text{C-N-}$ and C-S respectively in Kaolinite (KALO) and BG structure.

Figure 5.2a: SEM image of BENTONITE

Figure 5.3a: SEM image of MNC

Figure 5.4a: SEM image of KAOLINITE (K)

Figure 5.2b: SEM image of BG dye adsorbed

Figure 5.3b: SEM image of BG dye adsorbed
MNC

Figure 5.4b: SEM image of BG dye adsorbed
KAOLINITE (K)

Figure 5.5a: FTIR spectra of BG dye, Bent and BG-Bent

Figure 5.5b: FTIR spectra of BG dye, Mt and BG-Mt

Figure 5.5c: FTIR spectra of BG dye, Mt and BG-KALO

5.3.1.2 The role of point of zero charge (pH_{PZC})

BG is a disodium ionic dye, when placed in a solvent of high dielectric constant, such as water, dissociates to give anionic and cationic species. The three minerals under study, namely, Bent, Mt and K exhibit ionic character when placed in water. The ionic affinity of three minerals is pH dependent. As the pH of the solution in contact with the mineral is reduced below the pH_{PZC} , the surface of the mineral becomes positively charged. Conversely, as the pH is increased above pH_{PZC} , the surface becomes negatively charged. The protonation and deprotonation of the surface hydroxyl groups of the minerals is shown in Figures 5.6a, 5.6b and 5.6c.

Figure 5.6: Point of zero charge of (a) Bent (b) Mt and (c) K

pH_{PZC} studied for the three minerals, Bent, Mt and K are 8.18, 7.56 and 8.22 respectively. The plateau obtained for Bent and Mt between pH 4 and pH 10 infers that generic properties of surface charge, replicate certain macroscopic conditions imposed by electro neutrality and thermodynamic stability [2, 3]. This observation offers a great

advantage for the use of Bent and Mt as adsorbents in remediation of BG in a wide range of pH 4 to 10 for textile industrial effluent. Conversely, K did not display encouraging results.

5.3.2 The influence of variables on BG adsorption on clay minerals

5.3.2.1 Effect of solution pH

The adsorption capacity of the clay mineral depends on solution pH. The pH plays two important roles; first, it influences the characteristics of adsorbent surface and second, the chemistry of the dye solution [4]. Contrary to the common observation the adsorption capacity of Bent and Mt was found to be almost independent of pH between the ranges 4 to 10. Similar observation was observed for K but at low adsorption capacity (Figures 5.7a, 5.7b and 5.7c). The latter observation is similar to our studies on Kaolinite (K) [5]. Bent and Mt have almost similar structures. They present octahedral alumina between two tetrahedral silica layers and are highly colloidal and have the ability to absorb large quantities of water due to weak electrostatic forces. On the contrary, K is reported to be the least reactive clay [6].

Figure 5.7: Effect of pH on adsorption of BG on (a) Bent (b) Mt and (c) K

5.3.2.2 Effect of initial dye concentration

The methods available for colour measurement are colorimetry and spectrophotometry. The main disadvantage of colorimetric method is time consuming. Conversely, spectrophotometric method by knowing molar absorption coefficient (ϵ) of dye solution will help in the calculations of the absorbance of the dye at a given wavelength. The procedure for the calculation of ϵ is described elsewhere [7]. The adsorbed amount of BG dye at equilibrium q_e (mg g^{-1}) at a given time q_t (mg g^{-1}) and percentage removal efficiency (RE %) of the dye from aqueous solutions was determined using the Eqs. 1, 2 and 3 - Table 2.1. Mean values of three trials of the adsorption experiments were used in data analysis. Control experiments were performed with the addition of Bent, Mt or K.

Figure 5.8: Effect of initial dye concentration on adsorption of BG dye with % removal efficiency of (a) Bent (b) Mt and (c) K

The effect of initial BG dye concentration has profound influence on the adsorption capacity of clay minerals. The per cent adsorption capacity of Bent remains almost constant around 80% in the range 25-500 mg L^{-1} ; while, Mt displayed a plateau between 25–300 $\text{mg$

L^{-1} and gradually decreased to 60% in the range 300-500 $mg L^{-1}$. The novel behaviour exhibited by Bent and Mt in range 50-500 $mg L^{-1}$ and 50-300 $mg L^{-1}$ respectively is in contradiction to the earlier observation that increase in initial dye concentration leads to a decrease in the percentage of dye removal from the bulk solution. However, Mt behaves to the trend between 300-500 $mg L^{-1}$. The behaviour of Bent and Mt gives scope to scale to commercial applications as the industrial effluents have undefined composition, while, K does not show any encouraging results (Figs. 5.8a, 5.8b and 5.8c).

5.3.2.3 Effect of adsorbent dosage

The dosage as a parameter will have profound influence on the commercialization of the process because it decides the economic feasibility. Increase in adsorbent dose enhances the removal of dye from the solution. However, no significant changes were observed beyond 6.000 $g L^{-1}$. The results are depicted in Figs. 5.9a, 5.9b and 5.9c. K did not give encouraging results.

Figure 5.9: Effect of dosage on adsorption of BG (a) Bent (b) Mt and (c) K

5.3.2.4 Effect of temperature

Keeping in view, our focus to scale to commercial applications [8], evaluation of the process of adsorption of dyes onto the clays as function of solution temperature was studied using the Eqs. 4 and 5 - Table 2.1. The influence of temperature on BG dye adsorption onto the mineral clays is presented in Figures 5.10a, 5.10b and 5.10c. ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° are the important thermodynamic parameters used to describe thermodynamic behaviour of the process of adsorption.

Figure 5.10: Effect of temperature on adsorption of BG (a) Bent (b) Mt and (c) K

The negative enthalpy (ΔH°) values obtained by increasing the temperature of adsorption process from 303 to 323 K of all clay minerals indicate exothermic process. The overall negative values of free energy (ΔG°) obtained for three systems namely, BG-Bent, BG-Mt and BG-K confirm the feasibility and the spontaneous nature of the adsorption process in the order Bent>Mt>>K. The magnitude of ΔG° values is indicative of rapid and spontaneous adsorption at lower temperature. Further, it is inferred that the negative values of entropy (ΔS°) suggests minimum changes in the internal structure of the clay minerals.

Similar observation has been reported elsewhere [9]. Preliminary investigations on K did not give encouraging results to commensurate with needs and demands of commercialization of the process. Thus, further studies on K were not pursued.

5.4 Adsorption Isotherms - Modeling Analysis

Adsorption as process comprises of mass transfer phenomena of the species from the liquid phase (dye solution) onto the adsorbent (clay minerals) in three steps; first, the transfer of dye from solution onto external surface of the solid adsorbent, also known as external film diffusion; second, percolating into the solid pores by liquid phase diffusion and surface diffusion, commonly known as intraparticle diffusion. This step is slower than the other steps which influence the kinetics of the process. The latter step has two segments, first, adsorption kinetics described by mass transfer processes and second, adsorption equilibrium between the concentration of the bulk dye solution and adsorbent surface concentrations which are reached almost instantaneously inside the pores. These segments help in constructing an adsorption isotherm [10, 11]. Adsorption isotherm models record the distribution of BG dye between the bulk solution and adsorbent at various equilibrium concentrations. Also, the study of the remediation of the dye was planned to provide a prospect of the adsorption process under study to indicate the efficiency of the clay minerals for economic feasibility to scale for commercial applications. The data of adsorption of BG dye onto Bent and Mt were analyzed with the help of Langmuir, Freundlich, Jovanovic, Toth, Brouers-Sotolongo, Sips, Vieth-Sladek, Radke-Prausnitz and Redlich-Peterson isotherm models.

The main criterion to study different isotherm models is to select the best fit which has monolayer adsorption capacity Q_m value as closer to experimental equilibrium q_e value with coefficient of determination (R^2) ≥ 0.90 . In our study we found that R^2 for almost all the models studied displayed a value of 0.93 and above. Thus, sum square error (SSE) and chi-square test (χ^2) as two additional error functions were also calculated to arrive at the best fit.

Langmuir established an isotherm model on the basis of two important assumptions [12]. The surface of the adsorbent has a finite number of almost identical adsorption sites having uniform energies and no lateral interaction takes place between adsorbed molecules. A two-dimensional graphical representation of equilibrium concentration (C_e) as independent variable and adsorption capacity of the adsorbent (q_e) as dependent variable are shown in Figures 5.11a, 5.11b and 5.11c. The part of the curve which resembles a plateau characterizes

the saturation point where no further adsorption can follow. In other words, no further adsorption of the dye can take place on the already occupied site by the dye molecule which envisages that only a monolayer adsorption can take place.

Figure 5.11: Fitting of BG dye adsorption data to Langmuir, Freundlich, Jovanovic and Dubinin-Radushkevich adsorption isotherm (a) Bent (b) Mt and (c) K

Mathematical expressions of the Langmuir isotherm model are shown in Eqs. 6 and 7 - Table 2.1. The Q_m values 254.52, 582.0 and 143.69 mg g^{-1} obtained are high compared to the experimental q_e values 298.00, 170.00 and 85.00 mg g^{-1} for Bent Mt and K respectively. The experimental data and values of coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.71, 0.99 and 0.93 for Bent Mt and K respectively shows a good fit to the Langmuir isotherm model. The R_L values calculated for Bent Mt and K were between 0.677 to 0.116; 0.016 to 0.163; .048 to 0.289 respectively. These values indicate favourable adsorption of BG dye onto the clay minerals. The decrease in R_L value with increase in initial concentration indicates that the adsorption is more favourable at high concentration. The large difference between Q_m

(254.52, 582.0 and 143.69 mg g⁻¹) and q_e (298.00, 170.00 and 85.00 mg g⁻¹) for Bent Mt and K respectively has made the authors explore other adsorption isotherm models.

Freundlich isotherm model validates that the surface of the adsorbent is always heterogeneous. It further assumes that the process takes place at adsorption sites with different energy of adsorption [13]. The mathematical model proposed by Freundlich is also applicable to multilayer adsorption and is expressed in the Eq. 8 – Table 2.1. The values of n_F and $1/n_F$ 1.71 and 0.584 (Bent) and 1.34 and 0.746 (Mt) indicate that the adsorption is physisorption and favours normal Langmuir Isotherm. The values of K_F and n_F are presented in Table 5.2. The R^2 values of 0.99, 0.99 and 0.77 for Bent Mt and K respectively show that the process is linear.

The Jovanovic model introduces the exponential term K_J to minimize the deviations of the experimental results obtained from the Langmuir isotherm model [14]. The mathematical model is presented in Eq. 9 - Table 2.1. The Q_m value of 129.45 mg g⁻¹ (Bent), 358.7 mg g⁻¹ (Mt) and 122.34 mg g⁻¹ (K) obtained in Jovanovic isotherm is low compared to the experimental q_e values 298.00, 170.00 and 85.00 mg g⁻¹ respectively. Comparing the values obtained by Jovanovic model and Langmuir isotherm model, it was found that the former model has Q_m values nearer to the experimental q_e value. The data obtained using three two-parameter models are presented in Table 5.2. In pursuit to identify specific model(s) which has smaller gap between Q_m and q_e values; six three-parameter isotherm models, namely, Toth, Brouers-Sotolongo, Sips, Vieth-Sladek, Redlich-Peterson and Radke-Prausnitz, were also studied.

Table 5.2: Calculated parameters of two-parameter adsorption isotherms

Two Parameter Isotherms											
Langmuir				Freundlich				Jovanovic			
Constants	Bent	Mt	K	Constants	Bent	Mt	K	Constants	Bent	Mt	K
Q_m	254.52	582.0	143.69	K_F	43.61	13.56	33.15	Q_m	129.45	358.7	122.34
K_S	0.159	0.015	0.098	n_F	1.71	1.34	3.14	K_J	1.70	0.023	0.086

Table 5.3A: Calculated parameters of three-parameter adsorption isotherms

Three Parameter Isotherms											
Toth				Brouers-Sotolongo				Sips			
Constants	Bent	Mt	K	Constants	Bent	Mt	K	Constants	Bent	Mt	K
Q_m	229.0	384.0	120.84	Q_m	890.4	309.7	120.54	Q_m	233.20	441.7	134.10
n_{TO}	0.51	1.53	3.124	K_{BS}	0.06	0.02	0.058	K_s	0.01	0.04	1.486
b_{TO}	0.66	396.1	6672.33	α	0.50	1.1	1.169	m_s	0.200	1.39	9.102

Table 5.3B: Calculated parameters of three-parameter adsorption isotherms

Three Parameter Isotherms											
Vieth-Sladek				Radke- Prausnitz				Redlich-Peterson			
Constants	Bent	Mt	K	Constants	Bent	Mt	K	Constants	Bent	Mt	K
Q_m	116594.6	581.9	143.69	Q_m	84756.5	4384.9	733.25	A_{RP}	19025.5	7.8	8.11
K_{VS}	2385.9	1E-07	1.0E-07	k_{rp}	92.6	0.002	0.013	B_{RP}	38.5	0.01	0.006
β_{VS}	0.74	0.015	0.098	m_{rp}	2.1	5.735	2.651	g	2.1	1.35	1.522

Table 5.4A: Statistical parameters for adsorption isotherm model fitting

Isotherms	Langmuir			Freundlich			Jovanovic			Toth			Brouers-Sotolongo		
	Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K
SSE	1.2E+05	547.7	708.3	1.1E+05	991.6	2305.1	6.2E+04	532.1	270.7	84117.4	506.9	229.5	79.9	490.6	197.8
χ^2	1106.0	11.48	10.69	4.87	22.86	44.75	987.26	10.57	3.843	1296.05	9.10	3.290	0.815	7.46	2.545
R^2	0.71	0.99	0.93	0.99	0.99	0.77	0.72	0.99	0.97	0.73	0.99	0.98	0.98	0.99	0.98

Table 5.4B: Statistical parameters for adsorption isotherm model fitting

Isotherms	Vieth-Sladek			Radke-Prausnitz			Redlich-Peterson			Sips		
	Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K
SSE	253.0	547.7	708.3	14069.6	531.6	121.3	14068.8	506.9	110.6	77112.8	514.6	440.8
χ^2	0.1	11.48	10.690	234.8	10.29	1.966	234.05	9.10	1.825	1058.4	9.39	4.501
R^2	0.5	0.99	0.93	0.77	0.99	0.99	0.77	0.99	0.99	0.72	0.99	0.95

Figure 5.12: Fitting of BG dye adsorption data to Radke-Prausnitz and Sips adsorption isotherm (a) Bent (b) Mt and (c) K

To describe heterogeneous adsorption system an empirical mathematical Eq. 10 - Table 2.1 was developed by Toth [15]. Eq. 11 - Table 2.1 represents Brouers-Sotolongo model [16]. Sips isotherm is a combined form of Langmuir and Freundlich expressions deduced for predicting the heterogeneous adsorption systems (Figures 5.12a and 5.12b) and the mathematical equation for the Sips isotherm is shown in Eq. 12 - Table 2.1 [17]. The Eq. 13 - Table 2.1 represents the Vieth-Sladek isotherm model and the importance of Vieth-Sladek isotherm is described by us elsewhere [18, 19]. The nonlinear component indicates the adherence of solutes to sites on the surface of porous adsorbents (Figs. 5.13a and 5.13b). The mathematical Eq. 14 - Table 2.1 represents Radke-Prausnitz isotherm model [20]. Redlich-Peterson isotherm model as shown in Eq. 15 - Table 2.1 has a correction exponent 'g' [21]. The 'g' value of 2.1, 1.35 and 1.522 obtained for Bent, Mt and K respectively, indicates that the adsorption tends towards Langmuir isotherm (Figures 5.14a and 5.14b).

Figure 5.13: Fitting of BG adsorption data to Vieth-Sladek, Toth and Brouers-Sotolongo adsorption isotherm (a) Bent (b) Mt and (c) K

The data obtained using six three-parameter models are presented in Table 5.3. The study of nine isotherm models and evaluation of statistical parameters are presented in Table 5.4. The study suggests the Toth isotherm is the best fit for the adsorption process of the dye onto the clay minerals. The data presented in the Table 5.4 display coefficient of determination R^2 value surmises that the process of adsorption of BG dye onto Bent or Mt or K is linear. The study of SSE as an error function confirms that K is better than Mt and K, while the study of Chi-square test values favours K first and Mt but not Bent (Table 5.4).

5.5 Adsorption Kinetics

Kinetic models provide an insight on the kinetic performance of adsorption of BG dye on Bent and Mt respectively. This is of great significance to scale for commercial applications. To provide the variation in adsorption rate, a concentration of $300 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of BG dye was used to carry out kinetic studies at 303, 313 and 323 K. The results are presented

in Table 5.5 and Figures 5.15a and 5.15b. The kinetic data of adsorption of BG on minerals was analysed using pseudo-first-order Eq. 16 - Table 2.1 and pseudo-second-order Eq. 17 - Table 2.1 [22, 23]. The R^2 and χ^2 values suggest the pseudo-second-order model is a better fit than pseudo-first-order for Bent and Mt respectively.

Analysis of adsorption kinetics data confirms multiple levels of linearity, which in turn suggests multiple mechanisms. When the concentrations and temperature are higher, the adsorption rate is high followed by a shift in the rate due to different linear routes and gets stabilized with respect to time. This was observed in film diffusion model Eq. 18 - Table 2.1 [24]. It can be seen from Figures 5.16a, 5.16b and 5.16c that good adherence to the model with high R^2 values gives the liquid film diffusion constant R' (Table 5.6). The values of R' infers that in the beginning the adsorption of solute is quick onto the surface of the particles to form a film which later on slows down further diffusion bringing some change in absorption rates. This confirms that diffusion is a rate limiting process.

Figure 5.14: Kinetics data fitted to the Film diffusion model with initial BG dye concentration $300 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ (a) Bent (b) Mt and (c) K

Figure 5.15: Kinetic model fits for 300 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ initial concentration of BG dye on (a) Bent (b) Mt and (c) K at different temperatures

Table 5.5A: Experimentally determined and theoretically predicted parameters for adsorption kinetics models

Initial dye concentration [$\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$]	Temp [K]	$Q_{e\text{expt}} [\text{mg g}^{-1}]$			Pseudo-first order											
					$Q_{e\text{pred}} [\text{mg g}^{-1}]$			k_1			R^2			χ^2		
		Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K
300	303	258	241	488	26.4	25.4	25.42	4.9E-02	3.9E-02	3.89E-02	0.83	0.83	0.83	1.57	1.57	1.57
	313	220	203	494	27.2	26.2	26.21	5.2E-02	4.2E-02	4.16E-02	0.81	0.81	0.81	1.61	1.61	1.61
	323	205	192	497	28.8	27.8	27.77	5.1E-02	4.1E-02	4.07E-02	0.79	0.79	0.79	1.98	1.98	1.98

Table 5.5B: Experimentally determined and theoretically predicted parameters for adsorption kinetics models

Initial dye concentration [$\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$]	Temp [K]	$Q_{e\text{expt}} [\text{mg g}^{-1}]$			Pseudo-second order											
					$Q_{e\text{pred}} [\text{mg g}^{-1}]$			k_2			R^2			χ^2		
		Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K
300	303	258	241	488	31.24	30.24	30.24	2.6E-03	1.5E-03	1.6E-03	0.90	0.90	0.90	0.76	0.76	0.76
	313	220	203	494	31.92	30.92	30.92	2.7E-03	1.6E-03	1.7E-03	0.90	0.90	0.90	0.76	0.76	0.76
	323	205	192	497	33.82	32.82	32.82	2.6E-03	1.6E-03	1.5E-03	0.87	0.87	0.87	1.00	1.00	1.00

Table 5.6: Calculated parameters for diffusion models

Initial dye conc. [$\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$]	Temp [K]	Film diffusion model						Weber-Morris model						Dumwald-Wagner					
		$R' [\text{min}^{-1}]$			R^2			$k_{ist} [\text{mg g}^{-1} \text{s}^{-0.5}]$			R^2			$K [\text{min}^{-1}]$			R^2		
		Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K
300	303	0.01	0.02	0.0557	0.97	0.97	0.92	7.59	12.06	10.66	0.93	0.96	0.89	0.008	0.018	0.049	0.97	0.98	0.97
	313	0.01	0.01	0.0443	0.98	0.99	0.86	5.69	8.78	10.71	0.96	0.99	0.91	0.011	0.011	0.038	0.97	0.99	0.85
	323	0.01	0.02	0.0348	0.98	0.98	0.92	4.34	17.79	11.21	0.95	0.97	0.94	0.010	0.015	0.028	0.98	0.97	0.89

5.6 Mechanistic Study

To describe adsorption data, mathematical models are proposed which are classified as adsorption reaction models and adsorption diffusion models. To identify the importance of diffusion in the adsorption process of the BG dye onto clay minerals, authors have resorted to functional empirical relationship of the uptake of the substrate at a given time q_t varying almost proportionally with $t^{1/2}$. This is done by fitting an intraparticle diffusion model Eq. 19 - Table 2.1. These results clearly show that the process of adsorption is not rate-limiting. The data also indicated that progression of adsorption is taking place in multiple steps. Initially the BG dye molecules move from bulk solution towards the Bent or Mt surface and then the solute molecules diffuse to the pores of clay minerals.

Figure 5.16: Kinetics data fitted to the Weber-Morris model with initial BG dye concentration 300 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ (a) Bent (b) Mt and (c) K

According to the Weber-Morris model the solute uptake varies with $t^{1/2}$ as shown in Eq. 20 - Table 2.1 [9]. Hence q_t versus $t^{1/2}$ plot should provide a straight line and it should pass through the origin whose slope (k_{int}) will be the diffusion rate constant (Figs. 5.17a, 5.17b and 5.17c). This infers that the intraparticle diffusion is the sole rate-limiting step. Conversely, the Dumwald-Wagner model calculates the true absorption rate (Eq. 21 - Table 2.1) [25]. The data with corrections for observed diffusion effects are presented in Table 5.6 and Figs. 5.18a, 5.18b and 5.18c.

Figure 5.17: Kinetics data fitted to the Dumwald-Wagner model with initial BG dye concentration of $300 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ (a) Bent (b) Mt and (c) K

5.7 Thermodynamics of the Adsorption Process

Gibbs free energy change (ΔG°) and entropy of the dye-clay mineral system (ΔS°) are the main features of the process design of adsorption thermodynamics. The relationship of ΔH° , ΔS° and E_a are presented in Eqs. - 22, 23 and 24 - Table 2.1. These parameters can be

calculated from the slope and the intercept of the Van't Hoff plots of $\ln(K_d)$ and $\ln(K_2)$ versus $1/T$ as shown in Figures 5.19 and 5.20. The thermodynamic parameter estimates are provided in Table 5.7. The values of ΔG° decide the extent of spontaneity of adsorption process. The decrease in the negative values of ΔG° with increase in the temperature infers that the reaction is almost spontaneous at lower temperature. The positive values of ΔS° indicate the randomness of dye/clay interface.

Table 5.7: Thermodynamic parameters of DR13-Bent and DR13-Mt systems at initial dye concentration of $300 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$

Temp [K]	ΔG° [kJ mol ⁻¹]			ΔS° [J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]			ΔH° [kJ mol ⁻¹]			ln A [-]			E _a [kJ mol ⁻¹]		
	Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K	Bent	Mt	K
303	-2.8	-4.9	-9.4												
313	-2.4	-4.7	-11.5	94.5	68.7	217.03	33.4	24.8	56.4	6.7	4.5	-6.7	6.9	4.8	-5.9
323	-2.1	-4.4	-13.7												

Figure 5.18: Plot of thermodynamic equilibrium constant versus $1/T$ to determine enthalpy and Gibbs free energy of (a) Bent (b) Mt and (c) K

Figure 5.19: The pseudo-second order kinetics for adsorption of BG dye on (a) Bent (b) Mt and (c) K

5.8 Statistical Process Optimization

The process optimization is achieved by using Fractional Factorial Experimental Design (FFED) under different combinations of five independent variables [26]. Analysis of variance (Table 5.8) obtained from the quadratic regression analysis manifests the significance of individual and combined effect of the factors for BG-Bent and BG-Mt systems respectively. Confidence interval of 95% with p -value $< 0.05\%$ was considered significant. The graphs in Figure 5.21 suggest a strong relationship between the experimental and predicted responses. (A, C, D, E, AC, A², C² and D²) and (A, B, C, D, E, A², C², D² and E²) are significant model terms for BG-Bent and BG-Mt systems respectively. The regression equations obtained for BG-Bent and BG-Mt systems are shown below:

$$\text{BG-Bent} = -42.7 + 40.4 * A - 15.4 * B + 197.5 * C - 140.3 * D - 67.1 * E - 16.3 * AB - 9.6 * A^2 - 2.6 * B^2 - 16.1 * C^2 + 150.4 * D^2 - 71.0 * E^2$$

$$\text{BG-Mt} = -12.3 + 58.9 * A - 27.7 * B + 157.1 * C - 129.3 * D - 42.6 * E - 7.3 * AB - 50.0 * A^2 + 5.2 * B^2 - 61.3 * C^2 + 127.9 * D^2 - 52.5 * E^2$$

Table 5.8: ANOVA Table of DR13-Bent and DR13-Mt systems

Source	Sum of Squares		Degree of freedom		Mean Square		F Value		P- Value	
	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt	Bent	Mt
Model	305238.3	280468.2	11	11	27748.9	25497.1	117.7	54.7	< 0.001**	< 0.001**
A	21983.8	46885.6	1	1	21983.8	46885.6	93.2	100.7	< 0.001**	< 0.001**
B	4419.1	14217.1	1	1	4419.1	14217.1	18.7	30.5	< 0.001**	< 0.001**
C	172242.9	109070.5	1	1	172242.9	109070.5	730.3	234.1	< 0.001**	< 0.001**
D	78434.9	66540.2	1	1	78434.9	66540.2	332.6	142.8	< 0.001**	< 0.001**
E	12596.0	5074.5	1	1	12596.0	5074.5	53.4	10.9	< 0.001**	0.0017**
AB	2632.9	520.7	1	1	2632.9	520.7	11.2	1.1	0.0015**	0.2950
A ²	361.5	9908.4	1	1	361.5	9908.4	1.5	21.3	0.2209	< 0.001**
B ²	39.8	160.2	1	1	39.8	160.2	0.2	0.3	0.6828	0.5600
C ²	484.0	7044.8	1	1	484.0	7044.8	2.1	15.1	0.1576	< 0.001**
D ²	25528.0	18439.0	1	1	25528.0	18439.0	108.2	39.6	< 0.001**	< 0.001**
E ²	8763.8	4796.8	1	1	8763.8	4796.8	37.2	10.3	< 0.001**	0.0022**
Residual	12971.7	25620.0	55	55	235.8	465.8				
Lack of Fit	12801.1	25331.4	53	53	241.5	478.0	2.8	3.3	0.2960	0.2594
Total	318210.0	306088.3	66	66						

a)

b)

Figure 5.20: Actual versus predicted values of (a) Bent and (b) Mt

The multiple regression analysis based on FFED was obtained using the optimum values of variables studied using second-order polynomial equations. The graphs in Figure 5.21 suggest a close interrelationship between the experimental data and expected responses and shows better results for the BG-Bent system compared to the BG-Mt system. Figure 5.21 suggests a close interrelationship between the experimental data and expected responses. While developing the regression equation, A, B, C, D, E, AB, D² and E² (BG-Bent) and A, B, C, D, E, A², C², D² and E² (BG-Mt) were found to be significant model terms and rest of the variables were considered insignificant. In both the systems cross products AD, AE, BD, BE, BF, CD, CE, CF and DE were found to be zero and therefore were excluded to construct the regression equations. At the confidence interval of 95% and *p*-value < 0.05% the two systems, namely, BG-Bent and BG-Mt displayed *F*-values of 117.7 and 54.7; *R*² values of 61.5% and 62.2% and coefficient of variance (CV) of 8.7% and 13.9% respectively. The prospects of the values of *R*² and CV help to navigate into systematic analysis and snipping of unwanted design points based on parameters of interest to indicate the effect of the variable(s) on the adsorption capacity.

Analysis of 3D response surface plots and 2D contour plots showed maximum adsorption obtained by the statistical optimization experiments with adsorbent dosage 0.06 g L⁻¹, particle size 175 μM, orbital shaking 165 rpm at 20 °C for BG-Bent and BG-Mt systems were 801 mg g⁻¹ and 436 mg g⁻¹ at pH 5.18 and 5.60; initial dye concentration 950 mg L⁻¹ and 560 mg L⁻¹; adsorption time 237 min and 162 min respectively. The contour and surface plots illustrate the combined effect of two factors on the process of adsorption and the results are graphically presented in Figure 5.22 and Figure 5.23. In brief, the importance of statistical optimization of the process variables leads us to interesting results which help to commercialize the process.

Figure 5.21: 3D-surface plot and contour plot showing the variation of adsorption capacity with BG-Bent (a) time versus concentration, (b) time versus adsorbent dosage and (c) concentration versus pH

Figure 5.23: 3D-surface plot and contour plot showing the variation of adsorption capacity with BG-Mt (a) time versus concentration, (b) time versus adsorbent dosage and (c) concentration versus pH

5.9 Adsorption Process for Textile Industrial Effluents

The details about the composition of the TIE, sample collection, measurement of absorbance are described elsewhere [27]. Two separate 0.1% (w/v) BG dye solutions were prepared by dissolving 5 g each of the dye in 5-litre distilled water (Solution 1) and in 5-litre TIE (Solution 2). Preliminary investigations revealed that addition of fresh samples of the adsorbent in Solution 1 and 2 after every 15 min enhanced the efficiency of removal of the dye aqueous matrices. The results are in conformance with our observations of adsorption kinetics where the solute adsorbs rapidly onto the surface of the clay particles forming a film. The process of adsorption gets delayed due to diffusion bringing changes in the adsorption rates. To augment the scale of operation, the experiments were performed using 1, 2 and 5 L of Solution 1 taken in polyethylene beakers containing 0.5, 1.0, and 5.0 g of Bent respectively. The polyethylene beakers were placed on three different magnetic stirrers and the solutions were agitated as per the procedure described above. The experiments were repeated with Solution 2 and Bent. The dye adsorbed Bent was separated by filtration and washed with distilled water until the filtrate was colorless. The powder was air-dried and sieved through 177 μ m mesh. The resultant powder is referred to as dye-modified Bent (dmBent) powder. Similar experiments were carried out using Mt for Solution 1 and Solution 2. Mean of the results of the three experiments did not exceed $\pm 2\%$ error. The percent recovery of 99%, 87% and 85% Bent, Mt and K respectively was observed from Solution 2 after 30 min. The photographs of the solutions are shown in Figure 5.24.

Figure 5.24: Color of the solutions after adsorption: 1. Distilled water; 2. BG dye in distilled water; 3. TIE; 4. BG dye in TIE; 5. Colour of the filtrate after 30 min adsorption (a) Bent (b) Mt and (c) K

5.10 Studies on Composites

High Density Polyethylene/dye unmodified bentonite (HDPE/dmBent) composites were prepared by melt compounding of master batches that were premixed by dry-blending in a tumble mixer and by extrusion of HDPE resin with different proportions of dmBent. HDPE granules and/or recycled product and dmBent master batch flakes were compounded using twin screw extruder. The specimens were prepared by cutting the extrudates strands into pellets and were tested for physico-mechanical and chemical properties. The procedure was repeated with dye unmodified montmorillonite K10 (dmMt) and Kaolinite (dmK). The results were encouraging.

5.11 Conclusion

The adsorption capacity of Bent, Mt and K obtained from the quadratic model developed for process optimization gave values of 801 mg g^{-1} and 436 mg g^{-1} and follows Toth's isotherm. The kinetic, mechanistic and thermodynamic studies confirm that the process is physisorption and follows second-order kinetics with a multi-step diffusion route. A broad range of pH 4 to 10 for the remediation of BG dye on Bent and Mt is encouraging. The high removal efficiency among studied clay minerals, followed the order Bent > Mt >>> K. The dye-adsorbed Bent and Mt minerals obtained as "sludge" can be used as filler/reinforcing materials for the fabrication of composites using plastic waste. The detailed study on the composites is in progress in our laboratory. In brief, two major conclusions are drawn from our study. First, the experimental design of the present study align with one of the facets of circular economy which encourages the waste and/or by-product of one process as resource material for the other and second, the research on the unmodified adsorbent needs to be encouraged which fits in to low-budget operational cost of the treatment of the industrial effluents.

5.12 References

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Chapter 6

PHOTOCATALYTIC DEGRADATION OF DYE USING NiO/CdS–CNT NANOCOMPOSITES

Nanomaterials are presently the best suitable materials for dye degradation compare to any other materials due their large surface area. Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are capable nanomaterials for boosting this application due to its numerous interesting adsorption characteristics. Metal nanoparticles like TiO₂, NiO, CdSe, CdS, etc. were found to have dye-degrading capacity comparably higher than others of the same kind because of their catalytic action and stability. NiO and CdS were opted for their fascinating degrading capabilities. These metal nanoparticles incorporated CNT based nanocomposites are found to have more conductivity and photocatalytic activity that contributes to the Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOP) which in turn enhances the degradation of dyes like methyl violet, methyl orange, congo red in the existence of UV/Visible light. In this work, the synthesized CdS–NiO nanoparticles are blended with CNT to get the composite. This novel composite showed effective photocatalytic degradation of methyl violet dye.

6.1 Introduction

6.1.1 Pollution

The surroundings we live in described as environment. Environment is a keen factor of survival for all the living beings, any change in the natural balance causes major effect on the species through various forms. A major concern about the environment is pollution. Pollution is regularly classified as point source and non-point source. Pollution is defined as the activity or phenomenon which contaminates the environment. Various major factors like growth in population, industrial waste, vehicles, natural calamities, etc. are the factors for rapid increase in the pollution rate. This had prominently caused an ill effect on the ecosystem. The major pollutions are air pollution, water pollution, soil pollution, and noise pollution [1]. The Textile Industrial Effluent (TIE) can contribute significant amount of toxic dyes to water bodies and also can pollute soil. Dye degradation is very important issue to be concerned for better environment and sustainability.

6.1.2 Effects of dyes

The products after the outcome of results are being thrown out to water, thus water sources get contaminated. Aquatic lives are also being in threat due to the pollution. The dyes which sustains in water, causes serious health hazards to the living being like cancer, tumor, cholera etc. The degradation of these dyes is the only source of solution since the removal of these is complicated in a large scale [2]. The colour of the material becomes permanent. Aquatic lives are also in threat due to the presence of these dyes. The only possible solution for this issue is initiating the large scale degradation of these dyes present in water bodies [2].

6.1.3 Nanotechnology and dye degradation

Nanotechnology, an emerging field of science is revolutionizing every field with its amazing characteristics. Nanomaterials are gaining world's attention due to their amazing properties which makes them excellent candidates in any applications compare to bulk materials. Dye degradation process can be boosted with high surface area of materials and nanomaterials has got higher surface to volume ratio. This high surface to volume ratio makes nanomaterials excellent and promising candidates for faster and favorable dye

degradation process [3, 4]. In this regard, nano materials are presently amongst the highly preferable of the materials that can be used for degradation of dye [5].

6.1.4 Carbon nano tube (CNTs)

Metal oxide nano particle incorporated CNT based nano composite are found to have more conductivity and photocatalytic activity that enhances the degradation of dyes like Methylene Blue, Methylene Orange, Congo Red, etc. in the presence of light. The electron transfer in the nano material/CNT composites reduces the electron-hole recombination and increases the photon efficiency and the convenient dye-degradation mechanisms. On detailed research, it was found that certain nano materials like TiO₂, NiO, CdSe, CdS were found to have dye-degrading capacity comparably higher than other materials of the same kind due to their catalytic activity and stability [6].

6.1.5 Nanoparticle and composite

To offer a better solution for dye degradation, the benefits of two individual materials were put together to make a composite. In order to make such a composite, a metal nano particle and carbon nanotube combination was preferred. Thus NiO/CNT composite was chosen. Considering the benefits of photocatalysis in waste water treatment and the need for high quality, large scale NiO nanostructures has to be produced but in a cost effective manner. The result of this main objective leads to the deployment of chemical precipitation method to produce materials for technological applications [5, 7].

6.1.6 Methyl violet

The dye predominantly available and causing very severe damages to living beings includes methyl violet, methyl orange, methyl blue, rhodamine B, etc. Out of these the most toxic and abundantly polluting dyes was chosen for testing the degradation using the nano composites.

Thus incorporating the benefits of metal nano particles and carbon nano tubes the composite material was made to enhance the degradation of industrial dye in a much simpler environment and in a cost effective manner [8].

6.1.7 Objectives

- To synthesize nickel oxide nanoparticles by chemical precipitation method
- To synthesize cadmium sulphide nanoparticles by chemical precipitation method
- To make NiO-CNT nanocomposites for degradation of the dye
- To make CdS-CNT nanocomposites for degradation of the dye
- To prepare stock solution of methylene violet
- To carry out dye degradation tests
- To prepare dye solutions of different concentrations
- To add different quantity of composites to each of the different concentrations of the dye
- To expose the NiO-CNT nanocomposites introduced sample to UV irradiation on constant stirring.
- To expose the CdS-CNT nanocomposites introduced sample to light radiation upon strong stirring
- To observe the colour change in the dye sample due to degradation of the dye molecules

6.2 Materials and Methods

6.2.1 Materials

The materials used for dye degradation process are Nickel nitrate ($\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$), Sodium hydroxide (NaOH), Cadmium nitrate ($\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$), Sodium sulphide ($\text{Na}_2\text{S} \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$), Ethanol ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$), Methanol (CH_3OH), Glucose, Deionised water (DW) and Methylene Violet (MV).

Methyl violet belongs to organic compounds and colour can be manipulated by methyl groups attached. MV is mostly utilized as purple dye for textile industry and also it is used in paint and ink [9].

Figure 6.1: Chemical structure of methyl violet

6.2.2 Synthesis of nanoparticles

Synthesis of nanoparticles was done by chemical precipitation method.

6.2.2.1 Nickel oxide nanoparticles

The Nickel oxide nanoparticles were produced by chemical precipitation method. Two different samples were prepared; one with 8.7 g of Ni(NO₃)₂ in 60 mL of DW and other with 3 g of NaOH in 150 mL of DW. 1 g of surfactants is added to sodium hydroxide solution. The NaOH sample was added drop wise into the Ni(NO₃)₂ sample on strong stirring.

The combined solution is subjected to magnetic stirrer with 1000 rpm at 37°C. The solution turned green colour is then subjected to filtration and washed frequently with DW and ethanol. The purified sample is now dried at 50°C for 1 day followed by calcinations at 450°C for 120 minutes.

The synthesis mechanism is given as follows:

6.2.2.2 Cadmium sulphide nanoparticles

The Cadmium sulphide nanoparticles were also produced by the simple chemical precipitation method. Two different samples were prepared; one with 1.54 g of Cd(NO₃)₂.xH₂O in 50 mL of DW and other with 0.39 g of Na₂S.9H₂O in 50 mL of DW. Next, the prepared sodium sulphide solution was added drop wise into the cadmium nitrate solution. The addition of the sodium sulphide to the cadmium nitrate solution was accompanied by strong stirring in order to avoid the agglomeration of the particles. 50 mL of 0.1 M glucose was prepared and added to the Cadmium sulphide solution as a capping agent after the synthesis procedure.

In order to facilitate strong stirring, the solution is then subjected to magnetic stirrer at 1000 rpm at 37°C during the dropwise addition of sodium sulphide to the cadmium nitrate solution. The colour of the sample changes from transparent to pale yellow to dark tangy yellow colour.

The resultant yellow solution is then subjected to filtration, and then washed with DW and ethanol for several times which is followed by methanol to remove the impurities and other by-products (Figure 6.2). The surfactants were discarded after the synthesis by

continuous washing and filtering and the filtrate is acquired. The filtrate was then dried at 100°C for 20 minutes using a hot plate.

Figure 6.2: Filtered with a) deionised water, b) ethanol and c) methanol

The synthesis mechanism is given as follows:

6.2.2.3 NiO nanoparticle

The stock solution of the preferred dye (methylene violet) was prepared by taking 0.2g of methyl violet dye and dissolving it in 100 mL of distilled water. The absorbance range for this stock solution was measured by using UV spectroscopy. Then 0.5 mL of the prepared dye solution was taken and to this NiO-CNT nanocomposite was added. Then the absorbance reading was taken for every five minutes for half an hour for sample 1 and for every 10 minutes for sample 2 under UV spectroscopy.

6.2.2.4 CdS nanoparticle

Similarly, the stock solution of the preferred dye (methylene violet) was prepared by taking 0.2 g of methyl violet dye and dissolving it in 100 mL of distilled water. The absorbance range for this stock solution was measured by using UV spectroscopy. Then 0.5 mL of the prepared dye solution was taken and to this Cadmium Sulphide - CNT nanocomposites was added. Then the absorbance reading was taken for five minutes for half an hour for sample 1 and for every 10 minutes for sample 2 under UV spectroscopy.

6.2.2.5 Metal oxide nanoparticles-CNT nanocomposites

The benefits of two individual nanomaterials were put together to make this composite. The metal nanoparticle incorporation with CNT to make it a nanocomposite can be achieved in two ways: Solid State Reaction and Ultrasonication.

6.2.2.6 NiO-CNT nanocomposites

The carbon nanotubes used are single walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNT) which is the product of Ad-nano company with the purity greater than 95%. The CNTs are heated at 350°C for 2 hours before composite preparation to remove the impurities. The nickel oxide - single walled carbon nanotubes nanocomposites were prepared by taking nickel oxide nanoparticles and carbon nanotubes in equal proportion. They are then placed in a crucible and mixed and placed in a furnace at a temperature of 400°C for 2 hours in order for the solid state reaction to take place to form the composite. The other suitable method used for making the composite is the ultrasonication method. In this equal proportion of CNT and NiO nanoparticles were taken and dissolved 5 mL of the solvent and ultrasonicated for 1 hour.

6.2.2.7 CdS-CNT nanocomposites

The cadmium sulphide-single walled carbon nanotubes nanocomposites were prepared by taking cadmium sulphide nanoparticles and carbon nanotubes in equal proportion. They are then placed in a crucible and mixed and placed in a furnace at a temperature of 450°C for 2 hours in order for the solid state reaction to take place to form the CdS CNT nanocomposite. The other suitable method used for making the composite is the ultra-sonication method. In this equal proportion of CNT and CdS nanoparticles were taken and dissolved 5 mL of the solvent and ultrasonicated for 1 hour.

6.2.2.8 Dye degradation test procedures

The mixture of nanoparticles and dye solution was subjected to UV rays and data was collected and observed that the absorption bands was decreasing with respect to time and disappeared gradually, representing the destruction of its chromophoric structure in the vicinity. It was noted by increasing the time with the nanoparticle the degradation were completed.

6.2.2.9 Characterization

The structural characterization was carried out by XRD, the morphological study was done by FESEM (Carl Zeiss sigma, Germany), the composition analysis was performed by EDAX (Carl Zeiss sigma, Germany) and Dye degradation was monitored by using Double beam UV spectrophotometer (Systronics 2202, India).

6.3 Results and Discussions

6.3.1 XRD results of NiO nanoparticles

The prepared NiO nanoparticles were characterized using XRD. The characteristic x-ray diffraction pattern of NiO nanoparticles, generated in a typical XRD analysis provides a unique “fingerprint” of the crystals present in the sample. The peaks positions are readily indexed as (111), (200), (220), (311), and (222) crystal planes of the NiO (Figure 6.3).

Figure 6.3: XRD analysis of NiO nanoparticles

All these diffraction peaks can be perfectly indexed face centered cubic (FCC) crystalline structure peak position, both in peak position and in relative intensity of the characteristic peaks, which is in accordance with that of the standard spectrum [10].

Table 6.1: XRD data

No.	2 - Theta (deg)	d (ang.)	Height (cps)	FWHM (deg)	Int. I (cps deg)
1	36.7	2.44	2957.9	0.80	3309.5
2	42.8	2.11	5034.1	0.86	5861.9
3	62.4	1.49	2118.5	1.13	3181.8
4	74.9	1.27	696.9	1.29	1193.2
5	78.9	1.21	504.9	1.38	924.4

The peaks positions are readily indexed as (111), (200), (220), (311), and (222) crystal planes of the NiO. Crystalline size calculated is nearly in the range of ~23nm (Scherrer formula). All these diffraction peaks can be perfectly indexed FCC crystalline structure peak position, both in peak position & in relative intensity of the characteristic peaks, which is in accordance with that of the standard spectrum (JCPDS, No. 04-0835).

6.3.2 FESEM (CdS nanoparticles)

FESEM analysis was carried out at Mangalore University, Mangalore, Karnataka. Size of the nanoparticles was calculated using IMAGE J software. The FESEM images (Figure 6.4) obtained shows that the average size of the prepared CdS nanostructures was found to be nearly 19 nm.

Figure 6.4: FESEM result for CdS nanoparticles

The method utilized to calculate the size was by the Image J software were the size of individual sphere was calculated (Table 6.2). Same procedure was repeated and average value of five particles is taken.

Table 6.2: SEM data

No.	Size (nm)
1	25
2	20
3	20
4	15
5	15

Therefore,

$$\text{Average} = [(25+20+20+15+15)/5] = 19 \text{ nm}$$

Average size of CdS nanoparticles ~ 19 nm

6.3.3 EDAX (CdS nanoparticles)

EDAX result shows (Figure 6.5) the composition and weight of cadmium and sulphate in the nanoparticles synthesized. It shows (Figure 6.6) that CdS composition is more i.e, 53.84% and sulphate as 46.16%.

Figure 6.5: EDAX result

Figure 6.6: EDAX elemental composition

Table 6.3: EDAX data

Element	Composition (%)	Weight (%)
Cd	53.84	6.95
S	46.16	1.70

6.3.4 UV-Vis spectroscopy (CdS nanoparticles)

UV-Vis absorption and transmittance spectrum of as synthesized CdS nanoparticles was measured. The reading shows (Figure 6.7) that the absorbance of CdS nanoparticles is nearly 460-490 nm.

Figure 6.7: UV-Vis spectroscopy (CdS nanoparticles)

6.3.5 Dye degradation test

Steps carried on for addition of NiO-CNT nanocomposite to 0.5 mL dye solution were:

6.3.5.1 Dye degradation test on addition of NiO-CNT nanocomposite

The solution was changed from blue colour to colorless solution and the absorbance was considerably decreasing for every 5 minutes.

By taking 0.5 mL of solution:

- The absorbance of the stock solution of 0.5 mL was found to be 1.39 (Figure 6.8).
- The time vs absorbance was shown in the Figure 6.9.
- The absorbance of the solution on addition of 0.2 gm composite was 1.32 (Figure 6.10 a).
- The absorbance of the solution after 10 minutes was found to be 0.94 (Figure 6.10 b).
- Absorbance of the solution after 20 minutes was found to be 0.76 (Figure 6.10 c).
- Absorbance of the solution after 30 minutes was found to be 0.50 (Figure 6.10 d).

Figure 6.8: Absorbance graph for 0.5 ml stock solution (NiO-CNT nanocomposite)

Table 6.4: Absorbance readings for 0.5 mL of dye solution NiO-CNT composites

Time	Absorbance
0	1.32
5	1.4
10	0.94
15	0.82
20	0.76
25	0.60
30	0.50

Figure 6.9: Time vs absorbance graph (0.5 mL)

Figure 6.10: 0.5mL dye solution. Absorbance graph for (a) 0 minutes (b) 10 minutes (c) 20 minutes (d) 30 minutes

By taking 1mL of solution:

- The absorbance of the stock solution was found to be 2.75 (Figure 6.11).
- Absorbance of the solution after 0 minutes was found to be 1.38 (Figure 6.12 a).
- Absorbance of the solution after 10 minutes was found to be 1.15 (Figure 6.12 b).
- Absorbance of the solution after 20 minutes was found to be 1.10 (Figure 6.12 c).
- Absorbance of the solution after 30 minutes was found to be 1.06 (Figure 6.12 d).
- Time vs absorbance relation for 1 mL solution is shown in Figure 6.13.

Figure 6.11: Absorbance graph for 1mL stock solution (NiO-CNT nanocomposite)

Table 6.5: Absorbance readings for 1 mL of dye solution NiO-CNT composites

Time	Concentration (cc)
0	1.38
5	1.32
10	1.15
15	1.14
20	1.10
25	1.10
30	1.06

Figure 6.12: 1mL dye solution. Absorbance graph for (a) 0 minutes (b) 10 minutes (c) 20 minutes (d) 30 minutes

Figure 6.13: Time vs absorbance graph (1 mL)

6.3.5.2 Dye degradation test on addition of CdS-CNT nanocomposite

Steps carried on for addition of CdS-CNT nanocomposite to 0.5 mL dye solution were: The colour of the solution has changed from blue to colourless solution and the absorbance was considerably decreasing for every 5 minutes.

- The absorbance of the stock solution of 0.5 mL was found to be 1.532 (Figure 6.14).
- The absorbance of the solution by the addition of 0.2 gm of composite was found to be 0.443 (Figure 6.15 a).
- The absorbance of the solution was found to be 0.404 (Figure 6.15 b).
- The absorbance of the solution was found to be 0.384 (Figure 6.15 c).
- The absorbance of the solution was found to be 0.366 (Figure 6.15 d).
- Time vs absorbance relation for 0.5 mL CdS solution shown in Figure 6.16.

Figure 6.14: Absorbance graph for 0.5 mL stock solution (CdS-CNT nanocomposite)

Figure 6.15: 0.5 mL dye solution. Absorbance graph for (a) 0 minutes (b) 10 minutes (c) 20 minutes (d) 30 minutes

Table 6.6: Absorbance readings for 0.5 mL of dye solution CdS-CNT composites

Time	Absorbance
0	00.443
5	00.420
10	00.404
15	00.398
20	00.384
25	00.376
30	00.366

Figure 6.16: Time vs absorbance graph [CdS (0.5 mL)]

From the UV results for 0.5mL and 1 mL for both NiO-CNT nanocomposites and CdS-CNT nanocomposites following were observed:

In case of addition of NiO-CNT nanocomposites to both 0.5 mL and 1 mL of stock dye solution, the absorbance decreases with time indicating the degradation of dye. On addition of CdS-CNT nanocomposites to 0.5 mL of stock dye solution, the absorbance decreases faster with time as degradation occurs faster.

Comparing these, both yields similar results but the rate of degradation is faster in CdS-CNT nanocomposites when compared to NiO-CNT nanocomposites.

6.3.5.3 Primary confirmation

The colour change was observed from blue to colourless (Figure 6.17) by the UV irradiation which was one of the primary confirmations of dye degradation.

Figure 6.17: Colour change from violet to colourless

On comparing the efficacy of both the nanoparticles, the results were almost similar, except the CdS nanoparticles shows faster degradation rates when compared to the NiO nanoparticles.

6.4 Conclusion

Through our project we are aiming for a simple process that favours the environment for the degradation of dye. This possibility of clearing the environment will dictate the success of nanotechnology in environmental remediation. Using carbon nano tubes will greatly influence the conductivity of the nanoparticle thereby initiating the photocatalysis process for degradation of industrial dye. By the outcome of the successful results, this will help us to find a solution for the contamination of water. Keeping the key factor of side effects of nanoparticles which again is an area of concern, research works on the toxic effects is still going on. The dissolution of nano particles and the later consumption or utilization has paid to rise for many ethical issues. On the other hand the toxic effect of the heavy metal

nanoparticles can be eliminated by functionalization of the nanoparticles which will bind and react with the toxic reactive groups and make it non-reactive. Functionalization is the attachment of any group like sulphates, phosphates, alcohol groups, etc. to the nanoparticles for decreasing the toxic effect of nanoparticles. Researches are widely going on this area of concern to reduce the toxic effects of the nanoparticles. But the level of toxicity produced by these is lesser when compared to that of the dyes in the water bodies.

6.5 References

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CHAPTER 7

AZOBENZENE DYE-SENSITIZED SOLAR CELLS USING TITANIUM DIOXIDE NANOPARTICLES AND CNT

7.1 Introduction

7.1.1 Solar cells

Solar cell (SC) works based on photoelectric effect wherein light energy can be converted into electrical energy. These cells can be building blocks to creating a solar panel which has over 100-1000 of solar cells integrated on the panel. Regardless of the source, i.e. sunlight or any artificial light, they are termed as photovoltaic. They have found wide applications in the sensor industries as photo detectors used in detecting electromagnetic radiations, light in the visible range or for measuring light intensity [1].

Silicon is one of the important for raw materials required in the manufacturing of solar cell; it is the same materials are used in integrated circuits and transistors. Silicon helps in the release of electrons after receiving sunlight. There are totally almost four generations of solar cells, this has allowed us to use various classes of solar cells based on our requirement and preferences. Types of the different generation of solar cells are First generation SCs, Second generation SCs, Third generation SCs and Fourth generation SCs [2].

7.1.2 Dye sensitized solar cells (DSSCs)

The DSSCs fall under third generation SCs which has got special importance interms of few drawback of 1st and 2nd generation SCs. DSSCs are capable of overcoming the Shockley-queisser barrier for single bad gap SCs. This provides a range of alternating technology to the semiconductor devices and the thin film cells. DSSC's cells provide better absorption, high frequency switch, hot carrier outcomes, and multiple carrier junction ejection techniques [2].

The DSSCs has been driven scientists interest because of their interesting properties; the fabrication is simple and can be adopted traditional roll-printing practices, DSSC is semi-

flexible and semi-transparent that offers higher options than the glass-based system. Noble metal and metal has been utilized in DSSC and is irreplaceable no matter its price, and also the liquid solution presents a heavy challenge to creating a cell appropriate to be used all told weather. Though its conversion potency is a smaller amount than the most effective thin-film cells, in theory, its price/performance quantitative relation ought to be ok to permit them to vie with fuel electrical generation by achieving grid parity [3].

Nanotechnology can help in fabrication of DSSCs and also it can boost its stability which is one of the major drawback of DSSCs. Nanomaterials can be used as anode and cathode components and also dyes like Azobenzene can be coated on the surface of SCs effectively by using nanofabrication processes like dip coating, spin coating, atomic layer deposition etc. As the surface area is more for nanomaterials which will become very important aspect for energy conversion, more the surface more atoms will be exposed and hence more reactivity leading to more faster and effective conversion of light energy into electrical energy [4].

Conventional DSSCs experienced degradation once they were exposed to UV radiation, this can be overcome by using additional layer which act as an effective barrier.

The barrier layer might embrace UV stabilizers and/or UV light absorbing luminescent chromo-phores and antioxidants to safeguard and increase the efficiency of the solar cells [5]. DSSCs are proven to be more effective 3rd generation solar cells and has got better efficiency than others which makes them competitive candidates with potential applications [6]. The key drawback to the DSSCs fabrication is the liquid electrolyte which is very unstable at different temperatures. The significant amount of research is going on to solve this issue which includes replacing liquid electrolyte with solid [7].

Nanomaterials like TiO₂, ZnO, SiO₂, CdS, CNTs, and so on will help conventional DSSCs to overcome their drawbacks and currently amazing outcomes with high efficiency, better stability and durability has been reported in several of the studies [8].

7.2 Materials and Methods

7.2.1 Materials

The following materials were used for our project. All the chemicals were purchased from Merck Chemical Reagent Co. Ltd. India.

The materials are used here are nitrobenzene, NaOH, ethanol, methanol, zinc dust, HCl, titanium iso-propoxide, iso-propanol, nitric acid, TUBALL™ BAT H₂O. The materials prepared for fabrications are CNTs, TiO₂ nanoparticles, azobenzene, conductive glasses and Fluorine-doped Tin Oxide (FTO).

7.2.1.1 Azobenzene

Azobenzene may be a chemical compound composed of 2 phenyl rings linked by an N=N double bond. It's the simplest example of an aryl azo compound. The Azobenzene is derived from diazenes that absorb light robustly and utilized as dyes in a several industries [9].

Figure 7.1: Structure of Azobenzene

7.2.1.2 TUBALL™ BATT

TUBALL™ BATT is a dispersion of single wall carbon nanotubes in NMP or water. It is a ready-to-use dispersion designed to easily incorporate TUBALL™ into electrode formulations during the battery manufacturing process. TUBALL™ BATT provides a complete or partial substitute for carbon black in battery electrodes and can replace several percent of carbon black with 0.03-0.05% of TUBALL™.

TUBALL™ BATT forms conductive 3D networks between active material particles at very low concentrations. It reinforces the electrode structure and improves its mechanical stability during cycling. It also progress linkage by creating strong bond between the particles, decreasing the quantity of binder needed.

7.2.2 Methods

7.2.2.1 Preparation of TiO₂ nanoparticles

TiO₂ was synthesised as follows: The ratio of the chemicals to be added should be in 1 (IPA): 10 (TTIP): 1 (HNO₃): 0.2 (H₂O). To prepare a 50 mL of this solution, we should

take the ratio of 4: 40: 4: 0.8 for the above mentioned chemicals. In a beaker 4 mL of isopropanol is added. Then 10 mL of Titanium isopropoxide added to the beaker, along with 4 mL of concentrated HNO₃ in it. Shake a little and add 0.8 mL of water in it. This mixture is later stirred at 200 rpm in a magnetic stirrer with constant temperature for 3 hours. After stirring the solution was left for ageing for 48 hours. The aged gel was then sintered at 600°C for 3 hours. The powder was collected and sent for characterization.

7.2.2.2 Preparation of TiO₂ – CNT composite

The procedure is initiated by preparing TiO₂ nanoparticles in the beginning and later Carbon Nanotubes is incorporated.

To synthesize Titanium dioxide (TiO₂): The ratio of the chemicals to be added should be in 1 (IPA): 10 (TTIP): 1 (HNO₃): 0.2 (H₂O). To prepare a 50 mL of this solution, we should take the ratio of 4: 40: 4: 0.8 for the above mentioned chemicals. In a beaker 4 mL of isopropanol is added. Then 10 mL of Titanium isopropoxide added to the beaker, along with 4 mL of concentrated HNO₃ in it. Shake a little and add 0.8 mL of water in it. This mixture is later stirred at 200 rpm in a magnetic stirrer with constant temperature for 1 hour.

In the meantime, TUBALL™ 75% Single walled carbon nanotubes were weighed around 0.21 g. CNT was added to the mixture after 1 hour of stirring inside the beaker. Again it was stirred for next 3 hours to make a perfect blend of TiO₂-CNT composite. Then after stirring was stopped, the beaker which contains the composite is kept 24 hours of aging. After 1 day, the blended mixture is baked at 80°C for 30 mins. Final product obtained after baking was sintered using the muffle furnace with a temperature of 600°C. Hence, the final product of TiO₂-CNT composite powder was observed. Confirmation of its presence was done using FE-SEM and EDAX.

7.2.2.3 Synthesis of azobenzene

The preparation of azobenzene is done as follows: A round bottomed flask was taken, in that 200 mL of nitrobenzene (2M) was added. To this, 150 mL of methanol was added and shake it a little. A solution of 32.4 g of sodium hydroxide in 100 mL of distilled water is prepared. This solution is added to the flask. To this mixture, zinc dust of 26.84 g is mixed. The flask in which these chemicals are added are later fitted with stirrer and reflux condenser. It is then refluxed for 3 hours at 600 rpm. The temperature was kept constant. After 3 hours, the mixture was filtered while hot, and the precipitate of sodium zincate was

observed. This sodium zincate is washed on the filter with a warm methanol. All the methanol is distilled from the filtrate. The obtained filtrate is then separated in beaker. The residue obtained is chilled using a chiller or refrigerator. The final product obtained is the azobenzene crystals. Colour of the filtrate was found to be yellowish orange colour. Confirmation was done using UV- spectroscopy.

7.2.2.4 Preparation of conductive glasses

The preparation of conductive glass slides is done as follows: Take a normal glass slide and check for the conductivity using the multimeter. Take a glass slide and place it behind the watch glass. Use tapes to stick one side of the glass slide. Using spatula, take few quantity of TUBALL™ BATT and add few drops on one end of the slide (Figure 7.2). Using another glass slide, gently swipe from the point of the drops to the other end. Keep it for drying for some time and check for conductivity (Figure 7.3). To get more thickness, one can do multiple swipes on the glass slide or single swipe will be enough.

Figure 7.2: The glass slide with single swipe of TUBALL™ BATT upon the glass surface

Figure 7.3: The conductivity test using multimeter. (a) Indicates a glass slide without any coating. (b) Indicates a glass slide with multiple coatings of TUBALL™ BATT. (c) Glass slide with a single coating of BATT

Figure 7.4: The resistivity test of each slide with TUBALL™ BATT coating and without coating

7.2.2.5 Assembly of solar cell

The dye sensitised solar cell was assembled as follows: The conductive glasses were checked for the conductive side. The conductive side should face each other. One side of the glass was coated with TiO_2 -CNT composite using spin coating. The glass was placed in the spin coater and a few drops of TiO_2 -CNT were placed on it. The coating was done at 3000 rpm for 80 seconds. The other glass was coated with azobenzene dye mixed with methylene violet. This was also done using spin coater with the same time and speed as used for TiO_2 -CNT composite. Then both the coated glass was placed on top of each other with the coated sides facing each other. These were held using tapes. Iodine solution was added in between the two glasses. This acts as an electrolyte. The formed solar cell was then tested (Figure 7.5).

Figure 7.5: The assembled Dye Sensitized Solar Cell (DSSC)

7.2.2.6 Characterization studies

The structural characterization was carried out by XRD, the morphological study was done by FESEM (Carl Zeiss sigma, Germany), the composition analysis was performed by EDAX (Carl Zeiss sigma, Germany) and Dye degradation was monitored by using Double beam UV spectrophotometer (Systronics 2202, India).

7.3 Results and Discussion

7.3.1 XRD analysis

The synthesised TiO₂ nanoparticles were characterized using X-ray diffraction technique to get the phase and confirmation of presence of TiO₂. The peaks obtained (Figure 7.6) at 2 θ values are 27.3°, 38.92°, 50.05°, 54.21°, 62.55° corresponds to the crystal planes (101), (004), (200), (105), (204) respectively indicating the formation of anatase phase of TiO₂ were studied and TiO₂ nanoparticles. The crystal structure of TiO₂ was found out to be Face Centered Cubic (FCC) was confirmed from literature report [10].

Figure 7.6: XRD peaks obtained for TiO₂

7.3.2 UV-Vis spectroscopy

The UV-Vis spectroscopy reading obtained for the prepared azobenzene showed broad peak at 333 nm (Figure 7.7). This shows the absorbance of azobenzene at 2.3. This is the absorbance range of azobenzene and was confirmed by literature survey [11].

Figure 7.7: UV readings for Azobenzene

7.3.3 FESEM

The images obtained shows that SWCNT was blended well with TiO₂ nanoparticles. The resolution was varied from 1 μ m till 100 nm. The size of the TiO₂ was analysed to be at an average of 40-50 nm. Size of the particles was calculated using IMAGE J software.

Figure 7.8: Image showing the TiO₂ spherical particles of 40 nm-50 nm in diameter

Figure 7.9: Image showing the functionalization of SWCNT with TiO₂ nanoparticles at 1 μ m

Figure 7.10: FESEM image of TiO₂ at 200 nm

Figure 7.11: Image of SWCNT functionalized on TiO₂ nanoparticles at 200 nm

7.3.4 EDAX

EDAX was done on the TiO₂-CNT composite. From EDAX the composition of the mixture was analysed. The composition is as follows:

Table 7.1: EDAX chemical composition analysis

Element	Atomic %
O K	50.77
Ti K	23.84
C	25.39

Figure 7.12: EDAX image of SWCNT-TiO₂ at 200 μm

Figure 7.13: EDAX composition analysis

7.3.5 Solar cell testing and efficiency

Figure 7.14: a) Testing of voltage and b) Testing of current

The efficiency of the solar cell was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Efficiency } (\eta) = \frac{P_{\max}}{E \cdot A_c}$$

Where

P_{\max} = maximum power obtained

$$= V \times I = 3\text{mV} \times 0.052\text{mA} = 0.156 \text{ mW}$$

E = light intensity in W/cm^2

$$= \frac{\text{Power of light source (W)}}{\text{Distance between the illuminator } (D^2)} = 50\text{W}/(30)^2 = 0.055 \text{ W}/\text{cm}^2$$

A_c = surface area of the solar cell

$$= 100 \text{ cm}^2$$

$$\eta = \frac{0.156}{0.055 * 100} * 100 = \mathbf{2.83\%}$$

Therefore efficiency obtained is **2.83%**

7.4 Conclusion

TiO₂ nano particles were synthesised and confirmed using XRD. Later the synthesised TiO₂ nano particles were functionalized with SWCNT (75%) to get TiO₂-CNT composite. This was confirmed using FESEM and the particle size obtained was around 40-50 nm. The particles were in spherical shape for TiO₂ and Carbon nanotubes were bonded to TiO₂ nanoparticles. Azobenzene dye was synthesized and was characterized by UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Absorbance of azobenzene is 2.3 at 333 nm. The spectrum of wavelength seen in the graph of azobenzene is of broad peak. Conductive glasses were prepared using TUBALL™ batt which is a composition of carbon nanotubes and NMP with water. Due to high resistivity, it was not able to conduct. Conductive glass was purchased and the solar cell was assembled. The efficiency was calculated using the solar cell efficiency setup which uses sodium lamp. The efficiency was found to 2.83%

We conclude that by increasing the absorbance of the dye and by controlling the size distribution and functionalization of TiO₂-CNT we can increase the electrical property of the solar cell. Azobenzene dyes with some metal nanoparticles dissolved in it will enhance the photo isomerism. This would increase the efficiency of the solar cell.

7.5 References

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Chapter 8

MAJOR CONCLUSIONS AND SCOPE FOR FUTURE WORK

The global situation for humanity continues to improve, but it is at the expense of the environment. The world is in a race to implement different ways to improve the human conditions but at the same time there is seemingly ever-increasing complexity and scale of global problems. Essential focuses of the countries that have incorporated the culture of industrialization seem to focus on the aspects of generating waste-water and its necessity to treat and recycle it. One of the most hazardous substances discharged from industries is dyes, especially industrial dyes.

Textile industry has recognized itself as a well-established industry with its nuances of commercialization taking place since several decades. The nexus of structure–toxicology of the commercial dyes and their intermediates have been studied in-depth as they face the heat of the toxicity issues that surround the industrial sectors in view of the environmental concerns. This has results in the specific dyes either being withdrawn from the market or is subjected to strict regulations. The testing of toxicity of the dyes is now a common practice and due to which it is a rarity that any dye would be introduced in the problem that has any gray area of toxicity issues. However, the scenario is totally different in many developing countries where the banned chemicals and dyes are being used unabated. Of the existing conventional strategies for removing dyes from textile industrial effluents, adsorption is considered as the most efficient method. Among several adsorbents available in the market, the activated carbon is the most frequently used adsorbent; although the bottleneck for its application is the economical hurdle. The present study examines the alternatives such as Nano Clay (NC) minerals and Unmodified Clay Minerals (UCM). NC minerals and UCM have got significant scope. Until better alternatives to activated carbon are focused for the adsorption methods, use of abundantly available nanoclays and renewable low-cost renewable nutraceutical industrial spent generated in millions of tons annually will continue to be more preferred materials for remediation of synthetic dyes.

The major conclusions of the study include:

- First, minerals which are the part of soil have been used to remediate dyes that are toxic emerging from industrial effluents which otherwise will have an adverse effect on the soils.
- Second, the results of remediation of toxic dyes will have a tremendous impact on retaining the quality of soils by decreasing the formation of colloids from dyes which will have a negative impact on germination and growth of the plants.
- Third, the results of my research work demonstrates profound influence on retaining the quality of soils, by its least effect on physico-chemical characteristics, susceptibility to erode, reduced efficiency of production, sustainability with reduced food chain quality.
- Fourth, NC and UCM have been developed as efficient, environmental-friendly economically-viable adsorbent to remediate toxic dyes.
- Fifth, parameters involved in the operational process influenced the adsorption efficiency of NC and UCM.
- Sixth, the modelling studies confirmed the complex mechanisms involved in the isotherms and kinetics of the dye adsorption system.
- Seventh, studies on the thermodynamics validated the adsorption process to be spontaneous and endothermic in nature.
- Eighth, NC as alternate to activated carbon has better claim due to the least impact of carbon footprint on the planet.
- Ninth, an alternate to burning/incineration/landfills of UCM to reduce carbon footprint has been explored.
- Tenth, NC and UCM are ready-to-use matrices for the researchers focusing on the adsorption based studies.
- Eleventh, the author envisages that the concept proposed and the template developed associated with dwindling resources will create an alternate paradigm to transform “waste-to-wealth”.
- Twelfth, the authors investigated the dye remediation process by using nanomaterials.
- Thirteenth, an extended research was carried out on using toxic Azobenzene dye for commercial application through Dye Sensitized Solar Cells (DSSCs).

In today's environmentally focused society, the demand for cost-effective, environmentally friendly materials continue to increase. The ongoing research efforts are aimed at NC minerals and UCM as sustainable adsorbents. Although adsorption process studies are widely studied in various spheres of scientific research, it still faces the challenge to scale-up beyond laboratory studies. Thus, some more research outputs are necessitated to confirm its feasibility on industrial scale and the scope of further studies are summarized below:

- Scope to continue fundamental research to understand the mechanism(s) of adsorption and to know what drives the selectivity of biosorptive and bioaccumulatory processes.
- Scope to develop more advanced and robust models of isotherms and kinetic studies to simulate more complicated biosorption systems, such as hybrid biosorption system.
- Scope to investigate the synchronized mode for removing other pollutants in industrial effluents using more than one adsorbent.
- Scope to study comparatively the physicochemical properties of different kinds of pollutant dyes.
- Scope to understand the adsorption phenomena involved vis-à-vis chemical structure of the dye and adsorption capacities.
- Scope to find alternative to pretreatment chemical methods to enhance adsorptive capacity and specificity of the biomass to commensurate with the cost at large scale.
- Scope to reduce the overall cost for pretreatments and/or to develop new methods that are both cheap and effective.
- Scope to develop NC and UCM as efficient, environmentally friendly and economically viable hybrid-biosorbent for simultaneous single point remediation of almost all classes of dyes, metals and organics from the effluent.
- Scope to resolve complexity involved in dye adsorption mechanism.
- Scope to use NC and UCM and the dye adsorbed NC and UCM as potential filler materials in the fabrication of thermoplastics and thermosets composites by utilizing either virgin or waste synthetic polymer matrices.
- Scope for valorization of NC-plastics and UCM-plastic composites.
- Scope to use the studied materials for sustainability.
- Scope to reuse toxic dyes for commercial applications after remediation.
- Scope to use dyes for Solar Cells- Dye Sensitized Solar Cells (DSSs).

- Scope to merge nanotechnology with adsorption concept for better adsorption properties to improve environmental sustainability.

The extensive and untiring efforts of procuring dyes for an established textile industry resulted in the dye that are good, strong and varied colored has unfortunately resulted in a new technological problem: disposal of the dye. There is an uphill task for the degradation of the dyes while treating wastewater and subsequently, it is also difficult to tackle certain degraded products classified as toxic. Undoubtedly, there is a surge in the scientific community in gathering efforts to address the toxicology issues by channelizing strategies for the treating the dye effluents. For future work, attempts have to be made for obtaining an equilibrated solution that encompasses the physicochemical properties of the dyes and the targeted profile of degradation of dyes.

In summary, humans can continue to strive on this planet when the water management is effectively implemented. Due to several natural and man-made courses of actions, there is a wide scope to ensure the quality of water and to keep a check on the environmental pollution. This calls for a need to address the concerns of water consumption by having joint collaborations with the policy makers, water technologists and industrialists. The industrialists need to find sustainable ways to efficiently manage consumption of water and the water technologists need to explore sustainable and novel methods to integrate use, reuse and recycle of the available water. In a gist, a preferred strategy would be to minimize the waste at the point source rather than incorporating the traditional “end-of-pipe-waste-treatment” strategy.

In conclusion, the economic importance of the renewable resources has been neglected in most countries in the past. However, as their value becomes increasingly recognized for a multiplicity of uses, they represent a substantial potential source of renewable raw material for the future. It is univocally clear from the preceding chapters that UCM may represent a more realistic approach to the design of adsorbent systems. Thus, it will not be surprising if the coming few years will witness the growth – if not the dominance - of research on Nano Clay Minerals and Unmodified Clay Minerals.

Appendix A: Publication Records

Paper Published

Inter National Journals- (SCI, Peer Reviewed, Scopus indexed & UGC approved)

- 1 Shareef, J. U., Rani, M. N., Anand, S., & Rangappa, D. (2017). Synthesis and characterization of silver nanoparticles from *Penicillium* sps. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 4(11), 11923-11932.
- 2 Prasad, P., Ukkund, S. J., Abhinaya, N., & Savitha, M. B. (2017). A Comparative study of efficiency of CDS-SWCNT, and NIO-SWCNT nanocomposites for degradation of methyl violet, *International Journal of Advanced Research in Science & Engineering*, 6(8), 1-9.
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Paper published in conferences proceedings

Inter National conferences

- 1 The paper entitled “Synthesis and characterization of silver nanoparticles from *Fuzarium oxysporum* and investigation of their antibacterial activity” has been presented in the ‘International Conference on Green Methods and Synthesis of Nanomaterials’ [GMSP&NS’18] and published in Elsevier: *Materials Today: Proceedings*, Vol. 9, P3, pp. 506-514, 2019 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2018.10.369>
- 2 The paper entitled “Biosynthesis and characterization of silver nanoparticles from *penicillium notatum* and their application to improve efficiency of antibiotics” is presented in ‘3rd International Conference on Advances in Materials and Manufacturing Applications’ [IConAMMA_2018] and published in the Scopus indexed as a special issue in “IOP: Science, Conference Series” *Material Science Engineering*, Vol. 577, No. 1, 012002, 2019 <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/577/1/012002>
- 3 The paper entitled “Experimental investigation on synthesis, characterization and antibacterial properties of silver nanoparticles from *Nigella sativa* powder/oil and *Cinnamon zeylanicum* extract” is under review is a part of ‘International Conference on Emerging Trends in Mechanical Engineering’ [eTIME-2018] and published in the AIP Conference Proceedings 2080, 020001 (2019); <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5092884>
- 4 The paper entitled “Microwave assisted Green synthesis and characterization of silver nanoparticles from *Hibiscus* leaf and flower extract and investigation of their antimicrobial activities” is under review is a part of ‘International Conference on Emerging Trends in Mechanical Engineering’ [eTIME-2018] and published in the AIP Conference Proceedings 2080, 020002 (2019); <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5092885>
- 5 The paper entitled “Preparation of azobenzene dye-sensitised Solar cell using tio_2 -swcnt nanocomposites” presented in International Conference AScenD-2020 organized by Christ University, Bangalore published in *International Journal on Physical Sciences* 11 (1), 26-29.
- 6 The paper entitled “Rapid synthesis of silver nanoparticles from *Hibiscus* flower extract by microwave method and their antibacterial studies” presented in International Conference AScenD-2020 organized by Christ University, Bangalore published in *International Journal on Physical Sciences* 11 (1), 20-25.

- 7 The paper entitled "Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles from negilla Sativa seed extract and their antibacterial studies" presented in International Conference AScenD-2020 organized by Christ University, Bangalore published in *International Journal on Physical Sciences* 11 (1), 14-19.

Paper presented in conferences

Inter National conferences

- 1 Green synthesis and characterization of Aluminium Oxide Nanoparticles by neem extracts, Conference proceedings of International Conference on Advanced Ceramics and Nanomaterials for Sustainable Developments (ACEND-2018), Organized by CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru on 19th – 21st September 2018, page number 105
- 2 Synthesis and characterization of graphene oxide and its effects on stiffness modulus of GFRP composites, Conference proceedings of International Conference on Advanced Ceramics and Nanomaterials for Sustainable Developments (ACEND-2018), Organized by CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru on 19th – 21st September 2018, page number 105
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 - 31 The paper entitled “Synthesis and characterization of silver nanoparticles from *fuzarium oxysporum* and investigation of their antibacterial activity” has been presented in the ‘International Conference on Green Methods and Synthesis of Nanomaterials’ [GMSP&NS’18] and published in Elsevier: *Materials Today: Proceedings*, Vol. 9, P3, pp. 506-514, 2019 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2018.10.369>
 - 32 The paper entitled “Biosynthesis and characterization of silver nanoparticles from *penicillium notatum* and their application to improve efficiency of antibiotics” is presented in ‘3rd International Conference on Advances in Materials and Manufacturing Applications’ [IConAMMA_2018] and published in the Scopus indexed as a special issue in “IOP: Science, Conference Series” *Material Science Engineering*, Vol. 577, No. 1, 012002, 2019 <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/577/1/012002>
 - 33 The paper entitled “Experimental investigation on synthesis, characterization and antibacterial

properties of silver nanoparticles from *Nigella sativa* powder/oil and *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* extract” is under review is a part of ‘International Conference on Emerging Trends in Mechanical Engineering’ [eTIME-2018] and published in the AIP Conference Proceedings 2080, 020001 (2019); <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5092884>

- 34 The paper entitled “Microwave assisted Green synthesis and characterization of silver nanoparticles from Hibiscus leaf and flower extract and investigation of their antimicrobial activities” is under review is a part of ‘International Conference on Emerging Trends in Mechanical Engineering’ [eTIME-2018] and published in the AIP Conference Proceedings 2080, 020002 (2019); <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5092885>

Books Published

- 1 “Foundation of Nanoscale Science and Technology”, Lambert Academic Publisher, Germany, with ISBN: 978-613-9-58649-3.
- 2 “Nano-Electronics and Quantum Computation”, Lambert Academic Publisher, Germany, with ISBN: 978-613-9-81812-9
- 3 “Mechanical Operations”, LAP-Lambert Academic Publishes, Omni Scriptum Publishing group, Mauritius, 2018, with ISBN: 978-613-9-82579-0
- 4 “Synthesis of Nanomaterials”, Lambert Academic Publisher, Germany, with ISBN: 978-613-9-82137-2
- 5 “Biochemistry and Microbiology”, Lambert Academic Publisher, Germany, with ISBN: 978-613-9-83272-9.
- 6 “Synthesis & Processing Techniques” Lambert Academic Publisher, Germany, with ISBN: 978-613-9-81532-6
- 7 “Quantum Mechanics & Quantum Electronics” Lambert Academic Publisher, Germany, with ISBN: 978-620-0-55074-3
- 8 “Quantum Electronics & Quantum Computations” Lambert Academic Publisher, Germany, with ISBN: 978-620-0-55074-3

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Publication Statics

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Citations Received as on March 2021	55
h-index as on March 2021	05
Research Gate Score as on March 2021	11